

The HuT

Innovative policy/governance enablers for multi-risk DRR

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WP3 Governance and policy, T3.1 Enablers and barriers to multi-hazard/systemic risk reduction

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1.1. Document history

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2. Executive summary

As disasters driven by natural hazards grow more complex and interconnected, largely linked to the growing impacts of climate change, there is a clear need for more flexible and integrated approaches to Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR). The HuT project seeks to respond to this challenge by bringing together European research groups, institutions, and stakeholders to identify and promote DRR strategies that are grounded in multidisciplinary knowledge and real-world practice. It has the goal of supporting the development of tools and approaches that can be applied across distinct regions and types of hazards, strengthening community resilience over the long term. Through its demonstration sites, HuT seeks to ensure that lessons learned, and tools created are directly applied to real-world DRR efforts, bridging research and practice.

Developed under the framework of Work Package 3 (WP3): Governance and Policy, this deliverable identified innovative governance and policy enablers that support the adoption and implementation of multi-risk DRR strategies, with a particular focus on Nature-Based Solutions (NbS). They are presented as suggestions. Here, we broadly define governance/policy enablers as those aspects catalysing collective and networked decision-making, including the social, ecological, political, legal and financial conditions through which NbS are implemented. Emphasis was placed in NbS because of their well-known potential to reduce the risks of multiple hazards, provide co-benefits, and enhance ecosystem resilience in a sustainable way. Notably, rather than representing entirely novel approaches, NbS are often rooted in traditional knowledge and long-established practices.

The suggestions presented in section 9 of this document are informed by relevant literature and the analyses conducted at three of The HuT demonstration sites: Valencia, Spain (DEM1), Ogliastra, Italy (DEM8), and Bern, Switzerland (DEM10), each characterized by different hazards, risk profiles and institutional settings. All three case studies investigated the barriers and enablers associated with the implementation of NbS to address specific environmental challenges. In Valencia, the analysis focused on the governance conditions influencing the implementation of NbS to enhance urban climate resilience, particularly addressing urban heatwaves, droughts, and urban flooding through urban green and blue infrastructure projects, such as parks, green corridors, and riverbed restorations. In Ogliastra, the primary focus was on locally adapted fire risk management, examining barriers and enablers for wildfire reduction and climate change adaptation, while also considering the impact of droughts. Finally, the case of Bern explored governance challenges and enabling factors related to the management and conservation of protection forests, as well as the implementation of the PROTECTpraxis guidelines, addressing a wide range of mountain hazards such as avalanches, rockfalls, landslides, and the movement of water and sediments in watercourses.

Guided by a common analytical framework (described in section 8.1), the methods employed are as follows:

- Ogliastra: Three participatory sessions were conducted, including:
 - A workshop with local administrators and representatives from territorial and regional entities involved in wildfire risk management (N=19);
 - A workshop with agro-livestock operators, including farmers and foresters (N=17);
 - A focus group with representatives from the tourism sector (N=5).
- Valencia: Semi structured interviews (N=11) with selected stakeholders from academia, the private sector, local authorities, and local associations.
- Bern: Semi-structured interviews (n=14) with selected stakeholders from academia, local authorities, private sector and educational institutions.

For the three cases, the data collected through interviews and discussions were transcribed and analysed using a qualitative-quantitative content analysis approach. In the case of Valencia and Bern, NVivo 15 software was used to support the analysis, while Atlas.ti and manual coding were employed for the Ogliastro dataset.

Our case studies highlight a few notable commonalities among enabling factors. Strong policy and legal frameworks stand out in both Bern and Ogliastro. Similarly, access to funding and financial instruments plays a crucial role in both Valencia and Bern. The influence of technical expertise and knowledge, however, is more variable, as it is identified as a key enablers in Ogliastro but as a major gap in Valencia, where its absence hampers progress. These findings indicate that, despite some shared enablers exist, the diversity of local conditions limits the transferability of enablers and barriers across contexts.

In Valencia, while slow progression can be observed, and the city already benefits from a number of green urban areas which contribute to mitigating urban heat and managing stormwater and flood risks, the adoption of NbS is still limited. Lack of knowledge and specialized expertise for design, implementation and maintenance, alongside path dependencies on established, traditional practices, are found to hinder further NbS implementation. Moreover, the lack of long-term planning and stable financing, particularly for maintenance, hampers their sustainability, highlighting the need for institutionalizing climate adaptation through stable entities and strategic plans. In Ogliastro, local willingness to engage in wildfire risk reduction is evident, especially among agro-livestock operators. However, the lack of clear policy support, legal frameworks, funding pathways, and cost-sharing mechanisms hampers community-driven initiatives, particularly in private and municipal forest areas. Additionally, a sense of helplessness and resignation prevails among local communities, who perceive current firefighting practices as ineffective. Finally, in Bern, the longstanding practice of maintaining protection forests is well-supported by subsidies and legal frameworks, yet stakeholders are concerned about the forests' resilience to climate change-related disturbances, such as storms and pest outbreaks. Additionally, tensions between forestry and hazard management sectors impede integrated planning.

To address these and other challenges, we conclude this report by suggesting a number of actions and reforms aimed at enabling the adoption, implementation, and conservation of NbS as multi-risk strategies. The full list of suggested actions, all emerging or inspired by the corresponding discussions with stakeholders, can be found in section 9. Some key suggestions include:

- From Valencia:
 - Establishing a municipal NbS coordination unit or role: Create dedicated roles within city governments to centralize guidance, coordinate across departments (e.g., risk management), and enhance long-term maintenance and stakeholder engagement in NbS projects.
 - Implementing mandatory comparative assessment in projects: Require urban and infrastructure projects to assess and compare grey, hybrid, and NbS alternatives, incorporating ecosystem service and multi-hazard analyses to support evidence-based decision-making.
 - Strengthening financing mechanisms linked to territorial equity: Develop funding strategies linked to ecosystem services, targeting vulnerable areas to enhance territorial equity, environmental justice, and resilience against climate hazards.
- From Ogliastro:
 - Promoting fire-smart management strategies: Develop integrated fire-smart approaches combining silviculture, prescribed grazing, and agroforestry to reduce wildfire risks while

- promoting multifunctional land uses, such as bioeconomy initiatives and collective land management through forest owner associations.
- Strengthening participatory governance and territorial alliances: Establish permanent “territorial laboratories” as inclusive governance platforms where local authorities, forest managers, farmers, and civil society co-design integrated risk management strategies, fostering collaboration and shared responsibility.
 - Fostering synergies between active and passive wildfire defence: Combine active fire prevention methods (e.g., prescribed fire, land management) with passive financial instruments like community-based insurance and payments for ecosystem services, creating sustainable, community-supported fire management.
- From Bern:
 - Strengthen the biodiversity and climate nexus: Strengthening the resilience of protection forests by integrating biodiversity and climate considerations into planning frameworks such as NaiS and PROTECTpraxis. This includes promoting adaptive silviculture (e.g. mixed-species planting, deadwood retention) and establishing interdisciplinary coordination bodies between forestry, hazard management, and environmental agencies.
 - Mitigate ungulate browsing pressure: To address forest regeneration challenges, targeted measures such as regional game management plans and subsidies for deer exclosures are proposed.
 - Enhance multi-risk and cascading risk integration: Multi-risk integration should be advanced through the creation of a cantonal coordination unit, pilot multi-risk scenarios using PROTECTpraxis, and the development of shared tools and terminology for cascading risk assessments.

While findings and suggestions in this deliverable offer valuable insights, they are not universally generalizable due to inherent limitations, including context-specific factors, sectoral biases, and varying temporal perspectives. Future research should focus on developing adaptive governance models, fostering cross-sectoral and cross-level collaboration, and exploring innovative financial mechanisms to enhance NbS integration into multi-risk DRR frameworks. We hope that this research will inspire further exploration and critical reflection among researchers, practitioners, and policymakers on innovative pathways for integrating NbS into multi-risk DRR practices.

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Glossary

Cascading risks: One event or trend triggering others; interactions can be one way (e.g., domino or contagion effects) but can also have feedbacks; cascading risk is often associated with the vulnerability component of risk, such as critical infrastructure (Simpson et al., 2021).

Compound risk: arise from the interaction of hazards, which may be characterised by single extreme events or multiple coincident or sequential events that interact with exposed systems or sectors (IPCC, 2019).

Disaster risk: The potential loss of life, injury, or destroyed or damaged assets which could occur to a system, society or a community in a specific period of time, determined probabilistically as a function of hazard, exposure, vulnerability and capacity (UNDRR, 2017).

Disaster Risk Governance: The system of institutions, mechanisms, policy and legal frameworks and other arrangements to guide, coordinate and oversee disaster risk reduction and related areas of policy (UNDRR, 2017).

Disaster Risk Management (DRM): The application of disaster risk reduction policies and strategies to prevent new disaster risk, reduce existing disaster risk and manage residual risk, contributing to the strengthening of resilience and reduction of disaster losses (UNDRR, 2017).

Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR): The policy objective of disaster risk management. Its goals and objectives are defined in disaster risk reduction strategies and plans. Disaster risk reduction is aimed at preventing new and reducing existing disaster risk and managing residual risk, all of which contribute to strengthening resilience and therefore to the achievement of sustainable development (UNDRR, 2017).

Exposure: The situation of people, infrastructure, housing, production capacities and other tangible human assets located in hazard-prone areas (UNDRR, 2017).

Hazard: A hazard is a process, phenomenon or human activity that may cause loss of life, injury or other health impacts, property damage, social and economic disruption or environmental degradation. Hazards may be natural, anthropogenic or socionatural in origin (UNDRR, 2017).

Impact: Effects on natural and human systems of extreme weather and climate events and of climate change. Impacts may be referred to as consequences or outcomes, and can be adverse or beneficial (IPCC, 2022).

Multi-hazard: (1) the selection of multiple major hazards that the country faces, and (2) the specific contexts where hazardous events may occur simultaneously, cascading or cumulatively over time, and taking into account the potential interrelated effects. Hazards include (as mentioned in the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030) biological, environmental, geological, hydrometeorological and technological processes and phenomena. (UNDRR, 2017).

Multi-risk: Risk generated from multiple hazards and the interrelationships between these hazards (and considering interrelationships on the vulnerability level) (Zschau, 2017). The whole risk from several hazards, taking into account possible hazards and vulnerability interactions entailing both multi-hazard and multi-vulnerability perspectives (Simpson et al., 2021).

Nature-based Solutions (NbS): actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems, which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services and resilience and biodiversity benefits (UNEA, 2022, p.2).

Systemic risk: Systemic risk is associated with cascading impacts that spread within and across systems and sectors via the movements of people, goods, capital and information within and across boundaries (e.g. regions, countries and continents) (Sillmann et al., 2022). Threats that have wide-reaching, cross-sectoral, or even global effects and are complex, have many unknowns and major ambiguities. Systemic risks extend their impact beyond the confines of the original system, posing the danger of systemic collapse rather than merely isolated failures of individual components (adapted from Mitra & Shaw, 2023).

Vulnerability: The conditions determined by physical, social, economic and environmental factors or processes which increase the susceptibility of an individual, a community, assets or systems to the impacts of hazards (UNDRR, 2017).

4. Introduction

As societies face increasingly complex and interconnected natural hazards that exacerbate the risk of disasters (Lee et al., 2024; Van Wyk de Vries, 2025), conventional disaster risk reduction (DRR) practices that address hazards in isolation have become insufficient (AIDR, 2021; Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2023). Data from the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR, 2021b) indicate that disasters linked to climate and weather extremes have nearly doubled over the past two decades. As global temperatures rise, risks are no longer confined to isolated events, instead, climate and non-climate hazards are interacting in complex, often unpredictable ways (IPCC, 2023), increasing the likelihood of concurrent or cascading risks that can quickly exceed the capacity of conventional Disaster Risk Management (DRM) systems. To effectively build resilience and safeguard people and assets, it is essential for DRM measures to account for the spatial and temporal interdependencies inherent in multi-hazard risk.

Recent events, such as the 2024 hurricane that hit the U.S. state of Florida, cyclone Idai in 2019 in Mozambique, Zimbabwe, and Malawi, and the DANA (Depresión Aislada en Niveles Altos) floods that affected Valencia, Spain in 2024, highlight the devastating impacts of multi-hazard scenarios and the vulnerabilities exposed by them. Regrettably, in the three cases, as in many others (e.g. Fukushima incident in 2011), a significant portion of the losses and damages could have been avoided with better preparation, communication, coordination, and clear action plans for events of unexpected magnitude and severe impacts (Busby et al., 2021; Munsaka et al., 2021). These events underscore the limitations of single-hazard risk management approaches and the urgent need for a paradigm shift towards more comprehensive and integrative strategies (Šakić Trogrlić et al., 2024; Schlumberger et al., 2022). Today, leading instruments like the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (SFDRR) advocate for multi-hazard approaches (UNISDR, 2015). In fact, research indicates that integrating multiple hazards/risks within risk and emergency management practices can lead to significant institutional improvements (Scolobig et al., 2013; Senevirathne et al., 2024). Yet adapting current governance approaches to manage multi-risks effectively remains a formidable challenge requiring substantial reforms to single-risk oriented management systems and the adoption of systems thinking to better understand the complexity of risk dynamics (Deubelli et al., 2022). Resilience-building through capacity development, fostering stakeholder engagement and collaborative knowledge production, and considering indirect and cascading risks are essential (AIDR, 2021; Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2023; Schweizer & Renn, 2019; Sillmann et al., 2022).

In this context, the adoption of Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) has emerged as a promising tool (Debele et al., 2023). Formally defined as 'actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems, which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services and resilience and biodiversity benefits' (UNEA, 2022), NbS build on the functionality and resilience of natural ecosystems to offer simultaneous and effective mitigation against a wide range of hazards. The restoration of native ecosystems, for example, can help reduce the risks of floods, droughts and landslides by promoting healthy soils and vegetation with increased capacities for water infiltration and storage, slope and shore stabilisation and wave energy attenuation (Seddon, 2022). NbS can also play a pivotal role in addressing systemic risks by strengthening socio-ecological systems and promoting the adoption of a more holistic understanding of the risk landscape. However, transitioning from conventional approaches remains difficult for communities, governments, and businesses accustomed to more traditional ways of functioning and problem-solving (Pescaroli et al., 2022; Scolobig et al., 2014).

The research presented in this deliverable explores the governance barriers and enablers of multi-risk DRR strategies, particularly NbS implementation. It aims to identify and suggest innovative enablers to support the adoption, implementation, and conservation of effective initiatives, with a special emphasis on NbS. Focusing on three case studies from selected demonstration sites (DEMs) from The HuT project, Valencia (DEM1), Ogliastro (DEM8), and Bern (DEM10), the deliverable offers practical insights into potential actions, tools or practices for advancing multi-hazard DRR. Below is a brief description of the case studies:

- **Valencia (DEM1):** This case study explores governance conditions influencing NbS implementation, focusing on the factors that enable or hinder their use in enhancing urban climate resilience. Building on its findings, it aims to provide insights into how NbS can be effectively integrated into urban policy and planning as multi-risk reduction measures. This case study primarily addresses the hazards of urban heatwaves and droughts, while also tackling the issue of urban flooding, through the implementation of urban green and blue infrastructure projects, including parks, green corridors, and riverbed restorations. The analysis of this case study had a primary focus on the earlier and implementation stages of NbS, including pre-conditions, initiation, planning, design, construction or planting, and execution. Data for the Valencia case study was collected through semi-structured interviews with stakeholders from various sectors, including academia, the private sector, and local authorities.
- **Ogliastro (DEM8):** The Ogliastro case study examines the main barriers and enabling factors in fire risk management, with a particular focus on prevention and mitigation, aiming to support the development of locally tailored strategies (including NbS) for wildfire risks reduction and climate change adaptation. The primary hazards addressed in this case are wildfires and droughts through co-identification of fire prevention and land management options (e.g., the generation and maintenance of agro-silvo-pastoral mosaic landscapes, considered a type of NbS). The stages of implementation considered range from pre-conditions, initiation, planning, and design of measures, which will be later tested in the DEM through simulation modelling. The methods employed in this case include participatory sessions such as workshops with local administrators and agro-livestock operators, and a focus group with representatives from the tourism sector.
- **Bern (DEM10):** The Bern case study investigates governance enablers and barriers affecting the conservation and restoration of protection forests and the implementation of the future natural hazard risk reduction guidelines, PROTECTpraxis. It addresses a wide range of hazards, including avalanches, rockfall, landslides and erosion, as well as floods and droughts. The NbS on the agenda of Bern are the protection forests themselves, conserved, maintained, and restored to boost their hazard mitigation capacities. In this case, the stages of NbS implementation on which the study case focused are the construction, planting, execution, maintenance, conservation and restoration. Data was gathered through semi-structured interviews with stakeholders from academia, local authorities, the private sector, and educational institutions.

By analysing the findings from the three cases and drawing inspiration from successful case studies, emerging tools, and transformative governance models from the literature, the report offers suggestions on how governments, organisations, and communities can collaboratively foster the adoption, implementation and longer-term conservation of NbS to navigate the complexities of multi-risk DRR. While the NbS discussed in the case studies may not all represent novel approaches in themselves, the report's innovative contribution lies in the suggestions offered. Through a forward-looking lens, the report aspires to contribute meaningfully to the ongoing discourse on developing a resilient future in the face of multi-risks.

Following the introduction, the report sets the context by providing a short background on the challenges of DRR in today's complex systems and the governance of multi-risk environments. It then presents NbS as promising strategies for addressing these risks, highlighting their potential to offer mitigation against a wide range of hazards. Next, the report introduces the three case studies, outlines their methodological approaches and, one by one, describes their policy and governance contexts, research design, and presents their key findings, summary, and key messages. Finally, the report offers a set of innovative suggestions aimed at advancing NbS as multi-hazard DRR strategies, followed by a concluding section that synthesizes the case study findings, discusses the study's limitations, and explores the broader implications for improving multi-hazard DRR.

5. DRR in a complex world

Disasters arising from natural hazards are widely recognized as significant disruptions that profoundly hinder human and economic development, impacting years of progress and limiting new growth opportunities (Cavallo et al., 2022). In recent decades, considerable efforts and resources have been dedicated to studying and managing these events, leading to a notable evolution in the conceptualization and governance of natural hazards and disaster risk (Chaudhary & Piracha, 2021; Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2023). Traditionally, "natural disasters" were often perceived as unpredictable, uncontrollable events caused almost exclusively by natural forces, such as earthquakes, floods, or hurricanes (Wisner et al., 2003). This perspective viewed disasters as inevitable outcomes of nature's power, placing little emphasis on human contributions to risk. However, advancements in technology, scientific research, and a broadening of social and political perspectives have reshaped this understanding, revealing the complex synergies between natural hazards and human activities (Van Wyk de Vries, 2025). Today, it is broadly accepted that disaster risks emerge not only from natural hazards but from the compounded effects of human-induced factors such as climate change, environmental degradation, and urbanization, which exacerbate societal vulnerabilities and exposure (Puttick et al., 2018; Van Wyk de Vries, 2025).

Figure 1: Extended risk framework illustrating how multiple climatic drivers can trigger one or multiple hazards, leading to societal and environmental risk. Source: UNDRR, 2022, adapted from Zscheischler et al., 2018 and IPCC, 2014.

The traditional, siloed approach to DRM is proving insufficient in the face of these complexities. In response, there has been a paradigmatic shift toward multi-risk DRR, an integrative approach that accounts for the interactions and co-occurrence of multiple hazards and their socio-ecological drivers (Sillmann et al., 2022). For instance, climate change is contributing to the intensification of extreme weather events, while unsustainable land use and urban planning are exacerbating vulnerabilities in both rural and urban areas (IPCC, 2023; Stauffer et al., 2023; UNDRR, 2021b). Climate extremes, such as droughts, floods, and heatwaves, often trigger compound and cascading impacts (Lawrence et al., 2020). At the same time, the unprecedented loss of natural capital and biodiversity is emerging as another critical driver of disaster risk, further increasing the severity of droughts, heatwaves, floods, landslides, wildfires, and other climate-related extremes (UNDRR, 2022; WHO, 2025). Yet, our knowledge of these dynamic interplays remains limited. Research typically considers only one isolated hazard, impact, system, socioeconomic sector at a time, often ignoring dependencies between them as well as how they interact with response and adaptation measures (Madruga de Brito, 2025).

Because risks are shaped by the choices we make, proper understanding of the dynamic interplays between hazards and human exposure and vulnerabilities is essential for effective disaster risk governance, DRM, and ultimately, DRR. The shift toward multi-risk approach is crucial for developing strategies that consider the full spectrum of interconnected risks and their potential systemic effects.

6. Governance for complex and multi-risk scenarios

Governance is a critical aspect of managing risks, especially when these risks stem from multiple hazards or lead to cascading effects. Terms like disaster risk governance, DRM, and DRR are often used interchangeably in both policy and practice. However, while they are closely related, they refer to different but interconnected aspects of how societies address disaster risk (Fig. 2). Disaster risk governance refers to the rules, systems, and institutions that guide the way in which communities prepare for and respond to disasters (see glossary) (UNDRR, 2017). It involves the coordination of a wide range of stakeholders, including government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), community groups, businesses, financiers and other market actors, and international partners, to ensure that DRM is well integrated and comprehensive (IFRC, 2024). A robust governance framework ensures that DRM is capable of addressing complex risks (Schweizer, 2021).

Figure 2: Simplified diagram to illustrate the connections between risk governance, Disaster Risk Management and Disaster Risk Reduction. Created by the author based on the concept's definitions and IFRC (2024).

The challenges

However, and in large part due to the already difficult task of addressing risks even in isolation, shifting from single to multi-hazard risk approaches has long been a challenge (Scolobig et al., 2017). Despite the growing recognition of these and other crucial needs, today, many risk governance systems still remain fragmented (Deubelli et al., 2022; Schweizer, 2021). As a result, risks are often both assessed and managed in isolation, missing the bigger picture of the challenges. Adopting this perspective limits the effectiveness of response and recovery and often results in gaps or overlaps in responsibilities. In Europe the scenario is similar, according to recent research by the EC-funded MYRIAD-EU project, multi-risk approaches are not yet systematically applied across Europe (Schlumberger et al., 2022). Moreover, the slow transition from theory to practical implementation previously observed, persists (Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2023; Komendantova et al., 2014), with risk assessments rarely considering multiple hazards and their interactions, or accounting for existing vulnerabilities in play (Poljanšek et al., 2019).

Different barriers appear to contribute to this slow progress, including insufficient data integration (e.g., high resolution data from earth observations, historic risk data), inadequate cross-sector collaboration, insufficient knowledge and understanding of the risks dynamics, and a lack of flexible strategies to address evolving risk landscapes (Sillmann et al., 2022; Zuccaro et al., 2020). Interestingly, lack of knowledge is no longer reported as a major problem (Izumi et al., 2019; Sillmann et al., 2022), instead, the main challenges seem to lie in the complexities of integrating, interpreting, and applying the vast amount of information already available or emerging (Schlumberger et al., 2022). At the same time, in spite of the increasing number of case-studies available from which relevant lessons could be extracted, cases studying more than one or two hazards at the time are still very limited (Ward et al., 2022).

The needs

According to the literature, effective governance relies on several enabling components (IFRC, 2024). Among the most important are legal and regulatory frameworks, which define clear roles, responsibilities, and procedures for disaster preparedness, response, and recovery (European Commission, n.d.). They shape the approach to governing and managing risks associated with both natural and man-made disasters, providing a structured framework for addressing specific issues, achieving goals, allocating funding, and regulating behaviour (UNISDR, 2015). For example, specific policies can guide the identification and assessment of risks and establish standardised methodologies and criteria for evaluating hazards and vulnerabilities (Plana et al., 2024). Others, such as local DRR and management plans facilitate coordination among stakeholders by delineating roles and responsibilities in DRR efforts (UNDRR, 2019). This aspect is especially influential, as fostering systematic collaboration among all key actors, across government levels, sectors, and communities, is essential to developing coherent, aligned, and effective strategies (Ibrahim et al., 2025; Wickenberg et al., 2021).

At the European level, the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM) plays a central role in multi-risk governance by requiring member states to submit National Risk Assessments (NRA) every three years (Poljansek et al., 2021). Nevertheless, beyond this mechanism, there remains a lack of binding instruments that mandate a multi-risk approach (Schlumberger et al., 2022). Yet, key international frameworks such as the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015-2030), encourage comprehensive risk understanding and mitigation of interrelated risks (UNISDR, 2015). Similarly, Agenda 21 advocates for extensive research on the vulnerabilities of human settlements and infrastructure, stressing the need for a holistic understanding of risks, while documents like the Reporting Guidelines on Disaster Risk Management provide structured frameworks for documenting and sharing progress, encouraging integrated planning that

accounts for the interactions between multiple risks. These guidelines help foster a more coordinated and resilient approach to disaster management.

However, governance goes beyond laws and policies, it also relies heavily on coordination across all relevant actors and levels, including government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and local communities (Deubelli et al., 2022). Collaboration ensures that responses are well-organized, context-specific, and efficiently resourced. In multi-risk contexts, where hazards like drought, wildfire, or infrastructure failure can reinforce one another and trigger cascading impacts, governance must address cross-sectoral interdependencies and uncertainty through coordinated planning, data sharing, and scenario-based strategies (IFRC, 2024; Sillmann et al., 2022). Moreover, bridging the gap between scientific research and practical policy implementation is also essential. Strong partnerships between scientists, policymakers, businesses, financiers, civil society and practitioners enable the translation of knowledge into actionable tools, while practitioner's inputs help ensure that multi-risk methodologies are both relevant and applicable (Scolobig et al., 2017; Zuccaro et al., 2020).

Moving toward a multi-risk governance model requires a shift in both mindset and practice: breaking down institutional silos, addressing complexity, improving cross-sector knowledge integration, fostering science-policy-practice collaboration, and creating adaptive, inclusive, and forward-looking policies (Brett et al., 2025). It also involves ensuring that vulnerable communities are meaningfully included in decision-making and that governance efforts are aligned across local, national, and international levels (Sillmann et al., 2022). Nevertheless, research demonstrates that effective citizen participation goes beyond token consultation, it requires creating inclusive spaces where community voices shape disaster governance (Kiss et al., 2022). Such engagement builds trust, fosters social learning, and helps address power imbalances, making governance more adaptive and responsive to those most affected.

7. Nature-based Solutions (NbS) for addressing multi-risk

A rapidly emerging and increasingly influential approach to reducing disaster risks, combating biodiversity loss, land degradation, and addressing a range of other challenges is the adoption of NbS (Fig. 3) (Dunlop et al., 2024). By protecting, restoring, and managing ecosystems, NbS harness natural processes to offer sustainable, cost-effective, and multifunctional strategies for mitigating hazards such as floods, droughts, heatwaves, and coastal erosion (Ommer et al., 2022; UNDRR, 2021a). At the same time, they address environmental, social, and economic challenges while promoting climate resilience, biodiversity, and sustainable development (see glossary). The growing body of research highlights the effectiveness of NbS in providing integrated, long-term solutions to complex risks, especially in the context of accelerating climate change and rapid urbanisation (Seddon et al., 2020; Turner et al., 2022).

Figure 3: Figure illustrating Nature-based Solutions as measures that contribute to sustainable development. Source: UNDRR, 2021a, adapted from UNEP/PEDRR 2020.

NbS are recognized for their ability to mitigate the impact of multiple hazards by enhancing ecosystem resilience and reducing human vulnerability (Turner et al., 2022). Key examples of these solutions include the restoration of wetlands, mangroves, and forests, which act as natural barriers against floods and coastal storms (Debele et al., 2023). Wetlands, for instance, help mitigate floods and droughts risks by storing and slowing the flow of water during heavy rain and gradually releasing it to recharge groundwater supplies during dry periods (Wu et al., 2023). Similarly, mangrove ecosystems reduce storm surge heights and protect coastal areas from erosion and flooding by dissipating wave energy. These solutions provide not only protection

against hazards but also other ecological services such as carbon sequestration and biodiversity conservation (UNEP, 2023). In Europe, a notable example of NbS with DRR purposes is the Lower Danube green corridor project initiated in 2000 by the governments of Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine and Moldova, which by 2020 had led to the restoration of over 60,000 hectares of floodplains along the Danube River. The positive outcomes of the project are multiple, from the considerable reduction of flood vulnerability to biodiversity conservation and the improvement of local economies through tourism. The World Wildlife Fund for Nature (WWF) estimates the net value of the restored landscape to €111.8 million per year (Nature-based Solutions Initiative, n.d.).

In urban environments, green infrastructure, including parks, green roofs, and urban forests, helps alleviate heatwaves and mitigating urban flooding by improving stormwater retention (Zhou et al., 2024). Therefore, it is not surprising that research related to the use and implementation of NbS for aspects like urban cooling and urban water management has surged over the past decade (Dunlop et al., 2024). Research related to NbS for DRR has also expanded significantly, showing a growing interest in their practical application. Examples include studies on governance enablers and barriers influencing flood risk mitigation through the restoration of the Isar River in Munich, Germany; the use of afforestation and anti-deforestation strategies to address flood and landslide risks in the Wolong Nature Reserve, China; and the application of natural measures to reduce landslide risks in Nocera Inferiore, Italy (Martin et al., 2019).

At present, a number of key policy frameworks advocate for the integration of NbS into DRR strategies. Notably, the latest revision of the Sendai Framework emphasises the promotion of NbS “at all levels and across all phases of DRR and management” (UNGA, 2023). Similarly, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework highlights this approach, with Targets 8 and 11 explicitly calling for the use of NbS to mitigate climate impacts and restore, maintain, and enhance nature’s contributions to human well-being (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022). At the European level, the European Green Deal incorporates NbS as a key element of its broad sustainability agenda, recognizing their potential to build climate-resilient communities (European Commission, 2021a). The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 reinforces this by prioritising the restoration and protection of ecosystems as essential for fostering societal resilience (European Commission, 2020). Additionally, the recent EU Adaptation Strategy aims to enhance climate resilience by integrating biodiversity considerations, further aligning with the main objectives of NbS implementation (European Commission, 2021b).

Despite the growing recognition of NbS, there are significant challenges in scaling up their adoption. These challenges include future climate uncertainties, lack of empirical evidence supporting their benefits and effectiveness, limited collaborative governance, low private sector engagement, lack of skilled implementers, lack of awareness of their potential use, and insufficient public resources (Castellar et al., 2024; Castelo et al., 2023; Martin et al., forthcoming). Furthermore, there is often resistance to replacing conventional “grey” infrastructure with NbS, partly due to perceptions of uncertainty about their long-term effectiveness (Seddon et al., 2020). However, recent research shows that NbS can be as effective, if not more so, than traditional infrastructure, especially when considering their ability to provide multiple co-benefits (Turner et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2024).

To overcome these barriers, measures need to be taken for the strengthening of knowledge and capacities, the fostering cross-sector communication and collaboration, and the adoption of an interdisciplinary approach for their planning and implementation (Castellar et al., 2024; Linnerooth-Bayer et al., 2023). Additionally, more research is needed to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of NbS over time, particularly in the context of evolving climate risks.

Boxes 1 and 2 showcase two successful examples of implementing NbS for risk reduction and mitigation purposes. These case studies highlight the versatility and effectiveness of NbS in diverse contexts and illustrate their potential to address complex challenges posed by natural hazards.

Box 1: Compensation agreements and collaborative governance in the Serchio River Basin, Italy

Under the framework of the PHUSICOS project (<https://www.phusicos.eu/>), NBS were implemented in the Serchio River Basin, located in Tuscany, central Italy. This mountainous area is prone to a number of risks, including floods, droughts, and runoff of sediments and pollutants from agricultural land, which impact irrigation canals and the nearby Lake Massaciuccoli. The river basin is also rich in biodiversity and cultural heritage, making the preservation of its natural environment particularly important.

To tackle these challenges, the project employed several NBS techniques, such as the creation of buffer strips, a sedimentation basin, and modifications to two key canals to improve their hydraulic capacity. These measures not only reduced flood risks and mitigated further damage to Lake Massaciuccoli, but also promoted the local green economy, improved the well-being of residents and visitors, and enhanced local biodiversity. The re-naturalized areas provided space for wildlife and beautified the landscape, which supported local tourism and recreational activities.

However, equally important was the strengthening of communication and collaboration among local stakeholders. The success of the project was made possible by the close cooperation between actors such as PHUSICOS, the Autorità di Bacino Distrettuale dell'Appennino Settentrionale (ADBS), the University of Pisa, and farmers and community organizations. In fact, a crucial aspect of the project was the negotiation of a compensation agreement with farmers, who agreed to stop cropping in certain areas of their land to allow for the creation of buffer strips. In exchange, farmers received payments for the ecosystem services provided as a way of compensation for the loss of their harvest. Currently, thanks to these agreements, they are responsible for the maintenance of the implemented NBS.

Source: PHUSICOS, 2023.

<https://www.phusicos.eu/case-studies/serchio-river-basin-italy/>

Box 2: The Food-IAP case: Establishment of the Upper Tana Nairobi Water Fund (UTNWF)

Nairobi, Kenya, is home to a thriving multi-sector initiative launched in 2015: The Upper Tana-Nairobi Water Fund (UTNWF). Conceived by the Nature Conservancy, the fund addresses pressing challenges such as drought, soil erosion, and water scarcity, issues driven and worsen by the area's naturally arid conditions and sedimentation in the Masinga Reservoir from unsustainable farming along the upper Tana River.

Guided by the principle that preventing problems at their source is more cost-effective than remediation, the fund focuses on assisting local farmers in adopting sustainable practices while preserving and restoring the area's ecological balance. Key downstream water users, including businesses, utility companies, and local governments, invest in water security through the fund. In turn, the fund works with tens of thousands of upstream farmers to implement critical conservation and restoration efforts. These include riparian zone management, afforestation and reforestation, soil conservation, sustainable land management, and wetland restoration. Together, these actions help reduce the risks of flooding, drought, water scarcity, and land degradation, while strengthening community resilience and adaptive capacity.

Beyond improving water quality, the fund generates employment and livelihood opportunities for the local population, whether as direct beneficiaries or through indirect means by the improvement of local ecosystem conditions. Importantly, the fund also helps prevent technical disruptions at water treatment and distribution plants, which in the past have caused prolonged water supply outages lasting days or even weeks.

After its long history, the fund is now an independent organization as of September 2021.

Source: Panorana, 2021.
<https://panorama.solutions/en/solution/upper-tana-nairobi-water-fund-trust-innovation-nexus-conservation-food-water-energy-and>

8. Case studies

In this section, we present the findings from three in-depth case studies conducted in Valencia (Spain), Ogliastra (Italy) and Bern (Switzerland), which explore the barriers and enablers to the adoption and implementation of NbS as multi-risk DRR strategies. In Valencia, urban green infrastructure projects such as parks, green corridors, and riverbed restorations are employed to reduce urban heat stress, drought impacts, and pluvial flooding, driven by the motivation to enhance urban resilience in the face of climate change. In Ogliastra, land management and fire prevention actions (e.g. agro-silvo-pastoral mosaic landscapes) aim to mitigate wildfire risk while sustaining rural livelihoods. In Bern, protection forests are conserved, maintained and restored to mitigate risks from avalanches, rockfall, landslides, and erosion.

Each case study is structured around a common analytical framework (described below in section 8.1) that examines the multi-risk context, the role of NbS, and the governance landscape shaping implementation. The case study subsections are organized as follows: first, a general introduction to the regional/local context; second, the methodological approach; third, the detailed case study results which explore enablers and barriers in each case study site; and fourth a summary and the key message of the case study. Table 1 provides an overview of the key features of each case study.

Table 1: Key features of the three case studies.

Case Study	Main NbS	Main risk(s) addressed	Other risks	Method used	Number of participants / interviewees	Governance level of NbS implementation
Valencia (Spain)	Urban green infrastructure (e.g. parks, orchards, green corridors)	Urban heat, heatwaves, drought	Pluvial flooding	Semi-structured interviews	11 interviewees	Municipal governance through Valencia City Council (including Las Naves); some support from regional (Generalitat Valenciana)
Ogliastra (Italy)	Land management (e.g., grazing, prescribed burning, preventive silviculture, agroforestry)	Wildfires	Droughts	2 workshop, 2 questionnaires , 1 focus group	41 participants	Almost equal share between regional organizations (Autonomous Region of Sardinia, Corpo Forestale) community-level actors (e.g., farmers, civil protection volunteers)

Bern (Switzerland)	Protection forests	Avalanches, rockfall, landslides, erosion	Floods, droughts	Semi-structured interviews	14 interviewees	Primarily cantonal (Canton Bern) and municipal forest services; federal guidelines (e.g., NaiS, PROTECTpraxis) shape practice and funding
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8.1 Research questions and methods

The focus of the research presented in this deliverable is the governance enablers and barriers of multi-risk DRR strategies, particularly NbS implementation. As part of the implementation stages considered, we included the initiation, planning, design, construction/planting or execution, maintenance, conservation and restoration of NbS.

A wide range of definitions of governance enablers and barriers exist in the literature (Fukuyama, 2013; Ruhanen et al., 2010; Sekulova & Anguelovski, 2017). In this deliverable, we broadly define governance enablers and barriers as all aspects respectively catalysing or hindering collective and networked decision-making, including the social, ecological, political, legal and financial conditions through which NbS are implemented. Enablers are defined therefore as factors that play a positive role at any given stage of the NbS implementation process, whereas barriers are factors that hinder the successful NbS implementation. In some instances, barriers and enablers were found to mirror one another, indicating a perceived need for specific enabling factors to address the corresponding barriers. However, this mirroring does not imply the actual presence of such enablers, rather, it reflects the interviewees' recognition of their necessity for overcoming the identified obstacles.

It is important to note that each case is at different stages in the NbS implementation process, which is key for the interpretation of each case's governance enablers and barriers analysis. In Valencia, despite the existence of a regulatory framework and strategic plans supporting NbS, and of green spaces such as the Turia Garden, the Central Park, and the historical agricultural landscape Huerta de Valencia, NbS implementation remains limited. In Ogliastra, actions for fire prevention purposes are applied only and partially in public forest areas, while other type of fire-smart management options (e.g. fuel management in strategic areas through grazing - aligned with NbS) are limited due to financial resources, operational and administrative difficulties, especially in private forest ownership. Meanwhile, in Canton Bern, protection forests have mostly existed for several decades, up to centuries (Swiss Federal Office for the Environment, 2025), with little to no large-scale afforestation. This means that governance enablers and barriers mostly represent an ex-post analysis either referring to the maintenance and sustainability of protection forests, or their past planting. This is different for the PROTECTpraxis guidelines, which are yet to be implemented in 2025. Enablers and barriers should therefore be interpreted accordingly.

To provide background and context for each of the three cases, a desk-based review of both peer-reviewed and grey literature was conducted. This included publications, reports, media sources, websites, and legal documents. Additionally, appendices A and B present an overview of the key

governance enablers and barriers identified from the desk review for Valencia and Ogliastra. Unfortunately, since the Bern case study joined the research at a later stage, similar information was not collected for that case.

In each case, data was co-created using tailored qualitative social research methods aimed at facilitating collaborative knowledge production and the engagement of stakeholders. In Ogliastra, two participatory workshops (N=36) and one focus group (N=5) were conducted. Quantitative data were collected through a semi-structured in-person questionnaire administered before the events. The tool was tailored to each target group and structured in sections to explore perceptions and experiences related to fire phenomena and prevention measures. In Valencia and Bern, N=11 and N=14 semi-structured interviews were carried out, respectively.

The data collected through interviews and workshop discussions were transcribed and analysed using a qualitative-quantitative content analysis approach (Vaismoradi et al., 2016). The analysis was carried out using NVivo 15 (Bern and Valencia), Atlas.ti, and manual coding in Excel (for the Ogliastra dataset). All interviews and workshop results were anonymised. Interviewees were attributed a number to maintain anonymity (i.e., B1-B14 for Bern, V1-V11 for Valencia). Ogliastra questionnaire results were analysed using descriptive statistics.

In the analysis of these case studies, a common framework was applied to classify enablers and barriers. The enabler and barrier clusters identified in (Martin et al., forthcoming) were used as broad enabler/barrier categories. This original framework was developed based on a literature review and the results of participatory workshops. Codes were inductively assigned to ideas emerging from the transcribed text, following a grounded theory approach (Adeoye-Olatunde & Olenik, 2021; Charmaz, 2014). Table 2 describes these clusters in more detail. Additionally, sub-categories (macro-codes) were used to capture more nuanced results in the data. This approach ensured that the analysis can accommodate for unanticipated findings, enabling a more objective interpretation of the data.

Table 2: Definitions and examples of barrier and enabler clusters used in the thematic analyses.

Barrier cluster code	Definition	Example from one of the three cases
Lack of expertise and knowledge	There is a lack of expertise, know-how, education or general knowledge on how to implement NbS.	“Training is needed to make a change in professionals, both engineers and architects, to be able to execute these projects.” (Interviewee V8)
Lack of evidence on performance and co-benefits	There is a lack of evidence on the benefits, co-benefits and general success of NbS.	“It is much harder to quantify the risk reduction of NbS compared to grey infrastructure.” (interviewee B9)
Stakeholder conflicts/equity	There are conflicts between stakeholders, their values, interests and worldviews regarding NbS, or issues arising from a lack of equity in stakeholder engagement processes or outcomes concerning NbS.	“One of the key issues is the emergence of conflicts driven by diverging interests. Today, even the slightest intervention, such as modifying vegetation, can spark opposition, particularly from environmental associations. The situation has reached such extremes that even historically rooted or traditional land management practices are increasingly contested on environmental and conservation grounds. This dynamic is not limited to forests but extends to any non-agricultural vegetation formation.” (Workshop Institutional actors)

		"As soon as an intervention is made, other stakeholders, especially environmentalists or uninformed citizens, perceive it as environmental destruction. Often, their opposition is driven by good faith and a sincere belief that they are protecting nature, even when this is not the case." (Workshop Institutional actors)
Path dependency	The governance system exhibits pathways that are irreversibly 'locked-in' due to habituation, making it hard to break away from norms that still favour grey infrastructure over NbS.	"By law, two solutions should be required, one in classic grey construction, the other considering NbS and assessing which one is actually the best for the project." (Interviewee V9)
Lack & complexity of financing	There are insufficient financing sources for NbS, or existing financing schemes are too complex to navigate.	"Dealing with the deer browsing issue in protection forests would require immense financial resources." (Interviewee B3).
Lack of supportive policy/legal frameworks	There is a lack of policies, regulations or legal frameworks that incentivize, facilitate or support the implementation of NbS.	"It should be considered a requirement within legislation and regulations that all projects incorporate NbS." (Interviewee V11)
Sectoral/administrative silos	There is a lack of coordination between the different sectors or administrative bodies that could be implementing NbS.	"There is a conflict between forest and energy policies, with no communication between the two sectors." (Interviewee B5).
Land ownership and availability	There is a lack of available land on which NbS can be implemented, or there are conflicts in implementing NbS on private land.	"There is little space left for forests, everything is already built up." (Interviewee B8).
Lack of political will & long-term commitment	There is a lack of political will for implementing NbS, including due to a lack of long-term vision for and commitment to NbS.	"Short-term thinking [is an issue], NbS need time. The decisions we make need to be thought out in the long term." (Interviewee V7).
Risk aversion	NbS are perceived as higher risk solutions than grey infrastructure.	"When an external event occurs, we become concerned, but we don't perceive it as a problem that could lead to serious consequences. We've experienced such events as distant occurrences, happening within a radius that hasn't directly affected us. We have a beautiful pine forest in front of us, which actually represents a high risk due to how easily this type of vegetation can catch fire. We are very close to it. Still, I'm not sure whether, on a personal or collective level, including people staying at the hotel, people truly think about it. There's a general feeling of being protected, more secure. I'm talking about perception. Rationally, if you look around, you see the pine forest and the surrounding vegetation, which could clearly pose a risk." (Focus group of tourism operators)

Maintenance challenges	NbS are difficult or expensive to maintain.	“A lot of private forest owners do not maintain their forests.” (Interviewee B5).
Potential negative impacts	NbS can result in so-called ecosystem disservices and have other negative impacts.	“NbS, such as grazing, aim to provide multiple benefits, but poor management or lack of resources can lead to unintended effects, such as overgrazing: “Some shrub species, such as juniper and broom, livestock do not eat. These shrubs become so dense that animals can no longer pass through. As a result, the livestock are forced to move only within the few open areas that remain.” (Workshop Agro-livestock operators)
Enabler cluster code	Definition	Example
Stakeholder engagement & equity	There is a genuine co-design process in engaging stakeholders in decisions regarding NbS, and/or stakeholders are involved in a just and inclusive manner.	“The Forest Service has been implementing prescribed burning, it's a project that started in 2010–2011, developed in collaboration with the agropastoral communities of several municipalities. In the municipality of Suni, for example, there was a long-standing tradition of burning pastures to take advantage of the first rains and improve forage availability for livestock. Before 2011, every time a fire was detected, a helicopter was dispatched to extinguish it. With the new approach, we began carrying out burns together with the locals. The long-term goal was to empower communities—such as the local Barricelli companies—to independently carry out prescribed burning within clearly defined time windows. This project led to a remarkable reduction in both the number of wildfires and emergency interventions. It generated cost savings for the regional administration and for public finances. It is a proactive example of territorial fire management, one that could be replicated in other parts of Sardinia, though perhaps not in Ogliastra.” (Workshop Institutional actors)
Evidence on performance and co-benefits	There is evidence on the benefits, co-benefits and general success of NbS.	“The experience of the River Turia with regard to green areas has always been very present in the configuration of the city. The success of the project has meant that green areas have always been the vertebral axis of the city.” (Interviewee V1).
Expertise and knowledge	There is existing expertise, know-how, education or general knowledge on how to implement NbS.	“To be able to maintain protection forests, knowledge of ecological dynamics is essential.” (Interviewee B3).
Polycentric and cross-sectoral arrangements	Decisions regarding NbS are taken across different jurisdictional levels and scales (e.g., national, regional, global) and/or sectors, fostering cross-sectoral and cross-scale cooperation.	“One of the key success factors of PROTECTpraxis is that disaster specialists will need to work with forestry specialists.” (Interviewee B4).
Supportive policies and legal frameworks	There are existing policies, regulations or legal frameworks that incentivize,	“If a fire breaks out, you're not allowed to graze livestock there for ten years [due to regulatory restrictions].” (Workshop Agro-livestock operators)

	facilitate or support the implementation of NbS.	
Funding and financial tools & support	There are existing financing tools, schemes and funding sources for NbS.	“By using SUDS, less water reaches the sewage treatment plant, and this is a saving for the municipality. [These savings can be used] to build new infrastructure and maintain it. Since it is being managed from the source.” (Interviewee V10)
Communication and raising awareness	Communication strategies and mechanisms to raise awareness on NbS are in place.	“There have been many communication events to present and gain feedback on PROTECTpraxis.” (Interviewee B3).
Flexibility and adaptiveness	The governance mechanisms through which NbS are implemented retain a level of flexibility, meaning that they can be adapted in case of changes in system dynamics.	“[NbS] not only solve the problem for which they were designed, but, because of their multifunctional character, they also solve others.” (Interviewee V3).
Champions and advocates	There are individuals or advocate groups spearheading NbS visibility and implementation.	“Alicante, the park where we should analyse the obstacles that there were, which were not in the planning but in the administration itself and in this project a few people who were clear that the project should be done thinking in the NbS were achieved.” (Interviewee V8).
Political will & long-term commitment	There is political will for implementing NbS, including a long-term vision for and commitment to NbS.	“Valencia’s designation as the European Green Capital can be seen as the result of strong political will and long-term commitment by a previous local government that actively promoted this type of planning approach.” (Interviewee V1).
Aesthetics	NbS are seen as aesthetically pleasing.	“Protection forests look nicer than grey infrastructure such as metal nets.” (Interviewee B13).
Disaster	The occurrence of a disaster (and potential failure of a previously grey solution) catalyses the consideration of NbS.	“The federal forest law mainly emerged because of deforestation leading to disease outbreaks, floods and landslides.” (Interviewee B11).

Additional details and methodological specifications for each case study can be found in their respective Methods sections.

8.2 Valencia, Spain

The objective of this case study is to identify the barriers and enablers for implementing NbS in Valencia, Spain, with a particular focus on urban green infrastructure. These solutions aim to address the dual climate threats faced by the city: the intensification of heatwaves and the increasing risk of flooding. In this context, NbS include a broad range of green and blue infrastructure interventions, such as urban green corridors, parks, tree canopies, and stormwater reservoirs, which also help reducing the urban heat island effect.

To explore these dynamics, a literature review was initially conducted to map existing knowledge on the key barriers and enablers influencing NbS deployment (see appendix A). This was followed by the development of a survey designed to capture stakeholders' perceptions of the most significant barriers and enablers to advancing NbS, particularly in the context of multi-risk DRR and climate resilience strategies. This approach offers valuable insights to inform the development of more effective NbS policies and actions in the city.

The structure of this case study is as follows: it begins with a geographic/political overview of the Valencia area, followed by a description of NbS within the local context. It then examines the overarching NbS policies in Valencia and outlines the research design adopted in this study. The core of the analysis discusses key barriers and enablers for implementing NbS, with a particular focus on urban green infrastructure. The final section provides a summary of findings and highlights key messages.

8.2.1 Background/Case study overview

The city of Valencia, located on the Mediterranean coast of Spain, is the third largest city in the country in both demographic and economic terms. In 2021, it had a population of 800,180 inhabitants, reaching 1,581,057 in its metropolitan area, thus consolidating its position as one of the main Spanish cities. Its climate is characterised by hot summers and low rainfall, interrupted by episodes of heavy rainfall. However, climate change is exacerbating these conditions, causing higher temperatures, even less precipitation and extreme weather events such as heatwaves and torrential rains (García-Blanco et al., 2023). Moreover, the uncontrolled growth of urban areas has intensified the phenomenon of urban heat islands (UHI), which has led to an increase in energy demand for building cooling, increasing greenhouse gas emissions (Prades-Gil et al., 2024). Water management also presents a major challenge, as the conventional urban drainage model based on the rapid evacuation of rainwater has generated problems such as flooding, pollution and loss of water resources (Andrés-Doménech et al., 2021).

In terms of green infrastructure, Valencia has important natural spaces such as the Huerta de Valencia, a unique UNESCO World Heritage agro-ecosystem, the Albufera Natural Park and the Turia Garden, which contribute to the sustainability and resilience of the city (Tudorie et al., 2020). Moreover, over the past two decades, the city has made significant progress in integrating policies and strategies to address climate change and promote sustainable urban development. The city has actively participated in international initiatives and adopted comprehensive local action plans aimed at mitigation and adaptation. These efforts have included regulatory development, territorial planning instruments, and the promotion of NbS. A timeline of milestones illustrates this commitment:

- 2000s: Valencia joins climate action initiatives.
- 2009: Signing of the Covenant of Mayors, with a commitment to reduce GHG emissions by 20% by 2020.
- 2010: Approval of the Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP).
- 2011: Launch of the Valencia 2020 Climate Change Strategy and the development of case studies in Benaguasil and Xàtiva to collect data on the Mediterranean climate.
- 2014: Integration of the Environmental Action Plan and the SEAP, with new commitments and promotion of the Law on Territorial Planning, Urbanism and Landscape, which encourages green infrastructure in urban and developable areas.
- 2015: Accession to the Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy. Publication of the Territorial Action Plan for the prevention of flood risk in the Valencia Region and of the Regulation of the drainage network, these documents promote the use of SUDS.

- 2017: Publication of the Valencia 2050 Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change. In addition to the inauguration of the Valencia Logistics Park (Ribarroja del Turia).
- 2018: Inauguration of the Valencia Central Park (8.60ha).
- April 2019: Approval of the Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) in municipal plenary session.
- September 2019: Approval of the Declaration of Climate Emergency.
- August 2020: Creation of the City's Energy Transition Board, with representatives from various sectors.
- September 2020: Approval of the Valencia 2030 Strategic Framework, a sustainable urban planning instrument.
- February 2021: Approval of the 'Valencia Neutral City' mission, with the aim of achieving climate neutrality in three neighbourhoods by 2030.
- March 2021: Accession to the Green City Accord, a commitment to improve air quality, water management, urban biodiversity, circular economy and noise reduction (García-Blanco et al., 2023).

8.2.2 NbS policy and governance

Definition of NbS in the local context

NbS are intervention strategies that harness ecological processes and natural ecosystems to transform urban and rural environments, enhancing their resilience to environmental, social, and economic challenges (Beato Pérez, 2019). In Valencia, NbS go beyond physical infrastructure; they are adaptive strategies that support ecosystem regeneration and climate resilience. Their application ranges from the restoration of degraded ecosystems to the development of green and blue infrastructure, such as urban parks, green corridors, and stormwater reservoirs, that contribute to improved air quality, reduced urban heat island effects, and the mitigation of extreme climate risks, particularly heatwaves and both pluvial and storm-induced flooding (García-Blanco et al., 2023). In this study, NbS are considered as multifunctional, sustainable, and cost-effective tools, aiming to deliver long-term risk reduction and ecosystem services in the face of accelerating climate change and urbanization (see glossary).

Biodiversity conservation is a key focus of NbS strategies in Valencia. Through actions such as ecological restoration and the creation of green corridors, these strategies promote habitat connectivity, support native species, and contribute to ecological resilience. At the urban level, initiatives like urban parks, green roofs and walls, and sustainable urban drainage systems (SUDS) not only increase green cover but also improve urban biodiversity, stabilize local temperatures, and sequester carbon, contributing to both climate change mitigation and adaptation (Andrés-Doménech et al., 2021). NbS support broader sustainability priorities by enhancing energy efficiency in buildings, improving water management, and potentially advancing inclusive, equitable development when implemented thoughtfully. This multi-benefit approach enables the city to address a wide range of risks simultaneously from climate-related threats like heatwaves, droughts, and floods, to socio-economic vulnerabilities reinforcing the city's multi-risk resilience (García-Blanco et al., 2023).

At the strategic level, Valencia has adopted a progressive approach to the implementation of NbS through initiatives such as the Missions 2030 (Concejalía de Innovación y Gestión del Conocimiento + Las Naves, 2020), the Valencia 2030 Urban Strategy (Ajuntament de València, 2022a) and the Green Infrastructure and Biodiversity Plan (Ajuntament de València, 2022b). These strategies prioritize the integration of green infrastructure into urban planning and foster citizen engagement in the ecological transition, reinforcing NbS as a core component of the city's

climate resilience strategy, promoting the integration of green infrastructure into urban planning and strengthening citizen participation in the city's ecological transition (Prades-Gil et al., 2024).

Overall NbS policies in Valencia

The integration of NbS in Valencia has been marked by significant advances driven by planning strategies and cooperative projects, but also by challenges that still limit their implementation. Over the years, different initiatives and legislative frameworks have favoured their development, promoting biodiversity and urban resilience. However, factors such as dependence on national strategic infrastructures, lack of clear regulations and changing political priorities have created obstacles to their consolidation. Key moments of both momentum and setbacks in the implementation of the city's NbS are presented below.

- Missions 2030

Serves as the city's roadmap to achieve climate neutrality by 2030, as part of the European initiative of "100 climate-neutral cities." The strategy relies on systemic innovation, public policy, and strong citizen engagement to drive the transformation. It encompasses key areas such as sustainable mobility, energy transition, inclusive and sustainable housing and urbanism, green economy, sustainable tourism, and renaturalization and biodiversity. Moreover, it promotes a collaborative governance model involving public institutions, the private sector, academia, both individual citizens and civil organisations such as NGO, NPOs, professional associations, and foundations, and media (Concejalía de Innovación y Gestión del Conocimiento + Las Naves, 2020).

- Valencia 2030 Urban Strategy and the Green and Biodiversity Plan

Long-term planning has enabled the integration of the NbS into the city's sustainability policies. Economic incentives, regulations and governance strategies have been developed to strengthen green infrastructure and biodiversity (Ajuntament de València, 2022b, 2022a).

Valencia's Green and Biodiversity Plan positions NbS as a cornerstone of the city's climate adaptation and sustainability strategies, combining environmental, social, and spatial equity goals through an ambitious, multi-scale, and participatory approach. The plan outlines strategies to expand and improve green spaces, particularly in neighbourhoods with limited access to these resources, while promoting ecological gardening techniques, the use of native plant species, and low-maintenance landscaping to enhance urban biodiversity. Moreover, another key objective is to create a more resilient city through the implementation of sustainable drainage systems, increased tree canopy cover, and the expansion of green and blue infrastructure, including green roofs, vertical gardens, and ecological corridors. These interventions aim to mitigate the impacts of extreme weather events such as heatwaves and flooding, while also improving air quality and urban liveability. The plan emphasizes the importance of ecological connectivity between urban areas and natural surroundings, such as the Albufera Natural Park, the Turia River park, and the peri-urban agricultural belt (La Huerta), fostering a more integrated metropolitan ecosystem.

Citizen participation is also highlighted as a fundamental pillar of the plan, with actions designed to promote environmental awareness, and to involve residents in the co-management of green spaces. Furthermore, the plan adopts a phased approach to the implementation of NbS: in the short term (1–5 years), it prioritizes pilot projects and targeted interventions in vulnerable areas; in the medium term (5–10 years), it seeks to mainstream NbS into urban planning and offer incentives for private-sector participation; and in the long term (10–30 years), it envisions a city where green infrastructure is fully embedded in the urban development model.

- Implementation of the GrowGreen Project (2018-2023)

In recent years, Valencia City Council has participated in this European project, which has enabled the financing of urban interventions with NbS to improve climate resilience (Ajuntament de València, 2022b)

- Legislation and support from the Valencian Government

The Valencian Government, in the past, has supported long-term policies that seek to consolidate green infrastructure in the city, integrating it into territorial plans and promoting agroecology in the peri-urban huerta (Ajuntament de València, 2022b).

- Dependence on national strategic infrastructures

The implementation of some NbS has been limited due to the influence of infrastructure projects at state level, such as the extension of the port and the road network, which have conditioned the development of green spaces (Ajuntament de València, 2022b).

- Lack of clear regulations

Although plans and strategies for green infrastructure exist, the lack of specific regulations has hindered the uniform application of the NbS in Valencia, leading to uneven implementation (Ajuntament de València, 2022b). This challenge is not unique to Valencia, it reflects a broader pattern identified across Europe. A literature review conducted by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) found that the "Lack of supportive policy/legal frameworks" is one of the twelve key barrier themes for the implementation of NbS, and notably, it was among the most frequently cited barriers (Martin et al., 2023).

- Changing Political Priorities

In certain periods, changes in government have impacted on the continuity of environmental projects, which has slowed down the consolidation of long-term policies for urban biodiversity (Ajuntament de València, 2022b). The implementation of NbS in Valencia has largely depended on the political context and the willingness of local and regional governments to prioritise green infrastructure. While recent projects have favoured their expansion, regulatory barriers and economic priorities have sometimes limited their continued development.

Valencia has developed several regulations, projects and initiatives that encourage the implementation of NbS:

- València Urban Strategy 2030, which incorporates principles of sustainability and climate resilience.
- Law on Climate Change and Ecological Transition of the Valencian Community (Law 7/2021), which reinforces the region's climate commitments and promotes the integration of NbS in urban planning.
- Special Plan of Urban Quality Guidelines, which defines parameters for sustainable urban development, prioritizing access to green infrastructure and ecological connectivity.
- Missions València 2030, drives innovation in urban planning through NbS, aligning local strategies with the "Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)".
- Green Infrastructure and Biodiversity Plan, which promotes the creation and conservation of urban natural spaces.

- Law 5/2012 on Spatial Planning, Urban Planning and Landscape of the Valencian Community establishes the articulation of multi-scale planning instruments, such as the Territorial Strategy of the Valencian Community, the Territorial Action Plans and the General Urban Development Plan, promoting an integrated and strategic approach to urban development.
- Turia Garden, one of the largest urban parks in Spain, created in the old riverbed of the Turia River, which contributes to mitigating urban heat and improving biodiversity.
- Urban Orchard Network, a municipal initiative that promotes urban agriculture and citizen participation.
- Barrio La Pinada, the first sustainable eco-neighbourhood in Spain, based on circular economy and energy efficiency principles.
- GrowGreen Project (2018-2023), funded by the European Union, seeks to implement NbS in the Benicalap neighbourhood.

8.2.3 Research design

In the Valencia case study, key barriers and enablers for the implementation of NbS were identified through targeted, semi-structured interviews with selected stakeholders. In our study, NbS includes all types of green and blue infrastructure aimed at reducing risks from extreme weather events, such as heatwaves, particularly within the context of the city’s Green Infrastructure and Biodiversity Plan.

Interviewees participating in the study were identified using expert consultation and snowball sampling. They were conducted between June 2024 and January 2025 with a total of 11 stakeholders from five different sectors (see table 3 and appendix C), including academia and research, consultancy, public administration, associations, and developers involved in urban planning and environmental governance in Valencia.

Interview questions were organized into four sections: (A) background and role of the interviewee, (B) perspectives and experiences related to NbS, (C) knowledge and views on the "Green Infrastructure and Biodiversity Plan", and (D) closing questions and demographic data (see appendix D). All interviews were anonymized in accordance with the informed consent protocol approved by the Universitat Politècnica de València. With participants’ consent, interviews were recorded to ensure accuracy during analysis.

Table 3: List and details of interviewees - Valencia.

Number of interviewees (N)	Sector or affiliation
4	Academia and research
4	Consultancy
1	Former public administration
1	Association members
1	Developer

Interview transcripts were analysed using a qualitative content analysis. Codes were assigned to recurring ideas or concepts identified in the text and were grouped into predefined thematic clusters related to the barriers and enablers of NbS implementation. Codes were also linked to either of the two research foci: (1) general implementation of NbS in Valencia and (2) the governance, planning, and implementation of the city's Green and Biodiversity Plan. Multiple mentions of the same barrier or enabler by one interviewee were counted only once to avoid double counting.

The main research questions guiding this analysis were:

1. What are the enablers and barriers for implementing NbS in Valencia, with a particular focus on urban green infrastructure?
2. What are the implications of these findings for urban governance and climate resilience in the city?

8.2.4 Results and discussion

Barriers and enablers to NbS adoption and implementation in Valencia

Barriers

In terms of barriers, a total of 121 barriers were identified (figure 4), the most frequent being those related to lack of technical knowledge and specialised expertise. This lack limits the capacity to adequately design, implement and sustain nature-based interventions. Another relevant obstacle is path dependency, which reflects the difficulty of modifying established practices and rigid structures in favour of more sustainable approaches. This is compounded by a lack of political will and long-term commitment on the part of the authorities, as well as administrative and sectoral fragmentation, which prevents effective coordination between key actors and institutions.

While supportive frameworks, policies, and laws related to sustainability and climate adaptation do exist, one of the major barriers identified is the lack of specific guidelines or normative tools for the implementation of NbS. In practice, there are no standardized manuals or regulations to assist professionals, such as architects, engineers, or urban planners, in designing, contracting, and maintaining these solutions. This regulatory gap often leads to uncertainty or reliance on conventional infrastructure approaches. In addition, limitations in access to finance due both to its scarcity and the complexity of existing instruments further hinder implementation. Other factors identified include limited citizen participation in planning and decision-making processes, conflicts between actors or equity issues, limited availability of water resources, and problems associated with land ownership or availability. Altogether, these challenges continue to obstruct the systematic integration of NbS into public policies and territorial planning.

These results point to the existence of both institutional and structural obstacles that limit the deployment of NbS in the urban context of Valencia.

Figure 4: Frequency and classification of barriers to Nature-based Solutions implementation, based on interview data collected in Valencia.

The most frequently mentioned barriers to implementing NbS in Valencia are the **lack of expertise and knowledge** (N=21) and **path dependency** (N=20), both of which reflect deep-rooted structural challenges. The lack of expertise affects both public administration and the technical-professional sector. Although there are overarching policies and frameworks that support NbS, these are not accompanied by detailed regulations, technical guidelines, or implementation manuals that could assist administrators and professionals alike. This regulatory and operational gap contributes to uncertainty in project execution. Moreover, while universities are beginning to address NbS in their curricula, this is a relatively recent development, and for many years the topic was absent from academic training. As a result, many professionals lack the necessary background, and in the absence of a clear and supportive framework, it becomes easier and more comfortable to continue relying on conventional practices, ultimately reinforcing the second major barrier: path dependency.

“There is no regulation that accompanies those who sign the projects, so it is the responsibility of the engineer or architect. Better to carry on with business as usual.” - V9

Path dependency can be analysed through three lenses: technical-professional, public administration, and civil society. Beyond the professional and institutional inertia already mentioned, society itself tends to resist change. Many citizens hold a vision of the city as a clean, concrete dominated space and are reluctant to accept changes that might reduce their personal

benefits (such as parking space or urban aesthetics) for the sake of collective, long-term improvements. This cultural mindset represents a subtle but significant barrier to the widespread adoption of NbS.

“The concept of the city and how hygienic it has to be (what should be clean) is challenged by these solutions, as they break with traditional notions of urban space.” - V6

The lack and complexity of financing (N=8) and **lack of political will and long-term commitment** (N=10) in Valencia are closely interrelated. Annual budgets, bureaucratic rigidity, and short-term planning cycles make it difficult to secure the continuity required for NbS. These solutions often need consistent, long-term funding and maintenance, something that current systems are ill-equipped to provide. Similarly, **maintenance challenges and sector or administrative silos** (both with N=8 and N=10 respectively) point to institutional fragmentation, where responsibilities are unclear and no department or actor wants to assume long-term accountability. Contracts are not designed for long-term care, resulting in neglected or improperly maintained initiatives.

Land and water availability (N=5 each, 10 in total when combined) are also key physical constraints. NbS require adequate space and must be adapted to the local climate to function effectively with minimal irrigation or artificial inputs. While these are site specific issues, they are nonetheless critical to consider in the planning and design stages.

On a more positive note, barriers such as **risk aversion** (N=2) and **potential negative impacts** (N=1) were infrequently cited, suggesting that stakeholders recognize the general benefits of NbS and are not deterred by perceived risks. This could reflect growing awareness of the multiple co-benefits these solutions offer.

The effective implementation of NbS requires not only a solid technical foundation, but also an institutional, regulatory, financial and social environment that facilitates their development, consolidation and scalability. While NbS have demonstrated their potential to simultaneously address environmental, social and economic challenges, their large-scale adoption continues to face structural barriers that need to be addressed in a determined and coordinated manner.

The comparison between barriers to the implementation of NbS identified in the literature and those observed in the Valencia case study reveals significant overlaps, but also contextual distinctions.

In both the literature and the Valencia case, the lack of expertise and technical knowledge emerges as the most frequently mentioned barrier (Bernardi et al., 2019). The literature highlights this barrier across all stages of implementation, from planning to construction and maintenance, and notes the absence of adequate training programs, technical guidelines, and legal standards (ILO & IUCN, 2024; Sarabi et al., 2020; Solheim et al., 2021). In Valencia, this barrier is intensified by regulatory uncertainty and insufficient technical training, consistent with systemic gaps found in other urban contexts despite growing policy support. The lack of operational tools continues to constrain a transition away from conventional infrastructure (Martin et al., 2023).

Closely connected to this is the barrier of path dependency. In the literature, this barrier is associated with institutional lock-ins, habitual reliance on grey infrastructure, and regulatory inertia (Davies & Laforteza, 2019; IIASA, 2020; ILO & IUCN, 2024; Martin et al., 2023). Valencia adds a cultural dimension to this barrier, as interviewees pointed to citizen resistance shaped by dominant urban imaginaries that prioritize concrete over green aesthetics.

Lack of financing is another barrier that emerges consistently across both sources. In the literature, this is often tied to limited public budgets, low municipal autonomy, and the high upfront costs of NbS compared to grey alternatives (ILO & IUCN, 2024; Martin et al., 2021; Toxopeus & Polzin, 2021). Interviewees in Valencia pointed out how short-termism and bureaucratic rigidity mirror

financing constraints highlighted in the literature, reinforcing the challenge of ensuring continuity and scalability in NbS. Moreover, the absence of funding for maintenance was perceived as particularly important, especially for the long-term maintenance of projects, which interviewees see as essential for both the physical sustainability and public legitimacy of these interventions.

While the literature assigns significant importance to lack of evidence on performance and co-benefits, this theme is less prominent in the findings from our case study. This may reflect the city's relatively advanced trajectory in implementing green infrastructure and its participation in EU projects like GrowGreen, which may have provided sufficient local evidence to overcome initial scepticism (ILO & IUCN, 2024; Martin et al., 2023). However, this difference also underscores the ongoing challenge of generalizing local success stories to broader institutional systems, where decision-makers still demand quantifiable and comparative data on NbS effectiveness.

Lastly, sectoral silos and administrative fragmentation are well documented barriers in both sources, though more prominently in the literature (Sarabi et al., 2020, 2021). In Valencia, this manifests through unclear responsibilities and fragmented governance structures, consistent with findings across the literature.

Enablers

Focusing now on the enablers, 127 factors were identified as key enablers (Fig. 5) for the implementation of these solutions. Importantly, political will and long-term institutional commitment was perceived as the most critical enabler, which is essential to ensure the support, continuity and scalability of NbS. However, it is important to note that, in this case, this factor is also perceived by many as the major barriers currently present. Until recently, both the regional and municipal governments had demonstrated strong political commitment to increase climate resilience, resulting in robust plans, strategies, and policy frameworks. Nevertheless, many interviewees perceive that after the recent elections (July 2023), the new administrations have shown a reduced focus on climate-related priorities. As a result, respondents perceive political will as both an enabler and a barrier. While it existed in the past and enabled significant progress in the initial implementation of NbS, changes in government have led to a loss of long-term commitment. Many initiatives have not been followed up, not due to a general lack of willingness to maintain measures, but because the current administration has shown limited interest in continuing previous efforts. Therefore, although political will is seen as crucial, its dependence on political cycles emerges as a structural vulnerability for the sustained advancement of NbS.

The availability of financial tools and economic support models, including innovative financing instruments, also appears as a crucial element to overcome the economic barriers faced by these initiatives. A key challenge identified is that maintenance costs are often not included in project budgets, which puts at risk the long-term effectiveness and sustainability of the interventions.

In addition, the role of champions and active advocates of NbS has been widely cited as a driver for their adoption, as has the existence of evidence on their performance and co-benefits. This evidence reinforces the credibility of NbS and facilitates its acceptance by different stakeholders. Effective communication and awareness-raising strategies are identified as essential needs to foster social support and strengthen community participation. While some progress has been made, respondents highlight that broader and more consistent efforts are still required to build a solid and sustained base of public engagement. Finally, the flexibility and adaptability of these solutions allows for their implementation in diverse and evolving contexts, thus increasing their chances of success.

Figure 5: Frequency and classification of enablers to Nature based Solutions implementation, based on interview data collected in Valencia.

The most frequently mentioned enabler for implementing NbS in Valencia is **political will and long-term commitment** (N=29). This consensus underlines its critical role in driving effective NbS projects. A key local example is “Las Naves,” a public innovation center within the municipality that plays a central role in promoting and supporting social and urban innovation, including NbS. This illustrates the importance of local and regional initiatives, highlighting that successful implementation must be grounded in context specific, small-scale actions driven by committed institutions at the municipal level.

“European Union Green Capital (is) the result of a determined government that implemented this kind of planning.” - V1

Funding and financial tools and support (N=21) is the second most cited enabler, with a clear emphasis on the role of the European Union in providing both financial resources and regulatory guidance. Interestingly, the national government is largely absent in these discussions, reflecting the decentralized nature of Spain’s governance and the strong role played by autonomous communities and municipalities. European frameworks are viewed as enablers not only in terms of funding mechanisms, but also in the legislative alignment they promote. Additionally, there is increasing recognition that NbS should be framed as investments in ecosystem services, not as costs. This framing opens up new opportunities for blended financing, including public-private partnerships and emerging markets focused on green infrastructure.

“It (investing in green infrastructure) generates healthier environments: Citizens do not invest in NbS, they invest in health.” - V5

Three additional facilitators stand out due to the number of times they are mentioned: **champions and advocates** (N=16), **evidence on performance and co-benefits** (N=14), and **communication and raising awareness** (N=13). Together, these underline the importance of demonstrating the value of NbS to the public and involving communities throughout the process. Local champions, such as foundations, citizens' collectives, and technical professionals, are instrumental in driving change and building public trust. Effective communication strategies and accessible evidence on co-benefits are essential tools to foster engagement and facilitate maintenance responsibilities, which are often shared at the community level.

Closely related to these enablers is the need for active citizen participation in the design and implementation of NbS. Citizens should not only be informed but actively involved in decision-making and shared management. This direct involvement ensures that NbS are better aligned with local needs and context while strengthening the sense of ownership and agency within the community. Moreover, such engagement also contributes to greater social acceptance and can facilitate long-term maintenance and sustainability through deeper community commitment. Citizen science, participatory planning, and targeted awareness-raising are key to mobilizing local knowledge and ensuring inclusive, resilient initiatives. These approaches also translate technical and policy language into accessible narratives that make the benefits of NbS tangible and relevant to everyday life.

“Citizen opinion is increasingly recognised as a key element in planning and implementation processes. It is essential to count on the citizens, not only as a recipient of actions, but also as a source of knowledge about local problems and as an ally in the implementation of solutions. Their active participation makes it possible to identify real needs, enrich the design of interventions and strengthen community commitment to their implementation.” - V4

It is also notable that **supportive policies and legal frameworks** (N=6) and **expertise and knowledge** (N=4), while identified as facilitators, were far less frequently mentioned compared to their prominence as barriers in the corresponding analysis. This gap suggests that while the existence of supportive frameworks and technical expertise is appreciated when present, their absence is much more acutely felt, reinforcing the structural challenges previously identified.

A comparison between the enablers identified in the scientific literature and those found in the Valencia case study reveals both convergences and divergences, which reflect the influence of local governance structures and political dynamics.

One of the most prominent findings in Valencia is the strong role of political commitment and institutional willingness as a key enabler for implementing NbS. While this factor is also acknowledged in the literature, it is not consistently highlighted as the most cited enabler. In the broader literature, political commitment is often presented as a cross-cutting condition, closely tied to other enablers such as regulatory frameworks or actor participation (Calliari et al., 2022; ILO & IUCN, 2024). In contrast, the Valencia case elevates political will to a primary position, reflecting the strong influence of local political agendas on NbS implementation. The example of Las Naves illustrates how proactive municipal leadership can drive innovation, acting as both a policy incubator and a coordination node. However, the volatility associated with political cycles in the region also underscores a structural vulnerability; the success of NbS initiatives may hinge not only on technical or financial factors, but on the continuity of political priorities.

In line with existing literature (Martin et al., 2023), both the case study and prior studies emphasize the importance of funding mechanisms. Yet, the case of Valencia introduces a notable distinction, the dominant role of the European Union, both as a source of funding and as a provider of policy guidance, contrasted with the limited visibility of national institutions. This reflects Spain's

decentralized political system and suggests that future NbS strategies must be sensitive to multi-level governance dynamics, aligning local actions with supranational opportunities.

Another area of convergence relates to the role of evidence on NbS performance. Although the literature recognizes its potential as an enabler (Châles et al., 2023; IUCN, 2020; Scolobig et al., 2020; Somarakis et al., 2019), it often does so as a normative recommendation rather than as a demonstrated driver. In Valencia, while not the most cited enabler, the importance of communicating co-benefits and showcasing results is clearly appreciated by practitioners. This reflects a growing awareness of the political and social value of evidence in legitimizing investments and building trust among stakeholders.

The analysis of the main barriers and enablers of implementation of NbS in Valencia reveals a significant tension between political governance, institutional coordination and financial support. It reveals a clear need for context-sensitive, institutionally grounded, and culturally responsive approaches. While the main structural barriers such as lack of expertise, path dependency, and financial limitations are consistently recognized across contexts, the Valencia case study highlights additional challenges rooted in local perceptions of urban nature, fragmented governance structures, and the disconnect between ambitious policy frameworks and on-the-ground execution. At the same time, the enablers identified in both the literature and in Valencia show broad thematic alignment, yet their relative importance is shaped by the city's specific governance dynamics, and the critical role of local political leadership.

8.2.5 Summary and key messages

Local political commitment is crucial: Political will and long-term commitment is the most important enabler identified. Examples such as “Las Naves” and municipal strategic plans (València 2030, Green Infrastructure and Biodiversity Plan) demonstrate how local leadership can drive the effective adoption of NbS, especially at the urban scale.

Regulatory progress has been made, but operationalisation is lacking: Although Valencia has advanced strategic and regulatory frameworks, the absence of technical guidelines, manuals or specific regulations remains a critical barrier to the concrete implementation of NbS. This lack of clear tools reinforces the reliance on traditional solutions.

Funding is essential but complex: While European funding mechanisms have been key (e.g. the GrowGreen project), short-term budgets and bureaucratic rigidities limit the implementation of NbS in the city. Moreover, these solutions are often not seen as a long-term investment in spite of the ecosystem services and numerous co-benefits they may provide.

Effective implementation requires multi-scalar and multi-sectoral coordination: Lack of coordination between levels of government and between municipal departments obstructs the integrated development of NbS. This administrative and sectoral fragmentation also impacts the governance and long-term maintenance of green infrastructure.

The role of local actors is decisive: Local champions, such as citizen groups, foundations and committed professionals, as well as communication and awareness-raising strategies, are key to generating social acceptance, facilitating shared maintenance and consolidating these solutions over time.

Tensions between the structural and the operational persist: Despite the commitment and long-term vision at the strategic level, structural challenges, such as lack of specific technical capacities, regulatory complexity or lack of stable funding, remain significant obstacles that need to be addressed through coordinated action.

Previous experience makes Valencia a benchmark: Despite facing significant structural and institutional barriers, such as lack of technical expertise, regulatory gaps, and political and administrative fragmentation, Valencia has managed to implement emblematic projects like Central Park, Turia Garden, and La Huerta. These initiatives were made possible through a combination of factors that helped overcome systemic challenges, including strong political leadership at key moments, access to European funding, and the active role of local innovation hubs such as Las Naves. Moreover, the city has built a growing network of engaged stakeholders and professionals who championed these approaches and contributed to developing local expertise. This highlights that while barriers remain, targeted enabling conditions, particularly political will, financial support, and committed local actors can create windows of opportunity for advancing NbS in complex urban contexts.

8.3 Ogliastro, Italy

This section presents the Ogliastro study case, which aims to identify and analyse the key barriers and enablers to effective fire risk management in the region, supporting the development of locally adapted strategies for wildfire mitigation and climate change adaptation. While the primary focus is on wildfires, the study also indirectly addresses related hazards such as heatwaves and droughts by promoting the design and maintenance of fire risk management approaches that integrate both NbS and other traditional strategies, in line with the concept of “fire-smart solutions”. Through a combination of participatory workshops, stakeholder engagement and expert consultation, the study identifies key barriers and enablers for implementing fire risk prevention and mitigation strategies. Workshops and focus groups were organized with a range of local stakeholders, including representatives from territorial and regional fire management entities, local government representatives, agro-livestock operators, volunteer organizations, and members of the tourism sector to foster dialogue and co-develop locally adapted strategies.

The structure of the case study begins with an introduction to the region and its fire risk challenges. It then explores the policies and governance frameworks relevant to the implementation of NbS for fire risk management in Ogliastro. A detailed description of the research design follows, outlining the two participatory methods used (stakeholder workshops and focus groups). The results and discussion section presents the main findings from these sessions, including stakeholder’s perception of wildfire risks in the region, reported current fire risk prevention and mitigation efforts and key barriers and enablers to both land management and fire risk-prevention measures. The case study finally concludes with a summary of key insights and a short list of suggestions aimed to enable the development of locally adapted fire risk management and climate change adaptation strategies.

8.3.1 Background/Case study overview

Ogliastro, a former province in eastern Sardinia region, Italy, is a geographically isolated area known for its rugged landscape and small population. With approximately 57,600 inhabitants, it was the least populous province in Italy. The area is characterized by extensive forest cover (around 42%), a strong agricultural sector, and a growing urban-rural interface. In recent decades, Ogliastro has seen a booming tourism industry, especially during the summer months when visitors arrive to popular destinations like Tortoli, Lotzorai, and Cardedu.

The area, as well as other regions across the Mediterranean Basin, faces multiple climate related hazards, including heatwaves, droughts, and, most critically, wildfires, which often create cascading risks. Climatic conditions in the region are undergoing changes, with extreme weather events such as heatwaves and droughts becoming more frequent and projected to intensify in

the coming years (Arab et al., 2021). Across the Mediterranean, declining fuel moisture due to rising temperatures is projected to significantly increase weather-driven fire danger (De Rigo et al., 2017). As a result, several fire-prone regions, such as Sardinia, have experienced hundreds of thousands of hectares burned during critical wildfire events (Almeida et al., 2023), a lengthening of the fire season and an increase in fire severity (Eberle & Higuera Roa, 2022; Rodrigues et al., 2023; Ruffault et al., 2018). In Sardinia, these dynamics are further amplified by structural land-use changes, including widespread land abandonment and spontaneous shrub encroachment, which contribute to fuel accumulation and heighten the likelihood of severe wildfire events (Salis et al., 2019). This unplanned forest growth (Agnoletti et al., 2022) brings with it several ecosystem services, such as enhanced carbon storage, improved water infiltration, availability of forest products, soil stabilization. However, according to Bobiec et al., (2025), this process and the forest-centric conservation policies may undermine the preservation of traditional, multifunctional landscapes shaped by traditional agro-silvo-pastoral practices, which are essential for maintaining local biodiversity (Agnoletti & Santoro, 2022) and delivering a range of ecosystem services (Pardini & Nori, 2011).

In Sardinia, risks are managed through the Regional Functional Center (Decree of the President of the Region n. 156/2014), also called “Centro Funzionale Decentrato” (CFD), which aims to support emergency alerts and civil protection operations with continuous, year-round service. The CFD operates by risk areas (where risks are managed individually), and at the moment only two areas are active: the hydrogeological and hydraulic area, and wildland fire risk area.

Fire risk is managed through targeted planning at multiple levels and the integrated use of various techniques, ensuring the safeguarding of life, property and resources through the prevention, detection, control, restriction and suppression of fire in forest and other vegetation in rural areas. Borrowing terminology from adaptation strategies, fire risk management in Sardinia involves a mix of organizational measures (governance and planning), grey infrastructure (look-out, water points, helicopter bases), and biological approaches (prevention measures through fuel management and prescribed burning). Although, biodiversity protection and enhancement are not directly and explicitly mentioned.

8.3.2 NbS policy and governance

Definition of NbS in the local context

NbS, as defined by the IUCN (2020), are actions that protect, manage, or restore natural and modified ecosystems to address societal challenges while supporting both human well-being and biodiversity. As outlined in Section 7, NbS use natural processes to provide sustainable, cost-effective, and multifunctional approaches to reducing risks, while also addressing environmental, social, and economic issues, and promoting climate resilience and sustainable development. They are especially valued for enhancing ecosystem resilience and lowering human vulnerability to various hazards (Turner et al., 2022). Forests are often cited as examples of NbS because of their role in carbon sequestration and the many ecosystem services they provide (Keesstra et al., 2024). However, forests are increasingly threatened by climate change, facing more frequent and severe disturbances like heatwaves, droughts, wildfires, storms, and pest outbreaks, all of which can weaken their ability to deliver key services (Larsen et al., 2022; Lecina-Diaz et al., 2023). In this context, NbS can be an effective tool to help mitigating forest damages and losses, such as those due by wildfires. In this particular framework, NbS are measures aimed at mitigating the negative effects of changing fire regimes Castaldo & Mahmoud, 2024 while combining climate mitigation benefits with ecosystem restoration and various other socio-economic advantages (Keesstra et al., 2024). Perhaps using a more narrowly definition, Castaldo & Mahmoud (2024)

stated that “*NbS in wildfire management are measures which intervene on biomass reduction to control the fire regime in order to foster more fire-resistant/resilient environments*”.

In recent years, there has been a significant rise in the number of studies focusing on fire management and NbS; however, in practice, the NbS framework has been largely underutilized into management practices and policymaking, resulting in remaining challenges for funding and deployment at scale (Smeenk et al., 2024; FirESmart project, 2020). This is mainly due to the predominant emphasis on fire suppression and the lack of coordinated policies across fire-related sectors (Castaldo & Mahmoud, 2024; Mahmoud, 2024).

Keesstra et al. (2024), drawing on existing literature on the potential of NbS for climate change adaptation and DRR, and referencing current definitions and criteria from the IUCN and the European Commission, identify NbS approaches applicable to forested landscapes for reducing wildfire risks and impacts. One of those approaches is *close-to-nature and adaptive forestry*, a concept refers to sustainable forest management that works in harmony with natural ecosystems (Kalapodis & Sakkas, 2024; Vacchiano et al., 2020). This approach can substantially lower the risk of wildfire in forested areas through several measures (Keesstra et al., 2024; Vacchiano et al., 2020), including converting monocultures into diverse, uneven-aged mixed-species forests (e.g., Del Río et al., 2017) and planting fire-resistant or fire-retardant species (e.g., Moris et al., 2023) to reduce wildfire risks and slow fire spread. These practices are especially relevant for pine monocultures, where the flammable understory and dry lower branches increase fire vulnerability. By applying such nature-based methods, important ecosystem services can be preserved.

Another key strategy is the use of *fire-resistant vegetation*. Since certain plant species are more flammable than others, adapting the species composition of a landscape by introducing fire-resistant plants can significantly reduce wildfire risk (Casartelli & Mysiak, 2023). This also enhances habitat diversity and supports biodiversity, contributing to more resilient ecosystems. Meanwhile, *prescribed fire* is another tool used in sustainable forest management. These are controlled, low-intensity fires intentionally set to reduce excess dry biomass and deadwood (OECD, 2023). When applied correctly, prescribed fires decrease the chances of severe wildfires, promote fire-adapted species, recycle nutrients, and improve overall ecosystem health. Although, it cannot be neglected the public stigma surrounding the negative effects of prescribed burns (i.e., impact on atmospheric chemistry and air quality), which impacts their use near residential areas (Petralia & Potosnak, 2024).

Finally, *agroforestry*, a land use system combining trees with crops or livestock, also plays a role in fire risk reduction. Research from the Mediterranean region (Damianidis et al., 2021) showed that agroforestry areas experienced fewer wildfires than forests or shrublands, due to the disruption of continuous fuel loads and minimization of flammable aboveground vegetation, making it a promising strategy for both wildfire prevention and ecosystem conservation.

It is worth noting that recently, researchers (e.g., Ascoli et al., 2022; Leone et al., 2020; Pulido et al., 2023; Tedim et al., 2016) have focused attention on the concept of *fire-smart management*, defined as an “*integrated approach primarily based on fuel treatments through which the socio-economic impacts of fire are minimised while its ecological benefits are maximized*” (Hirsch et al., 2001). The concept has been reinforced as a viable pathway toward more fire-resistant and resilient landscapes (e.g., Ascoli et al., 2022; Moreira et al., 2020; Regos et al., 2023; Tedim et al., 2016) proposed it as a NbS. Recently, Ascoli et al. (2022) identified the main characteristics of fire-smart solutions:

- **Recognition:** Acknowledge wildfire prevention as an ecosystem service that supports a sustainable, circular economy.

- **Policy Integration:** Align sectoral policies (like forestry, agriculture, energy, tourism) into a unified wildfire risk management strategy, supported by public and EU funding.
- **Strategic Planning:** Optimize fuel reduction efforts to use limited resources efficiently and reduce wildfire risk at a landscape scale, and leverage economically efficient treatment methods (e.g., silviculture, grazing, agriculture).
- **Land Coordination:** Expand treatment areas by grouping public and private lands, promoting shared goals among stakeholders.
- **Diverse Treatments:** Apply varied, ecologically informed fuel management methods (e.g., grazing, prescribed burns) as NbS.
- **Market Valorisation:** Promote and certify products from fuel management practices to support local economies and incentivize fire mitigation.
- **Community Engagement:** Involve local communities in wildfire prevention through participatory processes and shared responsibility.

Overall NbS policies in Italy and Sardinia

Fire management in Italy is based on a strong national legal framework, including the Law n° 353/2000 and the Legislative Decree n° 120/2021, but then all Italian regions have their own legislation and policies, which must both comply with national legislation and define specific measures and responsibilities for the different phases of wildfire management, based on local climate, topography, vegetation types and socio-economic conditions. Similarly, due to the process of regionalization started in early '70s, all Italian Regions were allowed to develop regional forest policies based on their peculiar needs. In this case the lack of a common legal backbone till 2018 created a high degree of inhomogeneity in terms of forest monitoring and management, as well as policy implementation, dynamism and coordination (RAF Italia, 2019).

Regarding fire management, NbS (and related) concepts are little, and not explicitly, integrated in Italy's main policies and instruments. This is evident when considering that Italy's comprehensive wildfire management strategy is largely based on Law n° 353/2000, which focuses on "the protection and preservation of the national forest heritage as a vital resource for quality of life" but then classifies wildfires as a serious civil protection issue, highlighting the risk they pose to homes, infrastructure, and human activities, particularly in densely populated areas. The Law mandated the administrative Regions for planning the forecasting, prevention and firefighting activities in a regional strategic tool called AIB plan (*Anti Incendio Boschivo*, in Italian) (Pandey et al., 2023; Regione Autonoma della Sardegna, 2025). The AIB plan outlines several key components of fire management, including daily fire danger forecasting and alert systems, development of static fire risk maps, and regional guidelines for civil protection planning, covering evacuation procedures and wildfire response, especially in wildland-urban interface areas. It also addresses the organization of active fire-fighting operations and includes measures for fire prevention and risk mitigation. In Sardinia, this framework is complemented by the Regional Fire Regulations, which set rules for fire use (e.g., prescribed burns) and outline actions to prevent wildfire ignition (in particular firebreaks opening and clearing, areas adjacent to public roads clearing), with little reference to integrated fuel management strategies.

Regarding forest management, only in 2018, the national law on Forests and Forestry Supply Chains (TUFF, *Testo Unico Foreste e Filiere* in Italian) set unified regulatory guidelines and sector coordination for the Italian regions and relevant ministries for the "programming, planning, protection, and active management" of the national forest heritage. Its primary objective is to promote the sustainability of forest resources by creating a multilevel institutional competence structure for forest planning. This measure is intended to recognize Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) as a tool to ensure an increase in carbon absorption, as well as the production of quality wood products. TUFF also outlined key principles governing the forestry

sector, such as protecting ecological diversity, preventing natural and human-caused risks, and involving local communities in forestry development. Finally, in 2022, the National Forest Strategy (NFS) was published. The NFS takes an innovative and science-based approach also to key issues in wildfire governance, such as the coordination and integration of prevention and active fire-fighting, the alignment of forest, agro-pastoral, and environmental policies with wildfire management strategies, regulatory updates, and access to wildfire-related data (Ascoli et al., 2022a; Bacciu et al., 2025). The strategy aims to balance wildfire risk reduction with ecosystem resilience and biodiversity protection, integrate local needs with European policy goals, and combine ecological science, traditional knowledge, and technology to promote sustainable, cost-effective forest management and coherent cross-sectoral policies.

Although these recent crucial advancements that could have important implications on the integration of NbS concepts into fire management policies and instruments, their implementation still lack for different reasons, such as insufficient fundings or silos governance or lack of formal adoption of the new policies.

In Sardinia, public forests and almost half of the protected areas are managed by the Regional Forest Agency for Land and Environment of Sardinia (FORESTAS), with the aim of conserving habitats, supporting forest value chains and favouring resilience to human induced and natural hazards (Regional Law n° 8/2016). The foundational framework for the island's forest and environmental policies is represented by Sardinia's Regional Forest and Environmental Plan (PFAR), adopted in 2007. Despite its official expiration in 2018, the PFAR continues to guide regional forestry initiatives and is referenced in subsequent legislation. It includes five lines of action that form the general framework of the proposed measures within regional forest planning and serve as the reference for the programming of sector-specific interventions. Forest fire prevention measures are included in "Protection" line of action and are represented by two sub-action including basically all activities traditionally encompassed by the general concept of preventive silviculture for fire protection purposes. The objectives can be broadly categorized into two areas: on one hand, the reduction of biomass and necromass to lower the potential for fire ignition (also including the "prescribed burning" approach); on the other hand, as actions aimed at improving the structure of forest stands through silvicultural practices designed to increase their resilience (including renaturalization approaches). Hierarchical planning with a regional level is then followed by spatial or "district" planning and detailed planning on a local forest scale (Piano forestale particolareggiato, PFP).

The 2016 Regional Law No. 8, known as the "Forest Law of Sardinia," was introduced to fill the gap in comprehensive forestry legislation. It prioritizes wildfire prevention and control as a core element of forest management (Title IV), promoting the use of predictive systems, research, and innovative fire management techniques. The law mandates the development of the Regional Fire Prevention Plan (AIB) and sets standards for volunteer coordination, regulations, and penalties. It also defines the structure of the regional fire management system, involving the Regional Civil Protection, the Forest and Environmental Monitoring Corps, and FORESTAS. Beyond fire management, the law supports the forest economy by encouraging agro-silvo-pastoral practices, establishing a regional register of forest enterprises, promoting collaborative forest management, and supporting forest certification. It also aims to strengthen the timber value chain and the cultivation of cork oak.

Despite extensive legislation and planning activities, the region struggles with limited adoption of preventive silviculture for fire protection purposes or the implementation of NbS that could yield multiple benefits. Current fire management policies remain largely focused on suppression, often neglecting broader land management challenges, an oversight that may inadvertently contribute to the emergence of more flammable and fire-prone landscapes (Kirschner et al., 2024). According to the data reported in 2014 by the FORESTAS website, 88,000 hectares out of

220,000 hectares of regional land are under management, with only 51,000 hectares covered by Detailed Forest Planning. Actual forest management interventions have been carried out on just 9,400 hectares. Moreover, DRR efforts in the area are further hindered by a lack of dialogue and cooperation between local experts and key stakeholders such as farmers, tourist operators, firefighting personnel and policy and decision makers, within the framework of a policy cycle. This lack of communication limits the guidance available to policymakers for informed decision making.

8.3.3 Research design

The Ogliastro DEM8 aims at providing the science/knowledge base needed to assist policy and decision-makers on the co-definition of adaptation and mitigation pathways effective in reducing the impacts of fire events in the short- and medium term under a changing climate. Towards this aim, innovative tools and stakeholder engagement including participatory approaches are being developed.

First of all, as previously reported in section 7, key barriers and enablers for fire risk governance, including mitigation and adaptation strategies, were identified at two local DRR workshops. The workshops were organized in November 2023 as part of the DEM activities and aimed to foster dialogue and collaboration among stakeholders involved in fire risk management.

In both cases, stakeholders were identified through expert consultation and targeted invitations to ensure a balanced representation of relevant sectors. The workshops gathered 36 participants (see Table 4 and Appendix C), divided into two events with two stakeholder groups: one comprising local administrators and representatives from territorial and regional fire management entities (n=19), and the other consisting of agro-livestock operators (n=17). A focus group was organized online to reach the target group of tourism operators (n=5), because engaging this stakeholder group proved challenging. This distinction allowed for surveys and discussions to be better tailored to the needs, perceptions, and opinions of each group. Each discussion session lasted approximately 2 hours. Representatives from local communities, economic sectors (particularly tourism and agriculture), political decision-makers, and institutions responsible for fire risk management participated. Among these institutions were the Forestry and Environmental Vigilance Body of Sardinia (CFVA), the regional forestry agency FORESTAS, the national fire and rescue service, civil protection authorities (General Directorate of Civil Protection), volunteer organizations, and local government representatives.

It is important to highlight that in the organized discussions about mitigation and adaptation strategies, we did not explicitly refer to the “NbS solution” concept. Indeed, communicating the concept of NbS to stakeholders such as farmers or firefighters can be particularly challenging. These groups often operate within highly practical, results-oriented frameworks and may not immediately see the relevance of NbS, which can sometimes be perceived as abstract or overly academic. To overcome this difficulty, we proposed several approaches (NbS compatible) towards fire-risk mitigation and climate change adaptation. The approaches included governance and planning strategies, grey/green infrastructure, and land management and prevention options and strategies (including NbS and fire-smart (FS) measures). These are described in detail below.

Governance and planning

- **Integration of fire risk into urban planning** - Incorporating fire risks into spatial and urban development plans can help avoid the expansion of settlements into high-risk areas, apply risk assessment and implement measures to protect lives and infrastructure while guiding sustainable land use.

- **Integration of forest and agricultural planning** - Coordinating land use strategies to manage forests and agricultural areas together can encourage multifunctional landscapes that support biodiversity, maintain open areas to break fuel continuity, and enhance rural livelihoods.
- **Integration of fire prevention in regional forest management plans** - Embedding fire prevention objectives into “Territorial Forest Management Plans” and/or “District Forest Plans” could align forest management at a landscape scale with fire resilience goals, ensuring ecological coherence, improving biodiversity and efficient use of public resources.
- **Community-based insurance products** - Risk-sharing tools designed and managed at the community level to respond to fire risk aimed at strengthening local capacity to recover from wildfire damage, fosters collective responsibility, and encourages risk-aware land management and NbS practices. It must be highlighted, though, that different NbS offer varying levels of fire protection, and thus different types of insurance schemes. Forests managed primarily for biodiversity may be more vulnerable to fire and offer less protection to surrounding areas. In contrast, NbS focused on fuel reduction, such as thinning, controlled burning, grazing, planting fire-resistant species, creating firebreaks, and promoting mixed-use landscapes (e.g., forest-agriculture mosaics), can significantly reduce wildfire risk for neighbouring communities (Schinko et al., 2023).

Grey/green infrastructure and buffer zones

- **Development and maintenance of infrastructure aimed at containing the spread of wildfires** - While this may include some traditional ("grey") elements like firebreaks, access roads, or water reservoirs, when designed with ecological considerations, these interventions can function as green infrastructure. For example, strategic firebreaks integrated into mosaic landscapes (e.g., pastures, crops, managed forests) reduce fire spread while maintaining habitat connectivity; also, water points for firefighting can also serve as habitat for wildlife or enhance the local water cycle [NbS + FS].
- **Biomass reduction aimed at protecting the wildland-urban interface (WUI) areas** - It reduces fuel loads and the intensity of potential wildfires, thus protecting homes, infrastructure, and public safety, reducing the costs of emergency response and post-fire recovery.

Land management and prevention options

- **Prescribed burning** - Controlled use of fire under specific conditions (e.g., small-scale, low-intensity) to reduce accumulated biomass (OECD, 2023). This practice helps prevent large, high-intensity wildfires, protecting communities and infrastructure, while also maintaining fire-adapted ecosystems and promoting biodiversity [NbS].
- **Preventive silviculture** in forested or wooded areas (public/private) - Forest management practices (e.g., thinning, pruning in strategic high-fire risk areas) aimed at reducing fuel loads and improving forest structure. Fuel reduction can be achieved through both direct, strategic interventions financed by public authorities, and indirect, non-strategic actions carried out by local land managers, with or without public support, when economic returns justify the investment (e.g., associated with grazing, cropping, or wood harvesting) [FS].
- **Conversion of Conifer Plantations to Broadleaved Forests** - This approach consists of adapting the species composition of the landscape by replacing fire-prone conifer species with more resilient broadleaved species (Fernandes, 2013; Pais et al., 2020). Such an

intervention contributes to lowering fire intensity and frequency, and also increases diversity in habitats, and contributes to long-term forest stability [NbS + FS].

- **Mosaic Landscape Management** - Creating a patchwork of land uses to break fuel continuity through agroforestry and silvopastoralism (e.g., Campos et al., 2022; Pulido et al., 2023). This type of management reduces the spread of wildfires, supports local agriculture, and maintains landscape diversity, enhancing soil quality and providing habitats for wildlife (Damianidis et al., 2021), which benefits both biodiversity and rural livelihoods [FS].

Table 4: List and details of workshops and focus group participants - Ogliastra.

Method	Number of participants	Sector or affiliation
Participatory workshop + questionnaire	19	Institutional and operational actors: members of the regional Environmental Surveillance and Forestry Corps of Sardinia, Forestas Agency, firefighters, civil protection, volunteer associations, and representatives of local municipalities
Participatory workshop + questionnaire	17	Agro-livestock operators: farmers, shepherds, and agricultural entrepreneurs
Focus group (online)	5	Tourism operators: campsite and hotel owners, agritourism facilities

Both the workshops and focus group began with an introductory session designed to provide participants with a broad understanding of the global context of climate change, the need for climate adaptation, and the specific wildfire situation in Ogliastra. This segment also introduced The HuT project, its objectives, and the tools and strategies (modelling, financial and participatory tools) proposed to improve fire risk management and resilience in the region. Using a Collaborative Learning (CL) approach (Daniels & Walker, 1996), the session emphasized fostering enhanced communication and collaboration among stakeholders as a crucial step towards co-developing locally adapted, resilient strategies.

Data collection within the two workshops followed a mixed-method approach, combining an initial survey with structured discussions. The survey was tailored to each stakeholder group and included two sections: 1) participants' perceptions of wildfire risks and dynamics and 2) direct experiences with fires and prevention measures. Participants subsequently engaged in structured discussions around two key themes. In the first part of discussion, they examined the barriers and enablers influencing the implementation of land management and fire prevention strategies. To facilitate dialogue, participants were provided with a concise list of pre-identified barriers and enablers as a starting point for discussion. The second discussion focused on potential strategies and interventions for land management and wildfire prevention. Here, participants were invited to share their opinions and ideas, building upon a set of proposals initially identified by CNR and CMCC through an extensive literature review.

8.3.4 Results and discussion

Stakeholder perceptions of wildfire risks in Ogliastra

Survey results indicate that all institutional actors (N=19) perceive wildfire risk as high or moderate for their community and territory. All foresee changes in fire frequency or extent over the past 30 years. Among the 17 agro-livestock operators surveyed, most view wildfires as a significant problem, with only one considering them of little relevance. The majority (n=12) rate the fire risk as high, two see it as extreme, and three as moderate. Regarding fire trends, nine participants anticipated changes, while four reported no variation, and another four were uncertain. These findings highlight a strong awareness and concern about wildfire risks in the region (Fig. 6). In fact, 10 out of the 17 agro-livestock operators reported having suffered material losses and damages due to wildfires before, with the majority of them (N=7) reporting the use of personal savings to fund the necessary repairs.

Figure 6: Distribution of concern levels regarding wildfire-related impacts in the Ogliastra area, based on participants’ responses from workshops. Rating scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is "not concerned" and 5 "very much concerned".

When it comes to their perceived changes in the territory, both institutional actors and agro-livestock operators have mainly noticed longer wildfire seasons. Institutional actors listed “larger and more dangerous wildfires” as the second most important change, while agro-livestock operators believe it is an increase in the number of events, followed by “more extensive or more dangerous wildfires”, “greater property damage”, and “greater media coverage of the wildfire season”.

Institutional actors placed less emphasis on “increased media coverage of the wildfire season” and “greater property damage”.

Survey responses indicate that climate change impacts (e.g., prolonged droughts and heatwaves) are seen by both groups of actors as the main driver of changes in wildfire intensity and frequency. Other drivers include the abandonment of agro-silvo-pastoral and forestry practices, vegetation growth, and negligence from those living or working in rural areas. Institutional actors also point to a decline in firefighting and prevention efforts and indifference toward prevention policies, whereas agro-livestock operators emphasize recklessness from those unfamiliar with the landscape. Notably, all participants expect wildfires to become more intense and frequent in the future.

As it can be observed from figure 6, both groups exhibit greater concerns for the suffering and loss of human lives, impacts on local economy (e.g. impacts to livestock, agriculture, and tourism sectors), and damage to local systems and biodiversity. However, while agro-livestock operators appear more worried about the latter, institutional actors report the suffering and loss of human lives as their main concern. Both groups show somewhat lesser concern for wildlife loss, damage to buildings, and disruption to infrastructure. Overall, institutional actors tend to show slightly greater concern compared to agro-livestock operators across most areas.

Reported fire risk prevention and mitigation efforts

With regard to the institutional actors, the question concerning fire prevention and mitigation efforts changed slightly to take into consideration institutional duties across local and regional stakeholders.

The section for local administrators was completed by seven out of 17 institutional actors, with two not responding to either section. Among them, six participants indicated that their municipality adopted a Municipal Civil Protection Plan. When asked to rate the ease of compliance with regional fire prevention prescriptions on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 represented "not at all easy" and 5 "very easy", results showed that cutting hay and stubble, along with removing residues along roads and high-risk municipal property perimeters, was perceived as the easiest measure to implement, with an average score of 3.0 (n=4). In contrast, eliminating vegetal fuels along roads (average 2.0, n=4) and ensuring the accessibility and availability of fire hydrants (average 2.4, n=5) were considered more difficult.

Four participants reported that their municipality had developed strategies to inform the resident population about forest and interface fire risks, while one participant reported that this has been done so for tourists. Only two respondents stated that their municipality has developed short-term and/or long-term land planning to prevent and mitigate forest fire risks, noting that this was done with the municipality's own resources.

When asked about specific preventive actions implemented at the municipal level, only one participant confirmed that a combination of techniques such as silvicultural methods (thinning, clearing, and logging), mechanical and manual bush removal, controlled burns for managing stubble and crop residues, and biomass reduction projects, had been fully or partially implemented. Another respondent indicated that its municipality had integrated fire risk considerations into urban planning, while a third noted that only mechanical or manual clearing had been carried out. In executing these prevention and mitigation activities, the involvement of a variety of actors was indicated, including farms (N=2), forestry enterprises (N=3), cooperatives (N=3), and volunteers (N=2), as well as community watch groups, the Forestas Agency, and the Forestry and Environmental Surveillance Corps.

The section of the survey dedicated to regional entities responsible for fire management was completed by ten out of the 17 institutional actors. When asked to indicate which actions for fire risk prevention and mitigation are carried out by their entity/organisation, the most commonly reported measures included civil protection planning (N=10), public communication and awareness efforts (N=6), and integrated fire management with forestry, agricultural, and urban planning (N=6). Additionally, five respondents reported managing fuels, and three mentioned other actions such as environmental education, operator training for controlled burning, road cleaning, and fire extinguishment.

The six participants who selected "integrated fire management" were asked to specify which aspects were identified and implemented. All six indicated that the integration of forestry planning to prevent forest fires within "Territorial Forestry Plans" and/or "District Forestry Plans" had been implemented. Of these six participants, four indicated that projects aimed at improving the resistance and resilience of agroforestry ecosystems to forest fires had been carried out, and only one participant indicated they had been identified. Of the six participants, only one showed that the integration of forestry planning with agricultural planning had been identified. The aspect of informing urban planning with territorial forestry plans that identify areas exposed to fire danger was identified by two out of six respondents while implemented by one out of six. Only one participant indicated that defining an integrated approach that includes identifying vulnerable areas and susceptible populations with active community engagement in prevention, preparedness, and response efforts had been identified.

Overall, these findings highlight a number of challenges in implementing fire prevention and mitigation measures. While some municipalities and entities reported engagement in planning and awareness efforts, integrated fire management, fuel reduction, and land-use planning appears limited, the need for greater investment and coordination efforts in the region was emphasised.

In the case of agro-livestock operators, 14 respondents reported taking measures to protect themselves, their families, and their properties from fires. The measures include: compliance with regulations on agricultural and forestry management of stubble and crop residues (N=10), the use of mechanical means to clear the property area adjacent to public roads from hay, brambles, and dry material of any kind (N=8), grazing of livestock on the property for cleaning purposes (N=8), brush clearing to reduce vertical and horizontal continuity of vegetation and the excessive presence of shrub species (N=3), the creation of a firebreak or a green grazing strip around rural buildings and livestock enclosures (N=2), the creation of a plowed strip (in the case of agricultural crops) along the perimeter adjacent to the forest (N=2), and the use of cultural interventions (thinning, spacing, clearing, high stand establishment) to develop forest stands with a more natural structure and composition that improves their resistance to fires. No participant reported the use of prescribed burning or the creation of strips free of dry materials (in the case of land located on the outskirts or within urban areas). Likewise, there were no reports of the use of insurance policies on their properties to protect in the eventual occurrence of wildfires.

Nevertheless, when questioned about the ease of implementing such fire prevention practices, cleaning the area adjacent to public roads from hay, brambles, and dry material of any nature, as well as complying with agricultural and forestry regulations regarding stubble burning, crop and forestry residues, bare, bushy or treed pastures, as well as temporarily unproductive agricultural land, were considered the easiest measures to take or implement. Meanwhile, the creation of protective strips free of any dry material was considered slightly more difficult.

When asked whether public authorities should require residents in high-risk areas to have fire insurance, only two out of 17 participants agreed. Seven opposed the idea, and another seven were unsure. One participant suggested offering incentives instead of making insurance mandatory.

Barriers and enablers to land management and risk-prevention measures (including NbS) in Ogliastra

Barriers

During the discussions with both groups of participants, the barriers to the implementation of land management practices throughout the use of land management and fire prevention activities were discussed. As shown in figure 7, perceptions and opinions varied significantly between the three groups. Therefore, the following sub-sections provide a detailed analysis of these perspectives, first from institutional actors and then from agro-livestock operators and actors from the tourism sector.

Figure 7: Frequency and classification of barriers to Nature based Solutions-compatible wildfire prevention and mitigation measures, based on data collected from workshops and focus group in Ogliastra.

Institutional actors

As it can be observed in figure 7, during debates, these actors indicated their belief that a **lack of supportive policies and legal frameworks** (N=15) is the most significant barrier to the implementation of land management and risk prevention measures in the Ogliastra region. In this case, they indicate that the lack of specific integrated policies, which consider the development of particular bio-economies also aimed at mitigating the phenomenon of territorial abandonment, is a challenge. Moreover, they find that, in combination with other challenges such as excessive bureaucracy, some regulations can delay or complicate the implementation of preventive measures. In particular, it was considered that rigid forest management rules can discourage landowners from taking action, as they risk facing penalties. In their opinion, inadequate forest management has turned Sardinia into a predominantly forested region, posing challenges in fire risk management. Although in Sardinia there exists the PRAF, a regional environmental forestry

plan adopted in 2007, a key gap remains: the absence of territorial risk forestry planning to bridge regional strategy and local forest management. The FORESTAS Agency has developed 13 PFP (detailed planning on a local forest scale) and approved 9, yet, without intermediate risk planning, their effectiveness in fire prevention is limited.

In second place, participants considered that **societal challenges** (N=13) are very significant in the region. In this case, this is considered to be due to an existing sense of helplessness and perceived ineffectiveness of current firefighting strategies in the communities. Participants identified societal challenges as a major regional issue, particularly a sense of resignation and helplessness in local communities. This feeling is linked to the perceived ineffectiveness of firefighting strategies, deemed inadequate for controlling wildfires beyond the system's capacity. As one participant noted:

“We can’t even put out the small fires anymore—not with helicopters, not with planes.”

This leads to fatalism, leaving people feeling disempowered and discouraged. Another factor contributing to societal fragility is the abandonment of land due to depopulation and aging rural communities. Observers, such as firefighters, lament the lack of land stewardship:

“The land is abandoned, and it’s us who are not doing what should be done.”

Additionally, some participants noted a loss of collective memory about past extreme events, which can lead to underestimating fire risks and reduced preparedness:

“Sometimes we forget the events that have affected our territories.”

Combined with a low-risk perception among the population, and a lack of environmental awareness and education, the siloed mentality often prevents actors from taking actions. Participants also pointed to depopulation, an aging population, and the decline of traditional land management practices, which have all contributed to environmental risks and made fire prevention more difficult.

The **lack and complexity of financing** was referred to on six occasions. According to the participants, not only are there high costs linked to the management of fires in the territory, but there is also a need for prudent use of the available funding. Participants noted that fire prevention and land management have high costs, resulting in a lack of economic incentive to maintain certain vegetation like reeds. In Tortoli, for example, reeds are burned because they are no longer harvested. This illustrates how the loss of viable biomass uses leads to combustible material accumulation. One participant also highlighted how fire management operations, such as activating helicopters for extinguishing fires, place a heavy financial burden on public resources. This problem is worsened by limited access to funding:

“If I don’t have money to clear my land, and you fine me anyway, what can I do?”

Moreover, there were concerns about how public funds are managed. While some participants believe that funding is available, they criticized its inefficient and ineffective allocation. Overall, participants called for more transparent and strategic use of available financial resources.

Other challenges mentioned are **sectoral and administrative silos** (N=5), **lack of expertise and knowledge** (N=4), and **path dependency** (N=4). Despite being mentioned to a lesser extent, these barriers are considered by participants to have a high impact on fire risk management and prevention in Ogliastra, as the lack of coordination and communication between sectors and local and regional entities limits their ability to work effectively. **Stakeholder conflicts** (N=3), are

related to tensions between environmentalist and conservationist views, and a perspective oriented towards active management. Participants described tensions with environmental groups and citizens who oppose interventions such as vegetation management, often perceiving them as harmful:

“If they see us treating combustible vegetation, they’re firmly convinced we’re causing serious environmental damage.”

These situations reflect a broader fragmentation among stakeholders. Another participant commented:

“There are administrations that need to plan, operators with practical constraints, and private citizens or businesses who each see things from their own disconnected perspective.”

Technological barriers (N=3), **maintenance** challenges (N=2) and other barriers (N=1) such as the population's short memory of past negative and extreme events affecting the area, were also mentioned.

Agro-livestock operators

Agro-livestock operators considered challenges linked to the **maintenance** (N=19) of forests to represent the most significant barriers. Aspects such as the overgrowth of shrubs, which makes paths inaccessible, and the fact that some private owners and breeders aren't clearing the forests, leads to high risks of wildfires. In their opinion, this is a problem closely interlinked with a lack of awareness. In tourist areas, these behaviours can be particularly dangerous. Moreover, in certain areas of the region, dense vegetation resulting from the lack of maintenance makes flock passage and grazing impossible. According to participants, forests are perceived to have low commercial value, making maintenance uneconomical, and regulatory restrictions further decrease profitability.

Another frequent barrier mentioned in the discussions were **stakeholder conflicts and equity issues** (N=17). Participants reported poor communication between private landowners and forest managers, something that has resulted in misunderstandings and lack of cooperation, leading to limited engagement from some landowners. Differences are said to be evident between environmental associations, government departments, and landowners, who often have contrasting views on the best or ideal management practices. These clashes seem to even extend to issues such as forest cleaning, land use, and environmental protection, highlighting a deeper conflict between conservationist approaches and active land management. In the case of livestock breeders and landowners, in particular, they expressed frustration at the lack of dialogue with decision-makers and stakeholders, feeling their perspectives were overlooked.

A perceived **lack of supportive policy and legal frameworks** (N=13) was also often discussed in the workshop with agro-livestock operators. The participants considered that the forestry department faces regulatory challenges that hinder effective fuel management and routine maintenance, something that contributes to the ongoing degradation of forests and makes the use of forest unprofitable. There was a shared concern about the absence of context-sensitive policies that align with local realities, as laws and regulations were often described as not aligned to the needs and practices existing in the area.

Societal challenges (N=7), **Lack and complexity of financing** (N=7), and **path dependency** (N=7), despite less mentioned, were also considered relevant obstacles. Echoing the sentiment of institutional actors, this second group of participants considered that depopulation in rural areas has not only led to economic decline, but also to the abandonment of land and environmental

degradation, increasing the risk of wildfires. A lack of investment planning and short-term perspectives are said to further exacerbate these issues, while high forest management costs and the absence of dedicated funding leave many communities without the means to take actions. Additionally, the decline of traditional practices among the population, like firewood use and land management, combined with unfair competition from cheaper imported products, has reduced interest in active forest management. This combination of factors contributes to a negative outlook and diminished local engagement in forest preservation efforts, and together, the prevention of wildfires.

Other barriers perceived were the **lack of expertise and knowledge** (N=3), particularly regarding the development of wildfires, **lack of political will and long-term commitment** (N=2), issues with **land ownership and availability** (N=2), **potential negative impacts** from poor management practices, **sectoral and administrative silos** (N=1).

Actors in the tourism sector

Focus group discussions with stakeholders in the tourism sector (e.g., hotel and camping owners) revealed a number of perceived barriers. Among them, the most relevant appeared to be the **lack of supportive policy and legal frameworks** (N=5). They expressed frustration with the absence of coordinated action plans and comprehensive policies, limiting preventive efforts with prescribed actions on their own properties. In their opinion, there is a clear need for broader strategies, such as bottom-up awareness campaigns, to complement existing control and monitoring initiatives. Financial mechanisms, like insurance policies, were considered inadequate to address the growing risks, as coverage often excludes frequent climate-related events like wildfires and floods. A participant states:

"Episodic events like wildfires are becoming increasingly frequent. If you read the fine print in insurance policies, you'll see that certain events, once considered rare, are now so common that they are no longer covered."

The other two most mentioned barriers were the **lack and complexity of financing** (N=3) and **lack of expertise and knowledge** (N=3). These stakeholders highlighted challenges with limited resources, complex insurance mechanisms, and difficulties in accessing compensation, even when coverage is in place. There is also a perceived need for increased awareness and expertise to address climate change and implement effective NbS, emphasizing the importance of grassroots campaigns to engage communities and address both immediate and long-term environmental risks.

Other barriers identified include low **maintenance** (N=2) and prevention actions in the region, **societal challenges** (N=1), particularly due to the demographic characteristics of the region (vast and sparsely populated), and **risk aversion** (N=1). Regarding his last barrier, the existence of perceived risks associated with pine forests was mentioned, as this type of trees is considered highly vulnerable to wildfire. Finally, participants reference once to the **lack of political will & long-term commitment**, particularly for the implementation of NbS.

Enablers

In all cases, workshops and focus group participants yielded less information on perceived enablers as compared to barriers, possibly because it is easier to express challenges or negative aspects. Below, figure 8 illustrates the coded results from the discussions with the three groups of participants. As it can be observed, the enhancement of **expertise and knowledge**, the implementation of **fire risk prevention** measures, as well as the existence of **supportive policies and legal frameworks**, were considered to be the most significant enabling conditions

to land management and fire risk prevention in Ogliastra. In the following sub-section, a brief description of the enablers highlighted by each group of participants is provided.

Figure 8: Frequency and classification of enablers to Nature based Solutions-compatible wildfire prevention and mitigation measures, based on data collected from workshops and focus group in Ogliastra.

Institutional actors

Institutional actors identified five main enablers to NbS-compatible wildfire prevention and mitigation measures. In this case, the most important enabler was considered to be **stakeholder engagement and equity** (N=3), as a number of initiatives and projects exist in the territory with the aim of improving the region and its resources. These include activities to promote risk awareness and actively involve citizens in prevention and self-protection. During the event, a project developed by the CFVA in collaboration with the administration of Tortoli was presented. Such a project aims to promote aspects related to self-protection (fire-wise communities), not to distract resources during extinguishing activities.

Other enablers cited and closely linked to stakeholder engagement efforts were **communication and awareness raising** activities (N=1), **forest fire prevention** actions (N=2), and the presence and leadership of certain **champions and advocates** (N=1). Regarding the latter, participants made reference to the importance of operators who keep using traditional fuels such as reeds to promote sustainable economic development projects for social and environmental benefit.

Agro-livestock operators

Contrary to institutional actors, who did not refer to **supportive policies and legal frameworks** as particularly relevant enablers to forest management of wildfire risk prevention, this aspect was mentioned three times by agro-livestock operators, making it the most cited enabler (N=3) during

their discussions. In their opinion, the existing limitations on grazing after a fire and restrictions on access and use of the land in such situations allow for the self-recovery of the forest, which at the same time attenuates further risks. In Ogliastro, restriction over the construction works in affected areas is also in place (as per Law n° 353/2000).

Other enabling aspects were said to be some **forest fire prevention** activities (N=2). In particular, the use of fires (e.g. prescribed burning) is often considered positive by landowners rather than destructive, given that it helps to “keep the land clean”. Likewise, they noted a certain level of **knowledge** (N=2) among herders regarding the dynamics and issues related to forest thanks to their long experience. In this case, it is this experience and knowledge which could help not only learn from their expertise, but also facilitate the later promotion of new measures aligned with their knowledge. Participants also mentioned the fact that companies having greater financial capacity (compared to small landowners), could have an enhanced ability to allocate economic resources to maintenance and cleaning activities. Moreover, there is a perceived strong willingness of many farmers and landowners to more actively manage their plots, as such management is considered convenient as it reduces exposure to risk .

Tourism sector

Participants in the focus group discussions with the tourism sector cited **expertise and knowledge** as the most significant enabler (N=5) to forest management and fire prevention in Ogliastro. In their opinion, there exists a growing sensitivity among stakeholders (particularly young generations) on the impacts of environmental challenges, ecosystem vulnerabilities, and risks such as wildfires and desertification in the communities and relevant sectors (e.g. tourism). Moreover, they observe that stakeholders show proactive measures, including structural adjustments to mitigate fire risks.

In addition, participants equally mentioned **forest fire prevention** (N=4) actions as enablers, highlighting how they themselves, as local stakeholders, have implemented measures to protect their structures and surrounding areas. These actions include periodic cleaning of land strips most exposed to fire risk, the installation of hydrants, and collaboration with landowners, demonstrating a shared commitment. However, participants also seemed aware of the limitations of these measures, which, while useful, are confined to the local level and fail to address the issue on a broader scale.

Proposed strategies

Discussions during local workshops, both with institutional actors and agro-livestock operators, also touched on potential strategies in support of land and forest management and fire prevention in the Ogliastro sub-region. Figure 9 summarizes the main category of strategies identified by each participant group.

Institutional actors identified a significant number of strategies. Among the most mentioned are the **promotion of forest fire prevention and sustainable forest practices** (N=15). In their opinion, this includes the revitalization of rural areas and promoting local vitality by rediscovering the region’s agrarian identity and valuing traditional forest practices. Moreover, cleaning the forest and prioritizing biomass use are key strategies to manage fuel and reduce fire risks, especially given the challenging climate and terrain factors that characterize the region. In particular, efforts to extend wildfire prevention measures into high-risk areas and during critical periods are recommended. Likewise, active forest management was also cited, putting an emphasis on preventing land abandonment and improving planning to reduce excess fuel. Furthermore, promoting the use of controlled fire in high-risk areas is proposed to clear dense vegetation and mitigate wildfire risks. Finally, in this regard, the participants indicated that it is important to

increase human resources for the forest by hiring and collaborating with entities and cooperatives, as well as finding legislative solutions that allow access to land in diverse areas.

Figure 9: Strategies proposed by stakeholder participants during the local DRR workshops and focus groups in Ogliastra, identified as potential Nature-based Solutions for wildfire prevention and mitigation in the region.

Equally important, despite it being mentioned to a lesser extent, was **fostering public participation and local economy** (N=7). Institutional actors called for the promotion of local bioeconomy initiatives, fostering community involvement, and encouraging proactive measures to reduce wildfire consequences through a closer collaboration between forestry operators and municipal administrators. Moreover, and closely linked to these actions, it was suggested to **increase the knowledge and awareness** of the population (N=6) by raising awareness through educational campaigns and improving knowledge of fire use. Importantly, participants considered the involvement of citizens in the implementation of plans for sustainable development as key, as well as raising their awareness and knowledge on the criteria, methods and necessary conditions for the use and application of prescribed fires. Lastly, **increasing communication and dialogue among stakeholders** (N=1), including legislators, is seen as essential for fostering cooperation and effective decision-making.

Agro-livestock operators also pointed to the **promotion of forest fire prevention and sustainable forest management practices** in the first place (N=8). This includes reducing biomass through mechanical treatments and ensuring forests are actively managed to prevent wildfires. A holistic approach to land management, integrating grazing, livestock, and timber production, was also suggested, alongside the concept of "mosaicking" to create diversity. In their opinion, prescribed grazing is no longer sufficient in the region and should be combined with silviculture. Additionally, they called for reviving traditional land and forest management practices and ensuring the

protection of wildlife and biodiversity. The importance of **communication and dialogue with stakeholders** (N=3), including legislators, was cited along with the need for higher **public participation** (N=3), research investment, and collaborative interpretation of regulations. Finally, other of their proposals included promoting local bioeconomy initiatives, introducing payment for ecosystem services.

The strategies mentioned by tourism operators to address wildfire risk are mostly limited to regulatory requirements and management of areas under their direct responsibility. The measures mentioned include preventive actions such as “clearing dry grass in nearby areas” or “the annual cleaning of a strip of land near the facility,” as well as equipment upgrade and the presence of fire hydrants and emergency exits. However, these efforts are not perceived as sufficient:

“I wouldn’t say we’ve done much. We stick to what concerns our area.”

Rather than large-scale structural interventions, the group emphasized the importance of raising awareness and building collective consciousness, described as a key driver for promoting virtuous behaviours and widespread prevention: “awareness campaigns from the bottom up are essential.” In this regard, the idea of introducing innovative tools, such as a collective insurance policy linked to the adoption of preventive practices in the area, was received with interest. A participant said:

“Exactly. It’s like with cars: to be insured, the car needs to have passed its inspection. Similarly, with a wildfire insurance policy, you should be able to prove that you’ve done everything necessary to prevent the risk, such as keeping the forest safe. It’s an idea that should be implemented immediately.”

Although such a tool is not yet available in Italy, it was considered potentially helpful in encouraging shared and coordinated prevention strategies. However, as another participant pointed out:

“The aggregation of a broader community could provide greater strength, but the problem remains: how much would such coverage cost? And what real benefits would it bring?”

8.3.5 Summary and key messages

In the Ogliastra DEM8, participants’ perceptions of wildfire risks and dynamics, direct experiences with fires and prevention measures, key enablers and barriers related to a portfolio of measures for the implementation of land management and fire prevention strategies, and potential strategies and interventions for land management and wildfire prevention, which we have referred to as NbS-compatible wildfire prevention and mitigation measures, were investigated through two local workshops and a focus group. Below we summarize the main key points that arose:

Shared awareness and concern. Both institutional actors and agro-livestock operators recognize wildfires as a serious and growing problem, with increasing concern over their frequency, intensity, and seasonal extension. Both groups anticipate an increase in wildfire frequency and intensity, attributing climate change as a major driver. However, their perceptions differ in terms of specific impacts and priorities. Institutional actors tend to emphasize the environmental, infrastructural, and cultural consequences of wildfires, while agro-livestock operators are more focused on the impact on property and daily operations and place less importance on ecosystem or heritage damage.

Barriers and enablers. The analysis of perceptions on key enablers and barriers to land management and fire prevention strategies, strengths and drivers, and proposed strategies highlight different key themes for the success of NbS-related approaches (such as fire-smart management). The

main concern of institutional actors revolves around "Management and Regulation" issues, indicating a strong emphasis on current policies potentially perceived as overly restrictive. Agro-livestock operators, on the other hand, highlight local economic challenges and resource management as primary barriers, suggesting the need for targeted interventions to strengthen the local economy and optimize resource management.

Despite these differences, there is broad agreement on the importance of wildfire prevention and sustainable forest management as shared priorities. Both groups also recognize the value of public involvement, knowledge sharing, and local economic development in shaping more effective forest governance.

Agreed strategies and priorities. Discussions highlighted the need for active and integrated management of the territory and forests as an effective preventive measure against fires, emphasizing the challenges posed by stringent regulations and fees. A common goal appears to emerge, that is, to achieve a balance between the local economy, social well-being, and sustainable environmental management of the forestry sector, including balancing with other sectors. Nevertheless, the necessity for active forest management that supports local economic development and the multifunctionality of forests, mending the distance between humans and nature, which is essential in preventing mega-fires that are perceived as no longer controllable in a territory lacking presence and infrastructure, emerges. Overall, the two groups agreed on further promotion of NbS-compatible actions, such as silviculture, in combination with the existing prescribed grazing efforts taken by farmers, reviving traditional forest and land management practices, and adopting an integrated land management approach (grazing, livestock, timber, mosaicking) that combines land use with ecological health.

Conflicts and misunderstandings. The analysis also reveals a gap in discourses and perspectives: agro-livestock operators use terminology rooted in land use and rural practice, reflecting a direct connection with the natural environment. Institutional actors, on the other hand, employ a vocabulary more aligned with strategic planning and emergency response, emphasizing long-term risk reduction. This contrast reflects the broader distinction between practical, experience-based knowledge and a more policy-driven approach.

In addition, tensions between the groups emerged, particularly regarding the role of forestry agencies, which are often seen by farmers as imposing constraints on land use. Addressing these conflicts through inclusive dialogue and social learning is essential to building mutual understanding and finding collaborative solutions. Rather than trying to eliminate disagreements, the challenge lies in using them as opportunities for deeper insight and joint problem-solving. Given deeply rooted contradictions in perspectives, worldviews and interests, robust policies that gain wide support are typically built on compromise, not consensus (Linnerooth-Bayer et al., 2016; Scolobig & Lilliestam, 2016).

Final reflections on stakeholder engagement and perceptions. The stakeholder engagement process revealed both the complexity and the potential of participatory approaches to DRR, especially in multi-risk contexts such as those affected by wildfires, climate change, and socio-economic transformations. Participants, including institutional actors, agro-livestock operators, and civil society representatives, brought diverse, and sometimes conflicting, perspectives to the table. One of the workshops' most significant contributions was its effort to build trust and cornerstone towards the co-definition of effective adaptation and fire risk mitigation pathways with a wide range of stakeholders. This participatory approach recognized the value of not only technical and scientific expertise, but also local and experiential knowledge—particularly that of those who live and work closest to the land and are directly affected by both natural hazards and the policies designed to manage them. As proposed by Bacciu et al., (2025) and Casartelli & Mysiak, (2023), it is of utmost policy importance to encourage active community engagement and collaboration between different stakeholders, including local communities, landowners, public authorities and

researchers, to develop shared approaches and innovative solutions. By actively engaging local stakeholders, the process aimed to integrate their needs, capacities, and priorities into the broader risk governance framework. This included acknowledging economic constraints, institutional distrust, and cultural dimensions of land use and fire management. In doing so, the workshops helped activate latent local resources, such as informal networks, traditional practices, and community-based knowledge that are often overlooked in top-down planning.

8.4 Canton Bern, Switzerland

This section presents the Bern case study, which investigates the enablers and barriers of protection forests as NbS for mitigating gravitational natural hazards such as landslides, rockfalls and avalanches. In addition to examining the factors that support or hinder the effectiveness and resilience of protection forests, the case also explores stakeholder perspectives on the development and implementation of the PROTECTpraxis guidelines—a new methodological tool designed to enable the systematic evaluation of both biological and technical risk reduction measures. The analysis also explores how protection forests and the guidelines can support multi-risk DRR.

We first provide an overview of the regional context and natural hazard landscape, with a focus on the role of protection forests in alpine risk reduction. This is followed by a description of the governance setting, outlining key actors, institutional responsibilities, and policies addressing protection forests. Next, we describe the specific methods applied in the Bern case. The following results and discussion section examines the key enablers and barriers across three thematic areas: 1) NbS as multi-risk DRR strategies; 2) the maintenance, conservation and restoration of protection forests and 3) the development and anticipated implementation of the PROTECTpraxis guidelines. The section concludes with reflections on key messages and implications for future planning and decision-making.

8.4.1 Background/Case study overview

Switzerland is divided into 26 cantons which enjoy a relatively high degree of political independence. Bern is the second-largest canton of Switzerland, both in terms of population (approx. 1 million inhabitants) and size (5,958 km²). It encompasses a diverse range of landscapes, from high altitude mountains (up to 4,274 m asl.) to a section of the sub-alpine Jura mountains (up to 1608 m asl.) and the mostly hilly Swiss Plateau, which lies at around 400 masl. A large share of the Aare river's catchment area, including its headwaters, falls into the canton's boundaries. One third of the canton is forested.

In its Alpine areas, rivers generally have steep gradients. For example, Zulg river, which was studied in a previous The HuT work package, descends from 1000 masl. to 550 masl. over just 15 kilometers. The valleys in these areas are often characterized by steep slopes, cliffs and loose rock, which constitute risk factors for adjacent settlements and infrastructure. The region is affected by climate change through glacier and permafrost retreat, changing water availability, weather events such as sudden weather changes, heavy snowfall, hailstorms, extreme rainfall events (e.g. BAFU, 2020) and combined effects like rain-on-snow events (Fehlmann et al., 2019).

As a result, the canton faces multiple hazards, including gravitational and meteorological hazards like landslides, debris flows, rockfalls, snow avalanches, (flash) floods and storms as well as wildfires and, more rarely, earthquakes. Hazards related to climate change have already increased in frequency and intensity — a trend that is expected to continue in the future (AWN, 2023; BAFU, 2020).

A third of the canton is covered with forest. Over the past decades, the share of broad-leaved trees has increased, bringing the forests closer to a natural state, and the forest cover has slightly increased, mainly at higher altitudes. However, ungulate (in particular deer) populations have also increased and threaten the rejuvenation of forests and the diversity of tree species. Their influence puts more than a third of the forest area in Bern in either unsustainable or critical condition (AWN, 2023).

8.4.2 NbS policy and governance

Definition of NbS in the local context

The natural hazards present in Bern are addressed through a combination of grey infrastructure (“Technische Massnahmen”), biological measures (“Biologische Massnahmen”), and organizational measures. Grey infrastructure includes structures such as check dams and avalanche barriers, while biological measures primarily involve protection forests, yet include any type of greening (including planting shrubs, or any other plants, sometimes also referred to as “biological engineering measures”). While by definition they can also include land use change, revegetation with other plants and renaturation of river courses, these measures are less prevalent in the canton Bern.

In Switzerland, protection forests are defined as forests that provide protection to settlements and infrastructure against one or more of the following natural hazards: snow avalanches, rockfalls (including icefalls), landslides and movement of water and sediments in watercourses (Losey & Wehrli, 2013). In Switzerland, this definition applies to 44% of all forests and in the canton Bern, 51% of the forests are protection forests. Around 20,000 residential buildings and 2,700 kilometres of road benefit from forests protecting them (AWN, 2023). Unlike grey infrastructure, which is typically designed to mitigate a specific hazard at a specific location, most protection forests were not intended to protect against a specific hazard. Instead, they are designated as protection forests when their protective function is recognized. Tree species present in protection forests often derive from their original function. For this reason, spruces are overrepresented in many protection forests that also served as commercial purposes in the past. Not all protection forest areas are actively managed. In fact, over the last decade, 17% of all protection forests were actively managed to maintain the protective function and another 7% required emergency interventions (e.g. to stop bark beetle outbreaks). Areas that were not actively managed either provided sufficient protection without human intervention or lacked accessibility. The protection forest area that required emergency interventions increased by 60% in the last decade (BAFU and WSL, 2025).

Protection forests protect large areas against hazards, often multiple hazards. Indeed, 30% of all protection forests in Switzerland protect against multiple of the four defined natural hazards (BAFU and WSL, 2025). Once designated as protection forests, the primary goal of forest management becomes the conservation, maintenance and restoration of the forests' protective functions and specific rules and management guides apply. Key measures for protection forest management include cutting of old trees to support rejuvenation, targeted planting, both for rejuvenation and to support climate change adapted species, and protection of young trees against game browsing damage.

We consider protection forests to be a NbS as the sustainable management of ecosystems addresses societal challenges (here: DRR), while providing additional ecosystem services such as biodiversity benefits. While the primary management goal is to maintain the protective function of the forests, potentially taking precedence over biodiversity concerns, ecological standards are defined and considered in protection forest management. Biodiversity objectives and protection forest management often go hand in hand (e.g. Scherrer et al., 2023; Stritih et al., 2021), however,

there are some instances in which trade-offs need to be managed (BAFU, 2024c; Blatter et al., 2017). For example, pioneer and decay stages in natural forest cycles do not provide optimal protection and require human interventions (BAFU, 2024c), also, protection forests are typically managed to maintain a dense structure with few open areas, which can reduce habitat availability for species adapted to such conditions, e.g. certain butterfly species. Yet, achieving the same protective functions through grey infrastructure would likely cause larger environmental impacts.

Overall NbS policies in Switzerland

NbS (-related) concepts are integrated in several sectoral policies in Switzerland, though under different terms. The term NbS is explicitly mentioned only in the recently revised Biodiversity Action Plan (BAFU, 2024a) which is aligned with the Global Biodiversity Framework. It includes NbS as one of 15 action categories and compiles NbS best practices, along with a list of pilot projects for climate mitigation and adaptation. Specifically mentioned NbS are green spaces, near-natural water regimes, green roofs and alternative uses of peatlands and organic soils. While protection forests are not referenced in the Biodiversity Action Plan, they are subject to an established governance structure across national (federal), regional (cantonal) level and local (municipal and community) levels.

At the federal level, the Swiss Federal Office for the Environment (BAFU) is the primary authority responsible for forests and natural hazards. It coordinates expert bodies on both subjects, such as the Steering Committee on Intervention in Natural Hazards (LAINAT) in which the BAFU closely collaborates with the Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology, the Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP) and other relevant government institutions (BAFU, 2024b), as well as the expert commission National Platform for Natural Hazards (PLANAT) in which research, professional associations, private businesses and insurers are represented (PLANAT, 2024). Furthermore, the BAFU is supported by sectoral advisory bodies such as the Swiss Mountain Forest Management Group (Gebirgswaldpflegegruppe, GWG), which brings together practitioners and scientists (GWG, 2016), the Conference of Cantonal Foresters (KOK) and the Expert Group for Natural Hazards (Fachleute Naturgefahren, FAN) in which private businesses, cantonal and federal government agencies and science collaborate (FAN, 2025). The Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research (WSL) provides science-based solutions for forests, landscapes, biodiversity and natural hazards (WSL, 2025). It regularly collaborates with BAFU and other political actors.

At the cantonal level, forest and natural hazards are bundled jointly in the same agency (Amt für Wald und Naturgefahren). Other agencies dealing with relevant policy fields focus on environment and energy (responsibilities include e.g. climate protection) as well as agriculture and nature (responsibilities include hunting and biodiversity). All agencies are part of the same cantonal Department for Economics, Energy and Environment (WEU, 2024).

At the municipal level, forest engineers and forest rangers are tasked with the implementation of forest management work. They are provided with federal (e.g. NAIS, see below) and cantonal guidelines (WEU, 2025), some of which are binding while others are voluntary.

Swiss Forest Law

Federal forest laws have existed in Switzerland since 1876, when the first law was enacted to maintain and enhance the protective functions of the forest (Lange et al., 2019). It followed devastating floods, in particular in 1868, which had affected large parts of the country and for which forest loss had been identified as a contributing factor. The forest law has since undergone several major revisions, however, still today both the Federal Constitution (BV, Art. 77, SR 101) and the current Swiss Forest Act (WaG) oblige the federal government to ensure that the forests

are able to fulfil their protective, commercial and public amenity functions. Beyond that, the WaG states additional objectives of conserving the forest in its spatial distribution, protecting the forest as a close-to-nature community and promoting and maintaining the forestry sector (WaG, Art. 1, SR 921.0). While the initial law focused on preserving the forest cover by banning deforestation, later versions introduced financial incentives to encourage afforestation to ensure better protection against avalanches and rock fall as well as management requirements. Yet, it should be noted that cantons have a high degree of freedom in implementing the federal forest law (Brang et al., 2014). Over time, some cantons and other actors used broader definitions of protection forests that included forests contributing to nature conservation, water purification, air quality, recreation, public health or landscape. Additionally, the 2020 Swiss Forest Policy (BAFU, 2020) explicitly states that biodiversity in forests needs to be conserved and improved in a targeted way. Yet, the implementation of the policy's strategic goals remains largely at the discretion of cantonal and local forest services.

As soon as a forest (or forest section) is categorized as fulfilling a protective function, it is classified as protection forest and subject to federal forest protection, which cantonal authorities must adhere to. Accordingly, the share of protection forests is highest in mountainous cantons where gravitational hazards are more prevalent (e.g. Valais, 82.162 ha protection forest, 87% of the canton's forests) and lower in flatland cantons (Losey & Wehrli, 2013). Bern has 88.890 ha of protection forest that account for 50% of the canton's forests. On average, 44% of Switzerland's total forest area is categorized as protection forest (BAFU and WSL, 2025).

To support the maintenance of protection forests and any necessary infrastructure, the Swiss federal government compensates the cantons (WaG, Art. 37). However, the WaG only provides a broad definition of protection forests and initially clear standards were missing. At that time, cantons interpreted and handled the definition, and accordingly the demarcation and management, of protection forests differently. This caused, among other issues, challenges for the allocation of federal subsidies for protection forest management. In 2013, the definition was standardized for all cantons through the project SilvaProtect-CH.

SilvaProtect-CH

The project SilvaProtect-CH aimed to standardize the designation and management of protection forests across cantons (Losey and Wehrli, 2013). One of the principal aims was to develop a standardized basis for the allocation of federal subsidies for protection forests.

Over the course of several years (2004-2013), the BAFU and cantonal forest agencies developed a definition of protection forests: "A protection forest is a forest that can safeguard against a recognized potential hazard from an existing natural danger or reduce the associated risks". The main hazards that were considered are snow avalanches, rockfall, landslides and movement of water and sediments in watercourses. Along with the definition, SilvaProtect-CH also developed a methodology to assess the extent of protection forests and the possible damages in a harmonized and standardized way. Based on the results of SilvaProtect-CH, the cantons reevaluated their protection forests. Overall, the new definition led to 18% less forest area being classified as 'protection forest' (Losey & Wehrli, 2013).

Nachhaltigkeit und Erfolgskontrolle im Schutzwald (NaiS) (Sustainability and performance monitoring in protection forests)

Nachhaltigkeit und Erfolgskontrolle im Schutzwald (NaiS) are guidelines or "enforcement aids" that aim to guide practitioners in the management of protection forests in line with the WaG. The NaiS guidelines were first published in 2005 (Frehner et al., 2005) and updated in 2024 (BAFU, 2024c). NaiS draws on the realization that the protective function of the forest highly depends on the state

of the forest. It therefore details management practices while taking both the local conditions and the present hazards into account. Additionally, NaiS provides specific criteria for managing, conserving, and restoring protection forests, e.g., regarding intended rejuvenation rates, trade-offs with economic uses and biodiversity protection, adaptation to climate change and monitoring practices. NaiS remains the principal legal instrument and incentive for conserving protection forests in Switzerland. While it is not directly legally binding, forest managers receive funding for adhering to NaiS and maintaining protective forests using its criteria (Angst, 2012).

NaiS follows seven principles: Management of protection forests should (1) aim primarily at minimizing gravitational risks, (2) target areas where the forest can effectively reduce risks to humans and assets and be implemented at the time when they are most effective, (3) be implemented in accordance with natural processes, (4) be implemented under consideration of expected climatic changes, (5) be implemented by local experts and transparently documented, (6) effective, and (7) have a reasonable cost-benefit ratio.

While NaiS' primary goal is to ensure the protective function of forests against natural hazards, they address biodiversity in a number of ways. While its principle 3 relates to keeping forests as close to their natural state as possible ('close-to-nature'), they also encourage actions such as:

- Deadwood retention;
- Having mixed tree species;
- Conserving habitat trees (individual trees with cavities, old bark, or special features that provide shelters for biodiversity);
- Avoiding management during bird nesting periods; and
- Supporting diverse, near-natural forest structures.

All of these are compatible with forests' protective function. NaiS also includes indicators and checklists for assessing forest condition and function, which include stand structure, species composition, and natural regeneration, which serve as proxies for ecological quality. Some cantons, such as canton Bern, also complement NaiS with their own biodiversity guidance.

Finally, principle 4 of the guidelines is critical as it recognises the importance of biodiversity for forest resilience, i.e. less risks of pests, less damage in case of an extreme event like droughts.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that as biodiversity is not the primary objective of NaiS, if ecological goals conflict with protective function, which is rare but possible (e.g., open areas preferred by light-demanding species vs. dense forests for avalanche protection), hazard protection takes precedence. While NaiS acknowledge these trade-offs, they explicitly state that "Die Schutzwirkung hat Vorrang vor anderen Zielen wie der Förderung der Biodiversität oder der Holznutzung" (*the protective effect takes precedence over other objectives such as the promotion of biodiversity or timber use*). This means that certain trade-offs, such as leaving deadwood where it does not interfere with slope stability, are considered acceptable. Others, such as leaving deadwood in places where it would compromise slope stability, would not be recommended. Generally, NaiS uses a site-specific approach where biodiversity-enhancing actions are recommended in parts of the forest where the hazard intensity is lower. It is also important to highlight that NaiS focuses on gravity-driven hazards only, meaning that when certain measures can increase risks of other hazards (in this case, deadwood can increase wildfire risk), this is not addressed. Neither does NaiS prescribe silvicultural strategies for fire prevention, apart from the above-mentioned measures promoting forest resilience. Additionally, NaiS recommendations for biodiversity are generally non-binding, unless tied to cantonal policies.

PROTECT, Protect Bio, PROTECTpraxis

'PROTECT' was a project led by PLANAT to develop a methodology to assess the effectiveness of protective measures against gravitational natural hazards. A principal aim was to standardize the consideration of protective measures (mainly grey infrastructure) in the development of hazard maps. The methodology defines nine principles that are prerequisite for considering protective measures in hazard maps: (1) Quantifiable effects, (2) limited uncertainties, (3) applicable to different scenarios, (4) can be considered as a singular system and as part of the entire system (5) is permanently available, (6) can be monitored, (7) not dependent on temporary measures, (8) implemented according to plans, and (9) long-term changes of protective measures and hazard processes are considered. If these principles are met, PROTECTpraxis follows a standardized evaluation process, covering four steps from rapid assessment of expected protection outcomes, evaluation of feasibility of measures, quantification of protection outcomes and finally recommendations for spatial planning (Romang, 2008). Despite the traditional and widespread relevance of protection forests, the first guidelines were inspired by grey infrastructure and not directly applicable to biological measures (Wasser & Perren, 2014).

This shortcoming was addressed in a second project phase, 'ProtectBio', which aimed to extend and adapt the PROTECT methodology to biological measures and include the protective function of forests in hazard and risk assessments. It was clarified that protection forests indeed meet the nine principles defined in PROTECT (see above) and can therefore be acknowledged as protective measures (Wasser & Perren, 2014). In this process, several peculiarities of biological systems that distinguish them from built infrastructures were explicitly considered, e.g. that the provision of protection services is only one of many forest functions, that they can be influenced through interventions but not entirely designed, that they depend on natural cycles and that forests and hazard processes interact with each other (Sandri et al., 2016). ProtectBio integrated, for example, steps to evaluate the protective function of forests based on criteria defined in the NaiS guidelines and allowed the consideration of possible damages to forests (storms, bark beetle outbreaks, wildfires) that could reduce their protective function, possible replacement efforts, and general maintenance needs. In contrast to NaiS, ProtectBio allowed spatial prioritization, an integrated assessment of biological measures with other measures, and an understanding of the potential impacts of insufficient maintenance (Wasser and Perren, 2014). ProtectBio was then tested in several case studies (Scherer et al., 2019; Schwarz et al., 2019; Tegethoff & Steffen, 2021). In these case studies, ProtectBio helped to quantify the direct economic benefits of protection forests (i.e. preventing damages) and identify management needs in the concerned forests (e.g. need to increase the number of trees with small trunk diameter to decrease gaps between trees and ensure rejuvenation).

The latest amendment of the Protect methodology, called PROTECTpraxis, will be finalised in 2025. PROTECTpraxis, as its name suggests, aimed to improve the usability of the existing tool (this being focused on the 'practical' aspect), e.g. by providing practical examples. While ProtectBio mainly focused on developing and testing guidelines in solitary case studies, PROTECTpraxis will allow the assessment of biological measures by default and at the same level as grey infrastructure and organizational measures. Currently the final steps of the integrated methodology PROTECTpraxis are ongoing, which will result in the publication later in 2025.

In terms of biodiversity considerations, as PROTECTpraxis largely builds on NaiS for the biological measure module of the guidelines, both frameworks are very much aligned. For example, biodiversity-related indicators (e.g., species diversity, canopy cover, stand structure, natural regeneration) are part of the "Zuverlässigkeit" (reliability) assessment of the guidelines. As with NaiS, the guidelines introduce resilience as a key concept tied to biodiversity. However, here as well, forests are primarily assessed for their protective function and biodiversity is not the primary criterion, even though PROTECTpraxis explicitly encourages multifunctionality.

However, the guideline's primary goal differs in that PROTECTpraxis aims to compare the value of different risk reduction options (biological measures / protection forests included, yet representing only one of 3 types of measures).

To summarise, table 5 compares both guidelines in terms of their key features.

Table 5: Key features and comparison of NaiS and PROTECTpraxis guidelines.

	NaiS (Nachhaltigkeit und Erfolgskontrolle im Schutzwald)	PROTECTpraxis
Primary purpose	Guide management and monitoring of protection forests	Assess and compare the effectiveness of protective measures (biological, grey, organizational)
Treatment of biodiversity	Treated as a secondary but valuable goal, supportive of resilience and regeneration	Treated as a functional factor influencing forest reliability and resilience
Resilience integration	Encouraged via structural diversity, natural regeneration, mixed species	Explicitly defined; linked to the ability to recover from disturbance and withstand climate change
Key biodiversity evaluation criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Canopy cover - Natural regeneration - Habitat structures (deadwood, habitat trees) - Stand structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spider-Diagrams using NaiS-based parameters - TreeApp (climate suitability) - Resilience (post-disturbance performance) - Multifunctionality where applicable
Biodiversity trade-offs	Protection function prevails; biodiversity-enhancing measures applied only if compatible	Same principle: protective function has priority, but multifunctionality is evaluated more broadly
Climate change consideration	Mentioned in Principle 4; encourages climate-adapted species and stand structures	Explicitly integrated: considers species viability, forest regeneration, hazard exposure over time
How biodiversity influences guideline outputs	Biodiversity influences management actions (e.g. thinning, planting)	Biodiversity affects measure reliability scoring, which informs hazard zoning and planning decisions
Typical users	Foresters, cantonal forest services	Multidisciplinary teams: hazard experts, foresters, planners, engineers

Cantonal policies and institutions

In Bern, the federal forest law is complemented by the cantonal forest law (KwaG, BSG 921.11). It specifies that while the canton is responsible for identifying and monitoring natural hazards and considering them in spatial planning, municipalities and infrastructure owners are responsible for the protection of their areas and properties, i.e., for protection forest management (KWaG, Art. 28-31). In practical terms, this means that municipalities arrange financing and procurement of forest management services, e.g. from private forest owners, rangers or forest service providers (AWN, 2023).

The canton supports the implementation through the cantonal Agency for Forest and Natural Hazards (AWN) who advises municipalities and private forest owners, provides guidelines and distributes subsidies. AWN has developed a 2030 Protection Forest Strategy (AWN, 2023) which includes multiple measures for ensuring the maintenance of their protective functions. AWN also published a biodiversity guideline for forest managers which gives clear (but not legally binding) advice on how biodiversity can be considered in forestry. It gives specific examples how biodiversity and protection targets can go hand in hand (AWN, 2024). Recommendations join those included in NaiS and include: supporting diverse forests that are in a near natural state to increase forest resilience, supporting natural pioneer species for structural improvements and regrowth after damages, considering bird nesting/habitats when conducting forest management in nesting periods, leaving a certain amount of dead wood in the forest to support rejuvenation or leaving a limited number of old “habitat trees” in the forest.

8.4.3 Research design

In the Bern case site, key governance barriers and enablers of protection forests and the PROTECTpraxis guidelines were identified through targeted, semi-structured interviews with key informants (Karatsareas, 2022). PROTECTpraxis is a methodology that enables practitioners (such as engineers, foresters, and planners) to systematically and comparably evaluate biological and technical protection measures for natural hazards. PROTECTpraxis has three key modules for three types of measures: biological, structural and organisational. The biological measure module is largely based on the NaiS guidelines.

As noted in Section 8.1, the governance enablers and barriers extracted regarding protection forests mainly refer to their conservation, maintenance and restoration. Since protection forests have existed in canton Bern and Switzerland for several centuries and therefore already exist on nearly all land surfaces where they could have been added, large-scale afforestation is not currently on policy agendas; however, there are issues concerning their long-term survival, especially in light of a changing climate and related emerging threats. Enablers and barriers of the PROTECTpraxis guideline (which will only come into force in the second half of 2025) may refer to different phases of the implementation process up until their application (their design, planning, application). Figure 10 summarises the NbS implementation phases and describes to which phase the Bern enabler and barrier analyses (of both PROTECTpraxis and protection forests) are most relevant for.

NbS implementation stages and relevance for Bern case

Figure 10: Nature based Solutions implementation stages and to which stage the Bern enabler and barrier analysis is most relevant.

Thus, there is an important temporal aspect to our enabler/barrier results which needs to be taken into account. Identifying enablers and barriers for each individual phase of the implementation process (including the design, planning, construction/planting, monitoring and maintenance of both PROTECTpraxis and protection forests) would however require a larger dataset to be analysed in-depth. It should also be noted that the identification of ‘governance’ enablers and barriers was sometimes extended to include environmental and technical factors when these were deemed important (or mentioned frequently) by interviewees.

Interviewees were identified through expert consultation and snowball sampling (Parker et al., 2019). Interviews were performed between February and December 2024 with a total of 14 stakeholders from a variety of sectors and bodies (table 6). The interview protocol is provided in Appendix E. Interview questions were occasionally adapted to fit the interviewees knowledge and background using an iterative process (Kekeya, 2016). All interviews were fully anonymised, with interviewees being assigned a number to preserve their anonymity (B1-B14).

Table 6: List and details of interviewees - Bern.

Number of interviewees (N)	Sector or affiliation
6	Academia and research
3	Local authority (cantonal or regional)
4	Private sector
1	Education / professional training institutes

As mentioned in section 8.1, interview transcripts were analysed using a quantitative content analysis (Vaismoradi et al., 2016) to assign codes to ideas that emerged from the transcribed text. Codes were classified according to pre-defined clusters (see table 2) as well as sub-categories where necessary. Unless different aspects of a given enabler or barrier within a cluster were mentioned, double counting of codes was avoided (i.e., if an interviewee mentioned the same enabler/barrier several times throughout the interview, this was only counted once).

The Bern case had a dual research focus: i) the governance of protection forests in Canton Bern and beyond and ii) the aforementioned Swiss PROTECTpraxis guidelines. The focus on protection forests was decided on due to Switzerland’s pioneering role in legally protecting forests and recognising their protective role through the 1876 federal forest act (Angst, 2012). The PROTECTpraxis guidelines were selected as the other case’s focus due to their potential significance for biological measures (including protection forests) in Switzerland, as well as their novelty as they are due to be implemented in 2025.

The principal research questions the interviews aimed to answer hence consisted of:

- What are the key governance enablers of and barriers to the conservation, maintenance and restoration of protection forests for DRR in canton Bern (and beyond)?
- What are the key governance enablers of and barriers to the design, planning, application of the PROTECTpraxis guidelines?
- What are their governance enablers and barriers?
- What are the implications of these enablers and barriers for multi-risk DRR?

This means that in addition to codes being classified according to the predefined clusters, they were also classified according to their relevance to either 1) multi-risk DRR, 2) protection forest conservation, maintenance and restoration, and 3) the design, planning and application of the PROTECTpraxis guidelines. In what follows, key results from the analysis are highlighted for each of these aspects.

8.4.4 Results and discussion

Enablers and barriers of protection forests and PROTECTpraxis guidelines for multi-risk DRR

In this section, we explore enablers and barriers as well as other key observations from interviews which related to protection forests and the PROTECTpraxis guidelines for multi-risk DRR, including cascading effects. Table 7 depicts all barriers and enablers that emerged in this regard. Due to the small sample size, only key highlights are discussed in this section.

Table 7: Frequency of multi-risk DRR enablers and barriers, classified by clusters, identified from interviews in Bern.

Enabler cluster	Number of mentions in interviews
Evidence on performance and co-benefits	8
Biodiversity and climate change	4
Supportive policies and legal frameworks	4
Funding / financial tools and support or cost-effectiveness	2
Risk reduction	2
Disaster	1
Flexibility and adaptiveness	1
Polycentric and cross-sectoral arrangements	1
Stakeholder engagement & equity	1
Barrier cluster	Number of mentions in interviews
Risk and risk aversion	7
Biodiversity loss and climate threats	3
Lack of expertise and knowledge	2
Other	2
Lack of evidence on performance and co-benefits	1
Lack of and complexity of financing	1

As described in section 7, it is important to first distinguish between multi-risk and cascading risks, where the former represents multiple hazards that happen simultaneously or in succession,

whereas the latter represent a succession of events that are mutually reinforcing. Yet, different interpretations of multi-risk and cascading risk also became apparent in interviews. For example, some interviewees considered cascading events to be large-scale, freak events. Others saw multi-risk events as the same, whereas some considered that any risk in mountain areas is a potential multi-risk as hardly any event happens in isolation (e.g., heavy rainfall triggers landslide which also triggers rockfalls). This highlights that the definitions of multi-risk and cascading-risk definitions are not clear, even within the expert community.

Barriers

In terms of barriers, actual **risk and risk aversion** were most frequently mentioned. Interviewees highlighted the difficulty in forecasting and preparing for multi-risk events, thus limiting proactive planning and long-term investment strategies for these types of events. As noted by interviewee B3:

When you look at these [cascading] events, what would you do? What could you do about it? You can't really do anything, or you could, but it would cost so much in terms of area that it would be impossible.

Interviewees also highlighted the limits of biological measures (including protection forests) in mitigating the risk of a cascading event, and how this might differ in case of multi-risks that are not cascading:

For the cascading effects, if we're talking about bigger events, then I don't see any possibility for biological measures. If we talk about multi-risks, this means that different hazards can occur independently of each other in the same area. If I have a slope, there can be landslides, but rockfalls can also occur or rock slides. For me, this is the classic case where protective forests can often have a very good effect and there is great potential for them. (Interviewee B2)

Related to this is the fact that protective functions of forests are often invisible until a system failure occurs (Interviewee B12). This can result in underfunding or delayed implementation of measures.

Here as well, **biodiversity loss and climate threats** emerged as an important concern. Indeed, interviewees cited the many uncertainties concerning future climatic shifts, frequencies of extreme events and how this will impact protection forests and biodiversity as a whole. The many interdependencies (and thus multi-risks) between climate and biodiversity risks also arose as a potential challenge for the future. While generally, most interviewees agreed that protection forests can serve biodiversity goals all the while providing protection functions, interviewee B9 did give an example of a case where the type of forest needed for specific taxonomic groups, in this case, butterflies which require light and non-dense/open forests, stands at odds with the protection function of forests. However, this seems to be the exception rather than the rule, at least as far as trade-offs were mentioned in the interviews.

In terms of **lack of expertise and knowledge**, interviewees noted that current training and hazard assessment are often lacking holistic multi-risk integration (Interviewee B8). The need to better connect hydro-meteorological, geological, and ecological knowledge is a recurrent theme throughout interviews, as described in the following sections. Currently, coordination between departments responsible for forestry, natural hazards, biodiversity, and spatial planning is mostly case-based and depends on informal collaboration or personal initiative. Furthermore, the idea that predicting and planning for cascading risks might not be practical and even distract from more immediate risks emerged:

“Such cascading processes are taken into account in the hazard assessment if they are recognizable, i.e. if they are sufficiently likely to occur in an area. Theoretically, anything is possible almost anywhere (...). So you really need clear signs. For example, a rockfall from which a debris flow can occur must also be apparent or have already occurred so that the further cascades can then be mapped. Otherwise the 'normal' hazard processes will simply be completely dominated by these cascades and that won't serve the purpose either, as the priorities would then probably be on the wrong hazard sources.” B2

Enablers

In terms of enablers, interviewees pointed to the value of **supportive policies and legal frameworks**, in particular integrated risk management (IRM) frameworks that consider the full spectrum of natural hazards (Interviewees B8, B10). It was highlighted that IRM is legally grounded in Switzerland, and it is considered the standard for assessing and managing risk. This also goes hand in hand with the PROTECTpraxis guidelines, as they allow for more flexibility in terms of which measure is selected for risk mitigation:

“If a protection deficit exists, we follow the principles of integrated risk management. That means biological, technical, and organizational measures are fundamentally equal... and authorities must find the most appropriate and cost-effective combination.” - B10

In the case of protective forests, IRM was seen as helping prioritize protective functions while also integrating ecological, social, and economic factors in risk management. **Evidence on these co-benefits** was therefore seen as a key enabler, which relates to the multi-functionality (or co-benefits) of protection forests. The multifunctionality of forests is thus well recognised and highlighted in numerous Swiss policy reports (Angst, 2012; BAFU, 2021, 2025). Forests are also defined as multi-functional ecosystems in the Federal Forest Act (WaG) and defined as a forest management priority in the Swiss Forest Policy (BAFU, 2021). As previously noted, both NaiS and PROTECTpraxis equally address multi-functionality (even if secondary to protection functions). More relevant to multi-risks, in Switzerland, forests are also seen as inherently capable of addressing multiple risks simultaneously — including rockfall, avalanches, erosion, and shallow landslides.

“Protection forests always have the advantage that they work for several hazard processes at the same time.” - B2

Beyond their recognition as risk reduction measures for multiple natural hazards, several interviewees emphasized the synergies that protection forests provide for **biodiversity and climate change adaptation** (among others through carbon sequestration), which therefore represented the second most frequent enabler. Protection forests, when properly maintained, can thus be aligned with multiple land uses. Additionally, their resilience in case of an event, such as root structures continuing to stabilize slopes post-disturbance, also make them seen as valuable in multi-risk contexts.

A more general finding is the way risk (in the context of multi-risks) is prioritized. There was general consensus that human lives always stand at the highest order of priority, with everything else (including physical assets or even nature conservation) being secondary:

“If you look at the protection goals, human protection has absolute priority over property damage (...). When discussing risks and the need for action, the protection of people takes priority.” B3

Protection forest barriers

The governance barriers to protection forest conservation, restoration and maintenance, results are presented in figure 12 below. A total of N=120 barriers were extracted from interviews.

Figure 11: Frequency and classification of protection forest barriers, based on interview data collected in Bern.

Biodiversity loss and climate threats were by far the most frequently mentioned hindrance to maintaining protective forests (N=40), despite (as for the enablers) this cluster not being part of the original coding structure. As both of these threats are so strongly interrelated and therefore often impossible to differentiate, both themes were merged into the same cluster. We note that this barrier cluster mainly concerns the last part of the NbS implementation process, i.e., protection forests’ sustainability and long-term survival. Generally, our warming climate and the uncertainties associated with it were a core concern, particularly for the future protective function of forests. As mentioned by Interviewee B12:

“Protection forests are very important for our mountain regions to be habitable at all. Half of Swiss forests are protective forests. And if you imagine, for example, that half of it would no longer be functional due to climate change, it would probably be economically inconceivable to replace it all by technical measures.”

Interviewees also emphasised specific threats that a changing climate and related biodiversity loss represent for protection forests. These include bark beetle outbreaks, which are exacerbated by extreme climate events such as droughts and storms (Singh et al., 2024). Wildfires, which have been increasing in the southern parts of Switzerland, including canton Ticino, were also mentioned by interviewees. A paramount observation by interviewees is also the interconnectedness of these crises, such as droughts increasing the probability of pest outbreaks or droughts leading to increased wildfires. Many interviewees were very aware of feedback loops and cascading effects at the biodiversity-climate nexus.

In addition to the increased frequency of extreme events, changes in species compositions and richness, functional diversity, phenology (e.g., the seasonality of leaf falls) and entire ecosystem dynamics were highlighted as key threats. For example, interviewee B13 emphasised the vulnerability of mountain ecosystems to climate change:

“The biggest challenge at the moment is climate change. Because in protection forests we are in steep terrain, where climate gradients are very large over short distances and where a lot will change over the next few decades in terms of tree species, suitability and dynamics.”

Furthermore, the spread of invasive tree species such as the tree of heaven (*Ailanthus altissima*) that has little to no protection function due to its thin trunk and is not eaten by ungulates (which prefer native species) was mentioned by several interviewees (N=4).

These results are in line with a recent report on the state of Swiss forests, produced by the Federal Office for the Environment (BAFU, 2025). The report highlights that climate change (in particular extreme events, pests and invasives) are among the greatest threats to Swiss forests, with insufficient tree species that are ‘fit for the future’. The report also calls for adaptive, close-to-nature silviculture in order to retain forests’ adaptability and resilience to climatic changes.

Finally, a key topic which emerged throughout interviews was the lack of regeneration due to ungulate browsing. Because the issue is only indirectly related to biodiversity and climate change, it is addressed in a separate cluster.

Risk and risk aversion was the second most frequent cluster (N=14). This cluster was adapted from the original framework, which only included ‘risk aversion’ and therefore missed an essential aspect related to risk in itself, from a quantitative perspective (regardless of whether an aversion to it exists or not). For example, a recurrent barrier mentioned by interviewees is the limits of NbS and protection forests in high-risk areas. As pointed out by interviewee B3:

“Protection forests do have their limits. After all, what risk do you want to protect yourself against? That also has its limits.”

It appears that in Switzerland, risk is assessed in a very systematic and integrated manner (PLANAT, 2024). Thus, well-established quantitative tools such as hazard maps, guidelines the likes of NaiS and PROTECTpraxis, and risk classification systems play an important role in informing DRM, with very little being left to chance (Bründl, 2012).

A further important observation is the fact that grey measures in Swiss mountain regions often serve as temporary solutions until the biological measure has matured enough to take over the protection function (Interviewee B2, B3, B6). This is interesting as it helps overcome another criticism of NbS, namely their long gestation periods (Lehmann et al., 2025) - up to hundreds of years in the case of forests (Herbert et al., 2022). Indeed, due to a mismatch between long ecological maturity timeframes and short-term political election cycles, NbS are still mainly designed to achieve short-term successes rather than long-term sustainability (Turner et al., 2022). While less prevalent, risk aversion was also among the elements mentioned within this cluster. Several interviewees highlighted the uncertainty still associated with NbS, e.g. in case of a storm or a pest decimating the forest.

Human-wildlife conflicts emerged as a further important barrier (N=13). Ungulate (particularly deer and chamois) browsing is a complex socio-ecological issue in many alpine countries, including Switzerland. Drastic increases in ungulate populations (particularly in the Eastern parts of the country) have led to tree saplings and seedlings being browsed to an extent where forests can no longer regenerate (Kupferschmid et al., 2015). While there are many hypotheses for explaining the recent explosion in ungulate populations, likely reasons include the loss of predators which

would normally control population sizes, as well as the loss of snow cover, creating more suitable habitats for ungulates (Frei et al., 2025; Partl et al., 2002). Human-wildlife conflicts were the barrier for which interviewees expressed the biggest urgency:

“But if I have to prioritize one challenge, then it's absolutely the deer problem. It's the biggest problem by far. So factor 100 compared to forest fires for example.” - B7

“We can no longer manage the [forest] regeneration and regeneration is the future. In other words, from my point of view, we are simply throwing money down the drain because there is simply no more regeneration. If nothing new can grow, then we simply have to stop.” - B9

While hunting and culling are among the possible management strategies (Kupferschmid et al., 2020), the issue remains highly conflict-laden with hunting traditions often not being aligned with the most effective population control measures, e.g., hunting females while hunters prefer to hunt males, hunting for age groups with the highest reproduction rate.

The issue of ungulate browsing is widely recognised in Swiss forests assessments. For example, the 2025 Forest Report for Switzerland highlights that forest regeneration is inadequate in many places, impacting on protection forest function (BAFU, 2025). It was estimated that about 30% of protection forests have too little secondary growth, and that this number is increasing. The report therefore calls for silvicultural interventions and ungulate regulations which are systematically coordinated with representatives from hunting authorities and nature conservation bodies.

Lack of expertise and knowledge were the fourth most frequently mentioned barriers for protection forests (N=10). Interviewees mentioned the lack of existing data on forests, as well as the lack of quality in existing data. In particular, lack of knowledge on how protection forests will evolve in the face of extreme events and climate change were mentioned. The lack of workforces that can carry out protection forest maintenance was also mentioned, as pointed out by interviewee B6:

“In my canton, about half of the foresters, or those of the municipalities, have their own workers, so their own forest wardens. The rest is provided by forestry companies, and their availability is limited. If a municipality calls for tenders and no one responds because everyone already has enough work, no one is found or the costs become exorbitant. In other words, the shortage of skilled workers may also become an issue in this area.”

Similarly, the idea that forest dynamics are complex and require specialised knowledge and training emerged in several interviews. A (small) divide between natural hazard practitioners and forest ecologists also became apparent in several interviews. For example, interviewee B13 was of the opinion that:

“I actually think it's important that people who work in the field of natural hazards should also have a background in forests and forest dynamics (...). Or that they receive further training in relation to mountain forests and protection forests and the opportunities that are available there.”

Issues related to **land ownership and availability** also ranked high in terms of barriers (N=9). Codes in this cluster mainly referred to the fact that protection forests already exist on nearly all land surfaces on which they could exist - there is thus a lack of space for further forests. As Interviewee B8 explained:

“Either you're in a steep area and then there are already forests there, or you're in a flat area and then it's built over.”

The other issue addressed by interviewees concerned private forest owners who do not always maintain their forests. Private forests represent about a third of Switzerland’s forests or about half of canton Bern’s forests (Kuchli & Blaser, 2012). Yet, due to the financial incentives and subsidies provided to landowners for maintaining forests as well as regulative instruments, such as the clear-cutting ban, this barrier was not perceived as prominent.

The absence of data has important implications for our findings. For example, **funding and financing tools** did not feature prominently as barriers (N=6). This is most likely related to the fact that protection forests are well subsidized and long established in Switzerland. Funding and financing constraints were therefore not perceived as a significant barrier to protection forest implementation. This differs from other studies, where funding streams and existing financing mechanisms have consistently been identified as major hurdles for implementing NbS (Toxopeus & Polzin, 2021; den Heijer et al., 2023; Sarabi et al., 2020). However, this is also related to the fact that it is considered cheaper to conserve existing forests than to create new ones (through afforestation) or even restore them (Austin et al., 2020; Mori & Isbell, 2024).

Other barriers, such as stakeholder conflicts and equity (N=5), lack of evidence on performance and co-benefits (N=4), sectoral or administrative silos (N=4), lack of political will and long-term commitment (N=2), lack of supportive policy or legal frameworks (N=2), time commitment and complexity (N=1), path dependency (N=1) and potential negative impacts (N=1) were also identified as barriers, yet less frequently mentioned.

Protection forest enablers

Next, we discuss results related to enablers and barriers of implementing protection forests. A total of N=144 governance enablers of protection forests were extracted from interviews (Fig. 12). As most enablers within clusters were mentioned less than 5 times (9/16 clusters), we focus the discussion on those enablers that were most prevalent.

Figure 12: Frequency and classification of protection forest enablers, based on interview data collected in Bern.

As shown in figure 12, **supportive policies and legal frameworks** were the most frequently mentioned enabler (N=35). This is in line with the aforementioned strong legal backing pertaining to protection forests in Switzerland. Indeed, interviewees mostly referred to specific legal mechanisms and policies, such as the NaiS guidelines, designed to ensure the sustainable management of protection forests (Angst, 2012); SilvaProtect-CH, aimed to standardize the designation of protection forests (Losey & Wehrli, 2012); and the federal forestry law (WaG), yet interviewees specifically mentioned its 1902 clear-cutting ban (Bürgi & Schuler, 2003).

Among these policies and legal frameworks, NaiS were the most frequently mentioned (over 45 times) by interviewees, suggesting a high importance attributed to these guidelines.

“NaiS is the standard practice tool for protection forests here [in Switzerland]. It is also well understood and has been implemented for 20 years now.”- B9

With 23 mentions, **funding and financial tools, support and cost-effectiveness** were the second most prevalent enablers. This mainly included the state subsidies that exist for managing and conserving protection forests, as mentioned by interviewee B11:

“So, the thing with NaiS is, there is funding attached to that. That's why NaiS is highly relevant for financing of forest management for protection forests (...). That's why everyone knows it, because it is relevant for getting subsidies.”

While protection forest management and maintenance costs are covered differently depending on the canton and municipality, the general funding model consists of the federal government covering the largest part of the costs (around 60%, yet sometimes up to 90%), followed by the canton (around 30%), while the municipality covers the remainder and smallest proportion (around 10%).

A further perceived enabler in this cluster was the cost-effectiveness of protection forests for DRR, as highlighted by interviewee B2:

“And if there is a protection deficit and the protection deficit can be remedied with biological measures such as protection forest maintenance or reforestation, then it is usually the most cost-effective option.”

A further interesting finding is the fact that due to Switzerland's steep terrain, timber harvesting (particularly on slopes) would not be profitable. This is certainly an additional incentive for maintaining protection forests.

Biodiversity and climate change, which were not part of the original cluster framework, were added because of their emergent importance in results (N=20). Enablers in this cluster are not direct governance enablers. They related to the significance of biodiversity in maintaining the protective function of forests (therefore relating more to the sustainability of protection forests), as well as the fact that protection forests provide many co-benefits, including biodiversity, which adds more weight to arguments in their favour. The ways in which NaiS and PROTECTpraxis address biodiversity is described in detail in section 8.3.2. As noted by interviewee B9:

“We can certainly do something for biodiversity, for example, within a protection forest. So, there's no conflict at all. On the contrary. Or we lay trees across the floor, deliberately, that creates deadwood, and tall branches that still offer protection. So we also do something for biodiversity at the same time.”

In addition to the creation of deadwood, the conservation of grouse was given as a further example of biodiversity actions compatible with protection forests by several interviewees. This is also reflected in literature. For example, Kaeser & Zimmermann (2014) note the compatibility between Swiss forests' protection and biodiversity goals and argue that designated forest reserves within protection forests offers a high conservation potential.

The importance of biodiversity for maintaining resilience in light of a changing climate also emerged in interviews. Careful considerations and experiments to find out which species will prevail under new climatic conditions, as well as assisted migration of tree species, were mentioned as possible preparedness options. While NaiS recognises the need for climate change adaptation in the management of protection forests, in practice (according to interviewees), its application has been uneven.

Related to this, **evidence on performance and co-benefits** also emerged as an important enabler of protection forests (N=15). This cluster included many aspects, such as the long-proven evidence of protection forests' role in DRR, as noted by Interviewee B1:

“All communities where a certain slope is present trust and have been trusting in green infrastructure or measures for generations.”

The recognition of protection forests' role in protecting lives is well documented. For example, in a survey with over 3000 Swiss citizens, Frick et al. (2018) found that 81% of respondents were well informed about forest' role in mitigating risks from natural hazards.

The importance of quantifying risk reduction due to protection forests also emerged in several interviews. Interviewee B3 highlights:

“People have tried to refute these arguments [against protection forests], which have always claimed that, yes, there will be a storm and then [the forest] will be gone anyway. It's unsafe. It was then actually shown on the basis of all the storm damage, data etc. that this is not necessarily true. It can be just as reliable.”

The multifunctionality of Swiss forests in terms of co-benefits was also mentioned by interviewees. This multifunctionality (encompassing ecological, economic, and social dimensions) is recognised and highlighted in numerous reports and studies (Angst, 2012; BAFU, 2021; BAFU, 2025; Frick et al., 2018). Similarly, several interviewees mentioned the importance of protection forests mitigating multiple risks.

Expertise and knowledge was the fifth most frequently mentioned enabler (N=13). This largely relates to the importance of knowledge in ecological and forest dynamics for enabling the effective management of a protection forest. Indeed, as living structures, protection forests need constant maintenance to be able to fulfil all of their functions (Küchli & Blaser, 2012). Additionally, knowledge resources and platforms, such as Switzerland's mountain forest conservation office (Fachstelle Gebirgswaldpflege), the [TreeApp](#) website (an online mapping tool that provides recommendations on which tree species can grow where in Switzerland) and more local facilities like Bern's seedling nursery and their research were mentioned.

While the remaining clusters (from most frequently mentioned to least frequently mentioned: Polycentric and cross-sectoral arrangements (N=8); Stakeholder engagement & equity (N=7); Political will & long-term commitment (N=4); Champions and advocates (N=3); Disaster (N=3); Flexibility and adaptiveness (N=3); Clear roles and responsibilities (N=3); Aesthetics (N=1); Communication and raising awareness (N=1); Risk reduction (N=1)) should by no means be dismissed, they will not be discussed.

PROTECTpraxis guidelines barriers

As the PROTECTpraxis guidelines have not yet been implemented (as of May 2025), results in this section mostly refer to either potentially foreseen barriers, or barriers experienced in the runup to and the design of the guidelines (sometimes also relating to the previous versions of the guidelines, Protect and Protect Bio). Figure 13 illustrates the frequency of the 40 barriers mentioned by interviewees, organised by clusters.

Figure 13: Frequency and classification of PROTECTpraxis guideline governance barriers, based on interview data collected in Bern.

A first result to note is the low number of barriers mentioned by interviewees compared to enablers (40 vs. 84). This can either be due to the fact that the guidelines have not yet been applied, or the fact that interviewees simply perceived fewer barriers to the guidelines than enablers.

The most frequently mentioned barrier was **lack of and complexity of financing** (N=10). While this may seem surprising given the fact that funding and financial tools and support were the third most frequent enabler, interviewees highlighted a specific cost that they expect to increase with the new guidelines. Indeed, this barrier is closely related to the second most frequent one, **time requirements and complexity** (N=9). Interviewees raised concerns that PROTECTpraxis may still be relatively complex to apply, which incurs a larger time investment. This time requirement translates into higher costs for hazard management practitioners, which would have to account for this in offers to bids, giving them a competitive disadvantage. As interviewee B2 explained:

“But the question is simply how much time does a [hazard assessment] specialist plan to use this method? And precisely because of the competition, it can happen that hours are cut and then tightened up if you realize that you would have needed more time.”

Interviewee B4 also adds:

“Because the most economically advantageous offer, as the saying goes, will of course be awarded the contract. But basically, yes, if the conditions are the same for everyone, it should be done according to that. Of course, it then depends on how exactly it is implemented by the canton, what exactly is ultimately required. Whether you are then still the cheapest is the other question.”

Concerns about the second aspect of this cluster, the guideline methodology’s complexity, also emerged in interviews. However, this point was contested as it seems different target users of the guidelines feel differently about their complexity. As interviewee B9 explained:

“So originally the aim was to simplify Protect (...). And in the end we have a product that some [forest ecology] experts say is far too simple, that you can't do it that way. And the others probably say it's too complicated. It's just such a difficult balance.”

Yet, as mentioned before, creating a more user-friendly tool was a key aim of the new version of Protect - therefore, a certain level of simplification and streamlining was purposeful, as noted by interviewee B2:

“We deliberately left a lot of things out originally because we said it was too detailed, too specific. Even a natural sciences expert can't judge that. We don't have the basic data and so we deliberately left that out.”

In the same vein, **lack of expertise and knowledge** (N=8) was seen as a further potential barrier. The guidelines are seen (by some) as complex to use, therefore requiring specialised knowledge, as well as data (e.g., tree counts or diameter) that do not exist in all cantons. Interviewee B4 highlighted the potential conflict between specialists from different domains:

“And that was also a point. The forest specialists actually said from the onset that it is imperative that the natural hazards specialist also takes along the forest specialists for an assessment [using the PROTECTpraxis guidelines]. We then formulated this in such a way that it should actually be a rule. But of course we can't dictate that. But this is also one of these fields of tension between different specialists.”

Besides, the human element of organizational measures and depending on the preparedness, knowledge and training of citizens in case of an event was mentioned as a potential weak point of the guidelines.

Other barriers (N=3), biodiversity loss and climate threats (N=2), lack of supportive policy or legal frameworks (N=2), sectoral or administrative silos (N=2), stakeholder conflicts and equity (N=2), lack of evidence on performance and co-benefits (N=1) and risk and risk aversion (N=1) only represented small portions of the barriers mentioned by interviewees.

PROTECTpraxis guidelines enablers

We now turn to the analysis of enablers of the PROTECTpraxis guidelines. Here, enablers were less frequent (due to the specificity of the topic with which not all interviewees were familiar) more evenly distributed (N=84) than for protection forests as a whole, as can be seen in figure 14.

Figure 14: Frequency of PROTECTpraxis guideline governance enablers, classified by clusters, as identified from interviews in Bern.

The most frequently mentioned enablers related to **evidence on performance and co-benefits** (N=18). This is fully aligned with the primary aim of the guidelines, which is to provide a standardized tool and aid for assessing risk reduction of both structural and biological measures. Interviewees clearly highlighted the added value of the revised guidelines:

“[PROTECTpraxis] also makes [hazard] assessments comparable and provides a working aid to know which points you need to look at, and you can also discuss an assessment based on concrete criteria and not just a gut feeling. Whether it will work or not work. And you can explain exactly why you've come to this conclusion. (...)” - B2

This also matters for protection forests, since as pointed out by the same interviewee:

“You can also better compare the effect of a protective forest with a technical measure if you do it quantitatively.”

While the primary aim of the guidelines was not to focus solely on biological measures (as these are already covered by the NaiS guidelines), interviewees did highlight their overarching goal to better integrate natural hazard assessments and forestry and act as a ‘common language’ for practitioners coming from both of these fields.

The second most frequently mentioned enabler was, similarly to protection forests, **supportive policies and legal frameworks** (N=14). This related to the fact that guidelines built on preceding versions (Protect and Protect Bio) which, having existed for over a decade, are already established in the risk management landscape and known by practitioners. Additionally, while there is no direct legal obligation to apply the guidelines, it is expected that the federal government and cantonal agencies who mandate risk reduction measures will make the usage of the guideline’s compulsory in their terms of reference. Furthermore, there might be financial

incentives put into place at the federal level for applying the guidelines - however, this remains to be seen once they become fully implemented.

Funding and financial tools and support - and in our cluster, **cost-effectiveness** - was the third most frequently mentioned enabler cluster (N=11). This cluster included the fact that funding for the PROTECTpraxis project existed in the first place, representing an essential prerequisite. Additionally, cost-effectiveness represented an important aspect of this cluster which was not part of the original cluster framework. This related to the idea that the guidelines allow practitioners to consider the cost-effectiveness of biological, structural, organisational or a combination of these measures, where biological measures can (under certain circumstances) be the more cost-effective solution. Similarly, the fact that the guidelines help show a return on investment on biological measures was also highlighted by interviewees. As interviewee B4 highlighted:

“And what of course clearly plays a role is that we always have to prove whether the measure is cost-effective, i.e. whether it is economical, whether the benefits are greater than the costs.”

Expertise and knowledge were perceived as a further enabler of the guidelines. Here, interviewees referred to the fact that the guidelines were among others created to combine knowledge and expertise from different sectors, i.e. risk management and more classic engineering, forestry and to some extent ecology. Therefore, this aspect of the cluster represents more of an advantage or selling point of the guidelines than a proven enabler. As interviewee B9 pointed out:

“I think it is very important that the forest is viewed in the same way as a technical measure, a structural measure and/or an organizational measure. There was the predecessor of PROTECTpraxis, the Protect, and the forest was only very marginally included in that. Then there was Protect Bio, which was another historical development to include the forest. But that mainly appealed to foresters, forest engineers perhaps less so, or natural hazard people or people who work in natural hazard offices, and so on. And now the aim is to really bring it all together using the same method.”

Yet, interviewees also mentioned the fact that the guidelines were the result of an extensive consultation process that involved actors from the different relevant sectors and disciplines, including academia, practitioners, decision-makers at different scales and the private sector (particularly companies offering hazard management, mapping and management services).

Related to this, **polycentric and cross-sectoral arrangements** (N=8) was also seen as an enabler. Polycentricity denotes a governance system where decision-making is distributed both across different scales and sectors (Ostrom, 2010; Carlisle et al., 2019). This result can therefore be explained by the fact that one of the core goals of the PROTECTpraxis guidelines is to integrate knowledge from different sectors (mainly forestry and DRM) in one tool that can be used by different types of practitioners.

Less frequently mentioned enablers included communication and raising awareness (N=6) (which is aligned with the aforementioned consultation process of the guidelines), political will and long-term commitment (N=5), stakeholder engagement & equity (N=5), risk reduction (N=3), biodiversity & climate change (N=1), champions and advocates (N=1), flexibility and adaptiveness (N=1) and other enablers (N=1).

8.4.5 Summary and key messages

In the Bern case, key enablers and barriers related to protection forests and the Swiss PROTECTpraxis guidelines were identified through 14 semi-structured interviews. Protection forests have long existed in Switzerland (some for centuries) following their formal recognition in

the 1876 Federal Forest Act. As such, current governance challenges do not center on afforestation, but rather on the long-term conservation, maintenance and restoration of existing forests to ensure their continued protective function. In contrast, the PROTECTpraxis guidelines are still in the pre-implementation phase (even though they build on previous versions of the guidelines). Therefore, the identified enablers and barriers relate primarily to their design, planning, and anticipated application. Our analysis provides insights into the governance conditions that have or could further enable the implementation of protection forests and related PROTECTpraxis guidelines, as well as those aspects which pose challenges for their implementation. We also consider these enablers and barriers in the context of multi-risk DRR.

An important enabler of protection forests (and, though less prominently, the PROTECTpraxis guidelines) for multi-risk DRR was evidence on co-benefits, particularly relating to multifunctionality of protection forests which can mitigate multiple hazards (e.g., landslides, rockfalls) while contributing to biodiversity and climate goals. Supportive policies and legal frameworks, especially Switzerland's adherence to Integrated Risk Management (IRM) principles, were also seen as crucial for implementing multi-risk DRR. Main barriers included risk and risk aversion, where the unpredictability and complexity of multi-risk and cascading events was seen as making proactive planning challenging. Interviewees also questioned the effectiveness of protection forests in light of large-scale cascading events. As an important caveat to the most important enabler cluster, namely protection forests' co-benefits, future uncertainties relating to climate change and biodiversity loss (as well as trade-offs between them) and consequences for forest resilience emerged as key barriers. Interviewees also noted that current practices often fail to account for multi-risk interactions, and that disciplinary silos persist. This is compounded by unclear definitions of multi-risk and cascading risks, pointing to the need for clearer, cross-sectoral frameworks.

Key enablers for implementing protection forests in Bern and beyond included strong legal and policy frameworks, especially the widely used NaiS guidelines, and significant financial support through federal and cantonal subsidies. Protection forests are seen as cost-effective solutions for DRR. Biodiversity and climate co-benefits also emerged as important, with measures like deadwood creation supporting both ecological and protective functions. Longstanding evidence of protection forests' effectiveness, public trust, and strong knowledge networks further reinforce their role. Other enablers such as cross-sector collaboration and stakeholder engagement were also mentioned, but less frequently represented. In contrast, key barriers included the threat of climate change and biodiversity loss. Interviewees expressed concern over how extreme weather events, pest outbreaks, and shifting species compositions threaten the long-term survival and functionality of protection forests. Closely related was the growing problem of ungulate browsing which severely hinders forest regeneration. Risk and risk aversion were also cited, especially in high-risk zones where protection forests alone may be insufficient. Further barriers included a shortage of expert knowledge, data, and skilled labour and land availability, since most suitable areas for protection forests are already forested. Financing was not perceived as a major obstacle due to robust public support.

Regarding the PROTECTpraxis guidelines, the most frequently cited enabler was evidence on performance and co-benefits, highlighting how the guidelines provide a standardized method for assessing risk reduction, including from protection forests. Supportive policies and legal frameworks were also highlighted, as the guidelines build on long-established tools (Protect and Protect Bio) and may become a requirement for receiving subsidies. Similarly, funding, financing and cost-effectiveness were seen as key, with interviewees noting that the guidelines will help demonstrate the economic value of biological measures. The potential of the guidelines to increase expertise and knowledge sharing across forestry, engineering, and risk management experts was seen as a further important enabler. Interviewees also highlighted the polycentric and cross-sectoral arrangements that enabled this new version of the guidelines. In comparison,

the most cited barrier was lack and complexity of financing, mainly due to the higher time and cost demands interviewees anticipated for applying the guidelines. Closely related, the guideline's time requirements and complexity represented further concerns, especially regarding competition in public tenders and varying perceptions of the guidelines' difficulty across different fields of expertise. As the guidelines will require specialised knowledge from different fields, tensions between forest and natural hazard experts were noted as potential challenges for their implementation.

9. Suggested enablers for advancing NbS as multi-risk DRR

The following suggestions are drawn from insights gathered through the research conducted in the three case studies and supported by existing literature. They represent potential strategies for transforming current risk management practices by better integrating multi-risk and NbS. While many of these ideas are not new in concept, their ambitious implementation, scaling, and integration into risk governance have the potential to drive innovative, system-wide shifts in how we address complex, interconnected risks. These suggestions aim to address existing gaps, foster the adoption of NbS, and enhance the overall effectiveness of multi-risk DRR through the use of such measures.

Key suggested enablers from Valencia

- **Establish municipal NbS coordination units or roles**
 - Create a dedicated office or role within city governments, especially in cities with increasing experience in the implementation of NbS projects. This unit could facilitate cross-departmental coordination (e.g. with risk management) and provide centralised guidance, lifecycle planning, and stakeholder engagement. It can also address common challenges like limited technical capacity, fragmented governance structures, and unclear responsibilities, especially concerning the long-term maintenance and monitoring of NbS projects. In cases like Valencia, where municipalities benefit from a certain degree of autonomy, creating such roles within existing departments can be especially effective.
- **Develop a technical manual for NbS**
 - Develop a specific technical manual to guide the design, implementation, maintenance and evaluation of NbS, using different construction and design manuals as reference. This document should be elaborated by a multidisciplinary consortium of professionals (urban planners, engineers, ecologists, architects, etc.), be reviewed and updated periodically (e.g. every five years).
 - Institutionalize the manual as a normative reference framework, integrating ecological, social and technical aspects within a multi-risk and adaptive strategy. Such manual's dynamic nature would allow for the incorporation of learning from practical experience, thus ensuring continuous improvement in the application of NbS as they become more widespread.
- **Implement mandatory comparative assessment in projects**
 - Require urban and infrastructure intervention proposals to carry out comparative assessments in which grey, hybrid and nature-based alternatives are analysed. Integrate ecosystem services analysis and multi-hazard analysis to assess the environmental, social and economic benefits derived from each option, as well as the degree of protection against a wide range of hazards. The cost of maintenance should be included into financial assessments to ensure the economic sustainability of interventions in the long term. This will allow a solution to be chosen not on the basis of inertia or habit, but on the basis of evidence of performance, benefits and sustainability.

- **Strengthen financing mechanisms linked to territorial equity**
 - Strengthen mechanisms for collecting and directing resources linked to ecosystem services (e.g. surcharges currently applied to the water bill in Valencia).
 - Orient this collection towards priority interventions in vulnerable urban areas, promoting territorial equity, environmental justice and differential protection against climate hazards such as heatwaves and floods.
- **Incentivize the market for NbS**
 - Promote NbS market development through incentives such as tax incentives, specific public tenders, and technical training for companies and professionals working on the design, construction and maintenance of green infrastructure.
 - Establish a registry of local NbS suppliers and best practices to ensure quality standards and transparency within the sector.

Key suggested enablers from Ogliastro

- **Promote fire-smart management strategies**
 - Develop integrated fire-smart strategies that address key wildfire risk factors while increasing landscape heterogeneity. These include silviculture, prescribed grazing, and traditional agroforestry strategies that interrupt fuel continuity, slow wildfire spread, and enhance socio-ecological resilience.
 - Incentivize multifunctional land uses that combine ecological restoration with rural socio-economic development, for example, by fostering bioeconomy initiatives and payments for ecosystem services which support active land stewardship and counteract land abandonment.
 - Facilitate collective land management by fostering the creation of forest owner associations for fire prevention (La Mela Veca et al., 2024), “rural development policies (e.g., Rural Development Programme funds), forest certifications (e.g., FSC and PEFC), and biodiversity conservation programs (e.g., Life Program)” (Spadoni et al., 2023). These strategies would help to overcome land fragmentation and re-engage small landowners.
- **Integrate local and traditional knowledge in NbS design**
 - Acknowledge and institutionalise the knowledge of agro-pastoral communities through the co-development of guidelines or participatory advisory bodies so as to enhance both the effectiveness and legitimacy of NbS. For long-term success and the fostering of mutual learning, the exchange between local and institutional knowledge must be strengthened.
 - Invest in the continued training of forest personnel. This should be supported by targeted scientific research and multi-level collaboration.

- **Strengthen participatory governance and territorial alliances for integrated risk management**
 - Establish permanent “territorial laboratories” as platforms for dialogue and inclusive governance where local authorities, forest managers, farmers, communities, and civil society co-design shared strategies. These spaces would facilitate dialogue and the solving of land-use conflicts and forest management disagreements, fostering coordinated interventions and shared-responsibility.
- **Recognize prescribed fire and pyro silviculture as NbS tools**
 - Systematically include prescribed fire and pyro silviculture (as NbS tools) in Specific Prevention Plans (Piani Locali di Prevenzione AIB) to reduce flammable biomass and increase forest resilience. Enhance this adoption through financial incentives, technical training, and participatory governance mechanisms. In Sardinia, one of the longest-running prescribed fire programs has demonstrated the technique’s potential to mitigate wildfire impacts when planned collaboratively with local stakeholders at scales broad enough to generate territorial effects (Cabiddu et al., 2023).
- **Institutionalize integrated and flexible preventive planning**
 - Integrate NbS into Territorial Forest Plans (Piani Forestali Territoriali), Specific Prevention Plans (Piani AIB), and intermediate planning instruments (linking regional and local levels) to ensure coherence and continuity.
 - Adapt promising models such as the PFIT (Piani Forestali di Indirizzo Territoriale) in Piedmont and Lombardy or the “Piani Specifici” in Tuscany to other contexts, supported by stable regulatory and financial tools for managing and maintaining prevention interventions.
- **Foster inclusive risk education and social awareness**
 - Increase public awareness of fire-smart practices by investing in grassroots campaigns involving schools, youth, and local organizations to build trust, empowerment, and social cohesion. Target messages and participatory media strategies can also help overcome resistance to effective yet controversial tools like prescribed fire.
- **Recognize interdisciplinarity as a key condition for successful NbS**
 - Promote interdisciplinary approaches that integrate ecology, forestry, sociology, anthropology, and geography aspects. Use methods such as ethnography, participant observation, and risk perception surveys to help reveal local vulnerabilities and inform place-specific solutions.
 - Institutionalize interdisciplinary training and cross-sectoral collaboration in fire management policies to overcome narrow, technocratic approaches.
- **Foster synergies between active and passive wildfire defence through financial and community-based instruments**
 - Combine active prevention (e.g. land management, prescribed fire) with passive financial instruments such as community-based insurance schemes and payments for ecosystem

services to incentivise long-term land stewardship, enhance the economic viability of preventive practices, and ensure broader social participation. When designed collaboratively, these tools can strengthen trust among actors, redistribute risk, and create a virtuous cycle of co-responsibility and investment in fire-smart landscapes. Develop hybrid solutions that mutually reinforce ecological action and financial protection for moving beyond emergency responses and toward a culture of shared resilience.

Key suggested enablers from Bern

- **Strengthen the biodiversity and climate nexus**
 - Further recognition of biodiversity climate interactions and their impact on forest resilience in existing policy frameworks, including Forest Management Plans, NaiS and Protect guidelines. These can include adaptive silviculture practices (e.g., mixed-species planting, assisted migration) as well as biodiversity-enhancing practices (e.g., use of deadwood, invasive species management).
 - Incentivize these practices through enhanced federal or cantonal subsidies, which could be tied to existing guidelines, such as NaiS.
 - In order to bridge sectoral silos, establish a climate-biodiversity risk task force bringing together professionals from both disciplines to develop appropriate planning responses that consider the biodiversity-climate nexus, its linkages, synergies and feedbacks. For example, such a task force could sit between cantonal forest and natural hazard agencies (Amt für Wald und Naturgefahren) and cantonal agencies for the environment and energy (Amt für Umwelt und Energie).
- **Mitigate ungulate browsing pressure**
 - Mandate regional game management plans that include ecological (carrying capacity) targets and adapt hunting quotas accordingly.
 - Subsidize protective measures, such as deer exclosures and fencing in vulnerable regeneration zones, especially where afforestation is critical for slope stability.
 - Introduce a forest regeneration monitoring program to track recovery success and better target problem areas.
- **Address workforce gaps in protection forest and multi-risk management**
 - Expand forestry and natural hazard management apprenticeships, curricula and training programs to include interdisciplinary modules that go beyond their core discipline. Possible existing educational structures that could host interdisciplinary training in higher education include FAN, cantonal forestry schools and WSL.
 - Mandate interdisciplinary consultations in the PROTECTpraxis application, e.g. through a formal requirement to involve at least one expert outside the applicant's core discipline (e.g., ecology in civil engineering projects, forestry in hazard mapping).
 - Expand NaiS to include other non-gravitational hazards in specific modules, e.g. wildfires, floods, and how to incorporate them in multi-risk assessments.

- **Strengthen the uptake and implementation of PROTECTpraxis guidelines**
 - Mandate PROTECTpraxis use in all funded risk reduction planning (e.g. hazard maps, infrastructure projects)
 - Provide financial incentives for early adoption, such as one-time subsidies to consultancies adopting the new methodology or including it in tenders, thus overcoming the barrier of anticipated time commitments for its application
 - Organize further cross-sectoral training workshops to familiarize engineers, ecologists, foresters, and hazard management practitioners with PROTECTpraxis in a unified setting
- **Enhance multi-risk and cascading risk integration**
 - Create a multi-risk focal point (e.g., at AWN) to coordinate and liaise between natural hazard, forestry, biodiversity, and spatial planning units.
 - Pilot multi-hazard risk scenarios using PROTECTpraxis and existing hazard maps. This would involve identifying test sites where multi-risks are likely and help visualize how failure in one system (e.g., loss of forest cover) increases vulnerability in another (e.g., droughts).
 - Launch a terminology harmonization and training initiative to build common definitions and understandings of multi-risk between foresters, engineers, spatial planners, and civil society. This could also involve co-developing a visual risk matrix tool or decision-tree for identifying:
 - Interaction types (e.g., compounding, cascading).
 - Appropriate combinations of NbS, grey, and organizational measures.

The following table 8 presents the suggestions emerging from the three cases organized into categories. An inductive thematic analysis (Fereday & Muir-Cochrane, 2006; Vaismoradi et al., 2016) was used to identify patterns and themes directly from the data, allowing for the flexible development of categories based on the suggestions made by the three case studies.

Table 8: Governance strategies for integrating multi-risk and NbS. Suggestions organized by category.

Category	Suggestion	Valencia	Ogliastra	Bern
Institutional structures and coordination	Establish municipal NbS coordination units or roles within city governments	✓		
	Establish a registry of local NbS suppliers and best practices to ensure quality standards and transparency within the sector	✓		
	Establish permanent “territorial laboratories” as platforms for dialogue and inclusive governance where local authorities, forest managers, farmers, communities, and civil society co-design shared strategies		✓	

	Develop a climate-biodiversity risk task force to bridge sectoral silos and integrate interdisciplinary approaches in risk management			✓
	Create a multi-risk focal point to coordinate natural hazard, forestry, biodiversity, and spatial planning units			✓
Policy and regulatory frameworks	Develop and institutionalize a technical manual for NbS to guide the design, implementation, maintenance and evaluation of NbS	✓		
	Mandate comparative assessment in urban and infrastructure projects to include grey, hybrid, and nature-based alternatives.	✓		
	Strengthen financing mechanisms linked to territorial equity, such as resource collection from ecosystem services for vulnerable areas	✓		
	Systematically include prescribed fire and pyro silviculture (as NbS tools) in Specific Prevention Plans (Piani Locali di Prevenzione AIB)		✓	
	Integrate NbS into Territorial Forest Plans (Piani Forestali Territoriali), Specific Prevention Plans (Piani AIB), and intermediate planning instruments		✓	
	Mandate the use of PROTECTpraxis in risk reduction planning and interdisciplinary consultations in its application			✓
	Further recognition of biodiversity climate interactions and their impact on forest resilience in existing policy frameworks, including Forest Management Plans, NaiS and Protect guidelines.			✓
	Introduce a forest regeneration monitoring program to track recovery success and better target problem areas.			✓
	Mandate regional game management plans that include ecological (carrying capacity) targets and adapt hunting quotas accordingly			✓
	Launch a terminology harmonization and training initiative to build common definitions and understandings of multi-risk between foresters, engineers, spatial planners, and civil society.			✓
	Incentivize the NbS market through tax incentives, public tenders, and professional training	✓		

Financial and economic instruments	Invest in the continued training of forest personnel		✓	
	Foster synergies between active and passive wildfire defence through community-based insurance schemes and payments for ecosystem services		✓	
	Provide financial incentives for early adoption of PROTECTpraxis, such as one-time subsidies to consultancies adopting the new methodology or including it in tenders			✓
	Subsidize protective measures, such as deer exclosures and fencing in vulnerable regeneration zones, especially where afforestation is critical for slope stability			✓
Interdisciplinary and integrated risk management	Organize cross-sectoral / interdisciplinary training workshops. (e.g. to familiarize engineers, ecologists, foresters, and hazard management practitioners with PROTECTpraxis)		✓	✓
	Address workforce gaps through interdisciplinary training and consultations in risk management practices		✓	✓
	Promote interdisciplinary approaches by integrating ecology, sociology, anthropology, geography and forestry in risk management policies.		✓	
	Incentivize multifunctional land uses that combine ecological restoration with rural socio-economic development		✓	
	Expand NaiS to include other non-gravitational hazards in specific modules, e.g. wildfires, floods, and how to incorporate them in multi-risk assessments			✓
	Pilot multi-hazard risk scenarios using PROTECTpraxis and existing hazard maps			✓
	Integrate local and traditional knowledge in NbS design through participatory advisory bodies and training initiatives		✓	
Community and stakeholder engagement	Increase public awareness of fire-smart practices by investing in grassroots campaigns involving schools, youth, and local organizations to build trust, empowerment, and social cohesion.		✓	
	Facilitate collective land management by fostering the creation of forest owner associations for fire prevention		✓	

10. Conclusions and discussions

Key findings

The analysis of the three case studies, Valencia, Ogliastra and Bern, offers valuable insights into the enablers and barriers of NbS implementation for multi-risk DRR, highlighting critical considerations for practitioners and policymakers. When aggregated, the most commonly cited barrier across the cases is the lack of supportive policy or legal frameworks, followed by threats to biodiversity and climate, limited expertise or knowledge, and challenges related to maintenance (Fig. 15). Interestingly, the most frequently mentioned enabler mirrors the top barrier: the presence of enabling policies and legal structures. Other significant enablers include access to funding and financial tools, political will and long-term commitment, and robust evidence on performance and co-benefits (Fig. 16).

While these aggregated patterns are valuable, it is essential to acknowledge the case-specific nature of many findings due to differing socio-ecological and institutional contexts. For instance, supportive legal frameworks are key enablers in Bern and Ogliastra but play a minor role in Valencia. Conversely, access to financial tools is prominent in Bern and Valencia but less relevant in Ogliastra. In contrast, the role of expertise and knowledge varies: while it is a top enabler in Ogliastra, it represents a major gap in Valencia, indicating a critical barrier rather than a strength.

Figure 15: Frequency and classification of identified barriers to Nature-based Solutions. Aggregate from the three case studies.

Figure 16: Frequency and classification of identified enablers to Nature-based Solutions. Aggregate from the three case studies.

In Valencia, the progressive (even if slow) implementation of NbS demonstrates their potential in urban contexts. However, their long-term effectiveness and public perception seem significantly hindered by a lack of technical knowledge and specialized expertise for design, implementation and maintenance, alongside path dependency on established practices. Furthermore, limited political will and long-term commitment, coupled with administrative and sectoral fragmentation, impede effective progress. Moreover, the city still lacks dedicated planning frameworks and stable financing mechanisms, especially for ongoing maintenance. Strengthening local resilience requires anticipating cascading risks through long-term strategies. To ensure continuity amid political shifts, it is essential to institutionalize climate adaptation and mitigation through stable entities, such as municipal innovation platforms (e.g., Las Naves) and strategic plans that transcend electoral cycles. While stable financing mechanisms are crucial, the case of Valencia also highlights that fostering social acceptance and promoting shared responsibility through the engagement of local champions, including organized civil society, committed professionals, and foundations, coupled with targeted communication and awareness strategies, are critical enablers.

In Ogliastro, despite evidence of local willingness (from agro-livestock operators) to engage in wildfire risk reduction initiatives, the absence of clear funding pathways and mechanisms for cost-sharing, constrains community-led action. Fuel management for fire prevention purposes is applied only and partially in public forest areas, responding to some but not all fire-smart management criteria. In private forest ownership or at municipal level, other types of fire-smart management options (e.g., fuel management in strategic areas through grazing), although recognised as strategic, are limited due to financial resource and operational and administrative difficulties. This highlights the need for more active and integrated management of the territory

and its forests to effectively prevent wildfires, addressing challenges and the need to balance ecological, economic, and social needs.

In Bern, the long-established nature of protection forests has led to protection forests being well subsidized and supported by a strong legal framework. Nevertheless, stakeholders expressed concerns about the resilience of these forests in the face of climate change-induced disturbances, such as storms and bark beetle outbreaks. In particular, the lack of workforce capacity, and expert knowledge on forest dynamics, and tensions between forestry and hazard management professionals pose barriers to integrated planning. The multifunctionality of protection forests, particularly their contributions to biodiversity and climate co-benefits, was widely recognized as a major enabler. The forthcoming Protect Praxis guidelines are anticipated to be a valuable tool for recognising these co-benefits more systematically and enabling cross-sectoral evaluation. Yet, their successful implementation will depend on building shared understanding and technical capacity across disciplines.

Limitations

While findings from the three case studies in this report provide valuable insights, it is important to recognize that they cannot be generalized across other NbS contexts. This work had the objective to provide insights into governance institutions, procedures, and other factors that have enabled or hindered NbS within each specific socio-economic, political and ecological context. Although case studies can indeed help draw cross-case insights that inform existing theory and evidence on NbS governance, differences in temporal focus (ex-post, ex-ante and during NbS implementation) further limits cross-case compatibility.

The NbS enablers and barriers identified from interviews and workshops and described here are not meant to be exhaustive, but rather to provide subjective insights based on an inclusive sampling of stakeholders. Likewise, we acknowledge that accounts of what is perceived as an enabler or a barrier for NbS implementation vary, influenced by individual viewpoints, priorities and values. It is shaped by personal, professional, or sectoral contexts (Diaz et al., 2015; Pascual et al., 2023). The potential for sectoral overrepresentation in the interviews could also introduce biases in the findings. In fact, the small samples' size limited the ability to examine vulnerable groups in depth. Future research is needed to better incorporate considerations of equity and inclusiveness in NbS governance. Acknowledging these limitations is essential for a transparent and accurate interpretation of the results and for guiding future research efforts.

Future work

Building upon the insights from the three case studies, several key areas for future research and policy development emerge as critical for advancing the effective integration of NbS into multi-risk DRR, particularly in Europe.

In urban contexts like Valencia, priorities include establishing robust long-term planning and financing mechanisms to support NbS implementation and maintenance, while enhancing public visibility. Future research should explore innovative financial models, such as participatory budgeting, maintenance-linked subsidies, and public-private partnerships to improve governance transparency and build citizen trust. Strategic communication and engagement frameworks are also essential to foster civic involvement and position NbS as reliable, lasting solutions. Moreover, it is essential to design multidisciplinary, periodically updated manuals that incorporate ecological, technical, and social perspectives within a multi-risk, adaptive framework. Additionally, efforts should support a specialized NbS market through incentives, dedicated procurement channels, and quality assurance mechanisms like certified supplier registries. Integrating ecosystem-based

assessments early in projects can improve the relevance, multifunctionality, and resilience of urban NbS.

Findings from the case study of Ogliastro point to the potential of community-led fire risk reduction through traditional land-use systems. In this case, future research should explore co-financing models, legal frameworks, and institutional mechanisms that could enable cost and responsibility-sharing between regional governments and land users. Further efforts are also needed for the design and effectiveness of fire-smart mosaic landscapes, including spatial prioritization methods for grazing and vegetation management. Finally, interdisciplinary studies that examine the role of social memory, rural knowledge systems, and trust in institutions will be critical for understanding how to scale and sustain these initiatives.

While the case of Bern highlights the maturity of protection forest policy, it also reveals a gap in anticipatory climate adaptation strategies for forest-based risk mitigation under increasing disturbance regimes. More work is needed to develop adaptive silvicultural models that maintain protective functions while enhancing biodiversity and resilience. This also calls for longitudinal studies that assess how evolving threats like drought and pest outbreaks alter forest structure and function over time.

Across all three cases, there is clear and consistent need to strengthen cross-sectoral and cross-stakeholder collaboration, polycentric governance arrangements, and interdisciplinary capacity, echoing EU's emphasis on integrated capacity. Addressing these needs involves developing training programs, shared planning tools, and harmonized risk assessments that incorporate ecological, engineering, and social science perspectives. Tools such as PROTECTpraxis offer a valuable opportunity to assess how integrated methodologies influence decision-making processes in practice, and whether they lead to more robust, inclusive, and ecologically grounded risk governance.

However, our findings also illustrate how institutional silos and fragmented mandates hinder effective multi-risk DRR, despite growing policy support for integrated approaches. Addressing these challenges requires exploring models of institutional integration, such as dedicated coordination units, cross-sectoral planning forums, and shared accountability frameworks. It's particularly important to examine how actors from biodiversity, forestry, civil protection, and planning can co-manage NbS addressing multiple hazards. However, while the case studies touch on stakeholder tensions and governance fragmentation, other critical factors such as power asymmetries, institutional inertia and lock-ins that shape NbS implementation (e.g., who benefits, who bears the costs), though relevant in multi-risk governance contexts, were not addressed and warrant future exploration. At the same time, operational tools for evaluating NbS across interacting hazards (e.g., fire–erosion, drought–heat–flood) remain limited. Tools like PROTECTpraxis show potential but must be tested and refined in real-world settings, with particular attention to usability, data integration, and compatibility with existing hazard mapping systems.

In conclusion, moving from policy ambitions to implementation requires not only technical innovations, but also new forms of governance that are adaptive, inclusive, and responsive to complex, multi-risk realities. Future work should focus on how to build such governance systems, recognizing the ecological complexity of NbS, the institutional fragmentation of DRR, and the critical role of local actors in sustaining these solutions over time.

11. References

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12. Appendices

Appendix A - Literature-based summary of barriers and enablers to NbS in Valencia, Spain

- **Barriers**

Cluster	Description
Lack of expertise and knowledge	This barrier is considered to have low relevance for the case study of Valencia. The city of Valencia has collaborated with research groups and universities in the past years both directly as administration and using the publicly funded local innovation centre of 'Las Naves'. Recently our research group has collaborated with the Valencian municipality in the elaboration of the first Sustainable Drainage Systems manual for València (guide in Spanish). The city has been chosen as the European Green Capital for 2024 and has extensive experience in implementing green infrastructures.
Lack of evidence on NbS performance and co-benefits	This barrier is considered to have low relevance for the case study of Valencia as it is related to "lack of expertise and knowledge". The city of Valencia has extensive experience in the implementation of green infrastructures.
Stakeholder conflicts and equity	Barrier with high importance for the city of Valencia depending on the NbS implemented. Parks and green areas have a cooling effect on the sites where they are implemented. However, the value of housing tends to increase in neighbourhoods where green areas are put in place. Communities with fewer resources may be affected by this price increase. Additionally, parks and green areas often require substantial space, which could otherwise be used for other essential functions.
Lack and complexity of financing	Securing funding and coordinating between administrative bodies is complex in Valencia and can slow down the implementation of NbS projects. Moreover, short-term budgets and lack of long-term vision from the policy sector further complicate progress.
Lack of supportive policy and/or legal frameworks	Lack of coordination between administrations at the different scales and the lack of coordination for financing or maintaining NbS may hinder their implementation.
Sectoral and/or administrative silos	The lack of coordination between the departments of the municipality limits the effective integration of the functions of the different agents in order to achieve the established objectives. NbS implemented along the coast require coordination between different administrations and can further complicate the effective implementation of these projects.
Land ownership and availability	Competition for space is a major barrier in Valencia, especially in the implementation of parks and green areas that require substantial space.
Lack of political will and long term commitment	Many of the benefits (and co-benefits) of NbS are not immediate. The short-sighted vision of the government may result in a lack of investment in these types of projects.
Maintenance challenges	NbS require maintenance to be effective and to avoid negative effects. The maintenance of green areas must be considered in the total cost. In addition,

	Valencia's current drought issues pose challenges, as many of the green infrastructures require irrigation.
Potential negative impacts	Implementing NbS may unintentionally lead to adverse effects, such as accidents (e.g. break up of branches), attracting undesired animals (e.g. mosquitos), or creating a sense of insecurity if green areas in parks are not adequately maintained, for example at night. Moreover, green areas can also exacerbate allergies in sensitive populations. Green spaces could also become habitats for invasive species such as Kramer's conures (<i>Psittacula krameri</i>) (already present in Valencia), damaging agriculture, native vegetation and wildlife.

● **Enablers**

Cluster	Description
Stakeholder engagement and equity	Participatory processes from the early stages of NbS design and implementation are necessary to ensure the effectiveness and equity of the NbS. In addition, the processes increase the awareness and knowledge of participants.
Evidence on performance and co-benefits	Monetary evaluation of NbS co-benefits can facilitate decision-making and help convince policymakers and citizens of their benefits and co-benefits.
Expertise and knowledge	Careful design and a holistic, systemic view are necessary to maximise the co-benefits of NbS and to avoid negative effects.
Polycentric and cross-sectoral arrangements	NbS affect various stakeholders with diverse risk perception, values, and interests. In addition, large-scale projects require coordination between different administrations. Therefore, fostering integration, communication, and coordination between agents, administrations, and sectors can facilitate the implementation of NbS.
Funding and financial tools and support	The private sector can play an important role in the implementation of NbS, particularly in the case of large-scale projects.
Communication and raising awareness	Raising awareness through campaigns and participatory processes is essential to ensure acceptance of the NbS. Communication throughout the NbS implementation process also increases the acceptance of NbS measures.
Political will and long-term commitments	Political will and long-term commitment are closely related to the generation of awareness.
Aesthetics	Aesthetic NbS lead to better acceptance and can improve economic sectors such as tourism.

Appendix B – Literature-based summary of barriers and enablers to Wildfire risk management in Ogliastra, Italy

The following two tables present a brief summary of key barriers and enablers influencing the implementation of NbS in the Sardinia island. This information has been gathered from the peer-reviewed literature, workshops, discussion sessions with relevant stakeholders, and previous DRR projects in the region.

- **Barriers**

Clusters	Description
Lack of expertise and knowledge	<p>Forest management activities in Sardinia collide with a significant cultural problem linked to the absolute belief that cutting down (managing) the forest is always negative. This perception stems from intergenerational cultural erosion and the gradual loss of forest culture: “the relations with rural/forest areas are no longer defined due to depopulation and no longer perceived as elements capable of conditioning social and economic life” (Branca et al., 2020). Furthermore, lack of expertise and knowledge also affects management decisions.</p>
Stakeholder conflicts and equity	<p>Forest management activities, including those related to fire risk, involve different entities and a wide range of objectives. Management must also consider that, in Mediterranean complex systems, where agriculture interpenetrates with the forest, the number of stakeholders increases, raising numerous conflicts in management planning. Managing the territory and natural resources can give rise to conflicts among various social actors, such as farmers, environmentalists, landowners, local authorities. In some cases, these conflicts can escalate and even result in deliberate fires. Deliberate fires can have various motives, ranging from economic interests, revenge, politics, extremist views, or personal objectives for modifying the landscape (Ortega et al., 2012). Research indicates that deliberate fires often relate to work conflicts (Leone et al., 2009) and socio-economic factors (Lovreglio et al., 2010; Canepa & Drogo, 2021).</p> <p>The use of prescribed fires remains a controversial topic. However, it is already employed for multiple and integrated objectives in many geographical areas. In Italy, prescribed burning needs to be better studied and applied. A lack of collaboration and integration among the different disciplines or sectors involved in wildfire management hinders effective solutions to this complex and interdisciplinary problem. Moreover, the legal prohibition of traditional fire use can result in illegal burnings, which may trigger large-scale forest fires (Tedim et al., 2015).</p> <p>Conflicts can also arise from perception bias and attribution of responsibility. Several studies indicate farmers tend to believe that fires are mainly caused deliberately, emphasising the role of economic interests and local conflicts. The most cited causes of fires have been linked to financial claims or disputes, and the farmers could blame seasonal or forestry workers involved in fire suppression activities (Richelmy Tommaso, 2021). Additionally, farmers may criticise authorities for lacking resources and concrete actions in preventing and controlling fires.</p> <p>Another criticism is directed towards current environmental regulations establishing protected areas where most agricultural activities are prohibited or challenging to authorise; thus, environmental laws may be perceived as inadequate. Less relevance is attributed by farmers to unintentional fires linked to recreational activities (Richelmy Tommaso, 2021). Finally, the role of perception of fire ignition associated with the</p>

	<p>careless disposal of cigarettes is perceived as minimal, in line with what was observed by Lovreglio et al. (2010).</p> <p>To address these challenges, there is an urgent need to develop a dialogue between stakeholders, researchers and local communities. Greater involvement of local administrations, volunteers, schools, and private operators in agriculture and forestry is essential.</p>
Lack and complexity of financing	<p>Many stakeholders voiced concern about the adequacy of funds for forest management. Fundings for the forest compendiums envisaged by the Sardinia Rural Development Plan (PSR) of the Sardinia Region are often diverted in favour of the agricultural and zootechnical sectors. Furthermore, the different financing instruments are managed by distinct regional authorities that appear to lack adequate communication and fail to coordinate effectively to address the territory's needs.</p> <p>According to multiple stakeholders, implementing the territorial forest plans requires the elaboration of numerous documents, which is highly time-consuming for private owners. Simplified procedures accompanying funding applications are considered necessary.</p>
Lack of supportive policy and/or legal frameworks	<p>There is a common perception in the region that local administrations do not adequately participate in fire prevention good practices. In previous projects, stakeholders highlighted a lack of integration between regional forestry planning and environmental and urban planning, particularly regarding the potential effects of climate change and the need for specific adaptation and prevention actions.</p>
Sectoral and/or administrative silos	<p>In Ogliastra, there is a lack of a comprehensive vision for the integrated and sustainable management of the entire territory, extending beyond just wooded areas and addressing more than just summer emergency situations.</p>
Lack of political will and long term commitment	<p>Lack of political will and long term commitment are gaps often representing underlying obstacles and bureaucratic inefficiencies. In the framework of the MED4HUB project, these gaps were identified as the main criticalities in the forest management sector in Sardinia. Legislative and political inconsistency is considered significant, as addressing the "institutional levers" could lead to the formulation of more effective and efficient policies and programs for managing forest resources. Additionally, implementing a joint planning strategy between the agricultural and forestry sectors could activate "profitability levers", leading to improvements in the economic situation of the forestry sector.</p>

● **Enablers**

Clusters	Description
Stakeholder engagement and equity	<p>Due to their complex nature, forest fires require the attention and cooperation of all relevant stakeholders to be effectively prevented and managed. Greater participation through co-creation and co-design can build a relationship of trust between stakeholders and local/regional governance and also increase individual and local community awareness.</p>
Evidence on performance and co-benefits	<p>Providing evidence on the performance of NbS in fire management is crucial for supporting local governments and practitioners in designing, planning, and implementing effective solutions. It plays a key role in raising awareness among stakeholders by highlighting the multifunctionality and potential co-benefits of these measures, ultimately increasing their acceptance.</p> <p>In Ogliastra, quantitative targets and indicators for tracking NbS fire-related performance have been previously simulated using advanced fire models. Qualitative indicators have also been integrated and linked to final simulations and maps. These results offer modeled evidence of NbS effectiveness, which will be evaluated and discussed with local stakeholders to foster understanding and support for these strategies.</p>

	<p>Further simulations using next-generation fire models will develop quantitative targets and indicators to track NbS fire-related performance. Additional qualitative indicators may also be included and associated with final simulations and maps. These results can offer modelled evidence of the performance and possible co-benefit of NBS fire-related performance, potentially assisting local governments and practitioners in the design, planning and perhaps, the implementation of these solutions. Results will also be illustrated and evaluated with local stakeholders to raise awareness and shed new light on the multifunctionality of activities so that they are increasingly acceptable.</p>
Expertise and knowledge	<p>The transfer and dissemination of knowledge on climate change, fire risk and NbS as forest management tools to mitigate risk represents a fundamental element to overcome obstacles in the acceptance of certain practices.</p>
Polycentric and cross-sectoral arrangements	<p>Cross-sectoral arrangements offer a strong alternative to the current "siloed" governance and are important in the context of NbS for fire risk management. Since fire risk management is interconnected with agricultural practices, sustainable forest management, urban planning, and energy and climate strategies, it requires cooperation and collaboration among stakeholders from various sectors and scales.</p>
Funding and financial tools and support	<p>In DEM 8, as in the rest of Sardinia, financial tools and support are essential. In previous experiences, stakeholders highlighted the need for a new, coordinated forestry and rural policy that dialogues between sectors. This policy should include multifunctional measures aimed at both public and private entities to implement cultural interventions that address and mitigate the factors contributing to fire risk.</p>
Communication and awareness raising awareness	<p>Previous experiences have demonstrated the need for community engagement through targeted communication activities. These include using new media, conducting environmental education activities in schools with tailored learning tools, and employing training approaches to clearly and effectively communicate the challenges of climate change and the phenomenon of fires. Additionally, communication campaigns should actively involve regional and local communication bodies to improve their ability to provide correct, non-superficial information based on technical-scientific knowledge. Building on this, DEM8 plans to implement participatory processes involving citizens and stakeholders in the development and execution of adaptation plans. This will include sharing good practices, comparing national experiences, and fostering the creation of local communities dedicated to territorial protection. These efforts will also explore new financing instruments to support sustainable management.</p>
Champions and advocates	<p>Forerunners, early adopters, and agents of change are crucial to engaging local communities. In DEM8, some public agencies (e.g., Agenzia Forestas, CFVA, Civil Protection) will be involved as expert aggregators in the co-design, development and implementation of forestry sector projects, including those related to fire-risk mitigation.</p>
Political will and long-term commitments	<p>In Italy, current legislative innovations in the forestry sector, such as the national and regional forest law, reflect "greater institutional and social sensitivity". Notably, the recently issued National Forest Strategy (Jan 2022) aims at creating extensive and resilient forests, rich in biodiversity, and capable of contributing to climate change mitigation and adaptation. It seeks to support the generation of ecological, social and economic benefits, particularly for rural and mountain communities, but also for citizens and future generations. One of the three main objectives of the National Forest Strategy is to promote sustainable forest management and recognize the multifunctional role of forests, emphasizing biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation and adaptation.</p>

Appendix C - List of interviewees and workshop participants

Interviewee / participants Number	DEM	Sector	Age / age group*	Gender*	Date of Interview	Interviewer / facilitator (workshop)
O1	8	Regional Government (Institutional and Operational Actor)	55	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O2	8	Regional Forestry Agency (Institutional and Operational Actor)	59	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O3	8	Civil Protection Volunteer (Institutional and Operational Actor)	68	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O4	8	Civil Protection Volunteer (Institutional and Operational Actor)	34	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O5	8	Environmental Volunteer Organization (Institutional and Operational Actor)	40	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O6	8	State Forestry Corps (Institutional and Operational Actor)	58	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O7	8	Emergency Medical Services (Institutional and Operational Actor)	85	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O8	8	Civil Protection Volunteer Association (Institutional and Operational Actor)	49	F	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O9	8	Civil Protection Volunteer Association (Institutional and Operational Actor)	70	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O10	8	State Forestry Corps (Institutional and Operational Actor)	56	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O11	8	Municipal Administration (Institutional and Operational Actor)	47	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu

O12	8	State Forestry Corps (Institutional and Operational Actor)	64	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O13	8	Fire and Rescue Service (Institutional and Operational Actor)	61	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O14	8	Regional Forestry Agency (Institutional and Operational Actor)	63	F	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O15	8	Regional Forestry Agency (Institutional and Operational Actor)	36	F	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O16	8	Regional Civil Protection (Institutional and Operational Actor)	57	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O17	8	Civil Protection Volunteer (Institutional and Operational Actor)	47	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O18	8	Municipal Administration (Institutional and Operational Actor)	47	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O19	8	Municipal Administration (Institutional and Operational Actor)	25	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O20	8	Agro-livestock operators	32	F	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O21	8	Agro-livestock operators	31	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O22	8	Agro-livestock operators	47	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O23	8	Agro-livestock operators	24	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O24	8	Agro-livestock operators	49	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O25	8	Agro-livestock operators	27	F	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu

O26	8	Agro-livestock operators	34	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O27	8	Agro-livestock operators	60	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O28	8	Agro-livestock operators	54	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O29	8	Agro-livestock operators	53	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O30	8	Agro-livestock operators	48	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O31	8	Agro-livestock operators	NA	F	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O32	8	Agro-livestock operators	30	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O33	8	Agro-livestock operators	21	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O34	8	Agro-livestock operators	33	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O35	8	Agro-livestock operators	62	M	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O36	8	Agro-livestock operators	32	F	09/11/2023	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O37	8	Tourist operators: campsite and hotel owners, agritourism facilities	NA	NA	27/09/2024	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O38	8	Tourist operators: campsite and hotel owners, agritourism facilities	NA	NA	27/09/2024	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O39	8	Tourist operators: campsite and hotel owners, agritourism facilities	NA	NA	27/09/2024	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu

O40	8	Tourist operators: campsite and hotel owners, agritourism facilities	NA	NA	27/09/2024	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
O41	8	Tourist operators: campsite and hotel owners, agritourism facilities	NA	NA	27/09/2024	Alessio Menini / Valentina Bacciu
B1	10	Academia & research	40-50	M	27/02/2024	Juliette Martin
B2	10	Cantonal authority	40-50	M	22/08/2024	Juliette Martin
B3	10	Private sector (forestry)	50-60	M	05/09/2024	Juliette Martin
B4	10	Private sector (natural hazard management and risk assessment)	50-60	M	05/09/2024	Juliette Martin
B5	10	Academia & research	40-50	F	06/09/2024	Juliette Martin
B6	10	Cantonal authority	40-50	M	12/09/2024	Juliette Martin
B7	10	Academia & research	60-70	M	30/09/2024	Juliette Martin
B8	10	Private sector (natural hazard management and risk assessment)	40-50	F	04/10/2024	Juliette Martin
B9	10	Academia & research	50-60	M	10/10/2024	Juliette Martin
B10	10	Retired, federal authority	70-80	M	24/01/2025	Juliette Martin
B11	10	Academia & research	30-40	F	5/11/2024	Juliette Martin
B12	10	Private sector (natural hazard management and risk assessment)	50-60	F	26/11/2025	Juliette Martin

B13	10	Academia & research	50-60	M	02/12/2025	Juliette Martin
B14	10	Education / professional training institute	50-60	M	09/12/2025	Juliette Martin
V1	1	Academia & research	45-54	M	05/06/2024	Ana Fernandez-Garza / Adria Rubio-Martin
V2	1	Academia & research	35-44	M	12/06/2024	Ana Fernandez-Garza / Adria Rubio-Martin
V3	1	Academia & research	35-44	F	18/06/2024	Ana Fernandez-Garza / Adria Rubio-Martin
V4	1	Consultancy	45-54	M	29/07/2024	Ana Fernandez-Garza / Adria Rubio-Martin
V5	1	Former public administration	35-44	F	28/10/2024	Ana Fernandez-Garza / Adria Rubio-Martin
V6	1	Consultancy	35-44	M	03/12/2024	Ana Fernandez-Garza / Adria Rubio-Martin
V7	1	Consultancy	45-54	M	17/12/2024	Adria Rubio-Martin
V8	1	Consultancy	35-44	F	14/01/2025	Ana Fernandez-Garza
V9	1	Association members	45-54/35-44	M/F	16/01/2025	Ana Fernandez-Garza / Adria Rubio-Martin
V10	1	Developer	45-54	M	21/01/2025	Ana Fernandez-Garza
V11	1	Academia & research	35-44	F	21/01/2025	Ana Fernandez-Garza

*Note: "NA" indicates Not Available. No information was collected regarding age / age group or gender for these individuals.

Appendix D – Interview protocol: NbS in Valencia

Name of the interviewer:
Name of the interviewee:
Employer, Department:
Position:

Objectives

The objective of The HuT Project is to demonstrate that nature-based solutions (also often referred to as green/blue infrastructure) can reduce the risks of extreme weather events, such as heatwaves.

This questionnaire aims to identify the success factors and barriers to implementing nature-based solutions in València. Moreover, it seeks to better understand the opportunities and challenges involved in carrying out the “Green and Biodiversity Plan of València.” Green areas are zones characterized by relatively cooler temperatures, which help reduce heat stress.

Questions:

1. Please briefly describe your role in your organization/workplace.
2. Could you please briefly explain your connection to the “Green and Biodiversity Plan of València”? In what capacity have you been involved?
3. In your view, what types of challenges (e.g. social, environmental) does the plan seek to address?
4. Are you aware of the individuals or entities that initiated the plan? Were there any notable allies or opponents? Were there any notable allies? Was there any opposition?
5. During the drafting, development, and approval of the plan, was there any polarization among stakeholders? If so, between whom, and regarding what issues?
6. What opportunities or benefits do you perceive in relation to the implementation of the plan?
7. Do you believe there are any indirect or secondary benefits that may result from its implementation? If so, which ones?
8. What challenges or potential obstacles do you foresee in its implementation?
9. In your opinion, does the current version of the plan exclude any key green spaces or areas of biodiversity that are important for the city? If so, which ones?
10. Are there any neighbourhoods not currently included in the plan that you believe warrant priority attention? Why?
11. Do you consider the long-term financial sustainability of the plan to be viable?
12. In your opinion, which project implemented under the plan has been the most successful and could serve as a model? What factors contributed to its success?
13. Conversely, which has been the least successful project that could serve as a cautionary example? Why?
14. Which nature-based solutions do you think hold the most potential for success in València?

15. What key obstacles do you perceive for the adoption of nature-based solutions in València? (e.g., in their concept and underlying philosophy, design and planning, implementation and post-implementation, political support)
16. In your opinion, which phase of implementing nature-based solutions presents the greatest difficulty? (e.g., conceptualization, planning and design, execution, or maintenance and follow-up)
17. Would you be open to being contacted after this interview for any follow-up questions or to verify certain points?
18. Is there another individual you would recommend we speak with in the context of this research?

Demographic data:

Age group: 18–24, 25–34, 35–44, 45–54, 55–64, 65–74, 75+

Education background: Ecology, Biology, Economics, Engineering, Environmental Sciences, Landscape Planning, Urban Planning, Social Sciences, Political Sciences, Other:

Highest degree completed: Bachelor's, Master's, Diploma, Doctorate, Other

Sex: F / M

Appendix E – Interview protocol: Biological measures and Nature-based Solutions in Switzerland

Interview protocol: Biological measures and nature-based solutions in Switzerland

Introduction and background

Thank you for the interview. The aim of The Hut project is to demonstrate that nature-based solutions can reduce the risks of extreme weather events such as landslides. The University of Geneva together with the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) are leading a project on nature-based solutions and biological measures in Switzerland. We see biological measures as anything that is related to vegetation (according to the protect praxis definition) and NBS as the broader terms that includes vegetation but also river restorations for example.

Based on case studies, we want to find out through interviews what success factors and obstacles there are for nature-based solutions in Switzerland. If you are interested, we will be happy to inform you about the results of this research project.

Our interviews are for scientific purposes only and will be anonymized. In general, all data collected is subject to strict data protection regulations (as described in the data protection form you have received).

Do you agree with your answers being recorded? This makes it easier to take notes, so I can be sure that I don't leave out anything important. The recording can also be interrupted at any time. The interview will last around 45 minutes.

Interview questions

Biological measures / Protect Praxis

1. Can you briefly tell us about how your work relates to nature-based solutions?
2. Have you heard about biological measures guidelines / PROTECT Praxis project in Switzerland?

If **YES**:

3. What were the key success factors (or enablers) that led to the development of the guidelines?
4. In your opinion, what potential changes can these guidelines bring about? What will their impact be?
5. What are the disadvantages or possible obstacles that you see for their implementation?

If **NO**:

Protection forests

There is a long history of using protective forests to protect people, assets and infrastructure in Switzerland.

6. How are protection forests implemented in Switzerland: who are the different actors that are involved in their designation, protection and maintenance?
7. In your opinion, what have been the key factors in the success of protection forests in Switzerland (from a legal point of view)?
8. What are the main challenges regarding the conservation and management of protection forests in Switzerland?

9. In areas exposed to natural hazards, how is it usually decided whether a protection forest can guarantee protection or whether a structural measure is needed?
10. What research has been conducted so far on forest policy (main strands of research) in Switzerland? Are there any research gaps that still need to be addressed?

Protection forests for multi-hazards

When several natural hazards occur at the same time, we speak of multi-risks. If these processes reinforce each other, it is a cascading effect. An example of this would be an earthquake that triggers landslides.

11. Are multi-risks and cascading effects taken into account in the development of biological measures? If not, why?
12. In your opinion, what role could biological measures play for multi-risks and cascading effects? (what advantage do they have compared to grey infrastructure)
13. How are such risks currently taken into account in risk management by the Federal Office for the Environment (BAFU) and the cantons?

The multifunctionality of forests allows them to protect people from multiple types of disasters and risks.

14. How is this multi-functionality managed from a legal perspective (*how do the different relevant actors coordinate*)?
15. How are priorities set, e.g. between biodiversity goals, disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation goals?

Wildfire risk and management (optional)

16. What are currently the main measures for preventing and/or minimizing forest fires in Switzerland?
17. In your opinion, what are the greatest challenges (for the prevention and/or minimization of forest fires in Switzerland)?

Conclusion

18. Is it possible for me to contact you after the interview if I have further questions and/or want to confirm something in my notes?
19. Can you think of other people I should contact for this research project?

Demographics

Employer, department:

Job title:

Age group: 18-24; 25-34; 35-44; 45-54; 55-64; 65-74; 75 or older

Education: ecology; biology; economics; engineering landscape planning; environmental science; political science, social science; other

Highest education: Matura; Bachelor; Master; Diploma studies; Doctorate; other

Gender: F / M / other

Thank you for your insights and your time! Would you like to be informed when our report is completed? (approx. end of 2025?)

